

**An exploration of how university lecturers construct their
knowledge of information and digital literacy**

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Abstract

Where attempts have been made to measure digital competence, the focus has been on students and based on small, unrepresentative samples (Connaway *et al.*, 2017). Comparative work in university lecturers is in its infancy. This lack of knowledge hinders the ability of universities to develop lecturers to teach in increasingly digital and blended curricula (European Commission, 2020).

Utilising a contextual constructionism methodology (Nichols, 2015), my Professional Doctorate research aimed to explore the competencies that university lecturers require to be digitally competent. I began by exploring how digital competence is associated with information literacy, as related to university lecturers, by using a framework (Secker and Coonan, 2011) as a lens. My analysis provided a unique lecturer-focussed perspective on information literacy.

I then convened workshops with an expert group of librarians, learning technologists, and lecturers, key stakeholders in information and digital literacy, and curricula and lecturer development. The workshops aimed to form a multi-professional understanding of the digital competencies relevant to university lecturers through an information literacy lens. This novel approach to investigating digital competence revealed that multi-professional groups of librarians, learning technologists, and lecturers cannot agree on the digital competencies that relate to information literacy.

To deepen my understanding of why there was no agreement between workshop groups, I undertook in-depth interviews with eight lecturers to explore how they construct their knowledge of information and digital literacy. Using a thematic analysis method (Braun and Clarke, 2006), I revealed unique insights into this new field of research, concluding that lecturer construction of digital competence is still at an embryonic stage. Most lecturers struggled with the language of digital competence and information literacy as described in frameworks.

My findings have implications for researchers trying to assess digital competence in university lecturers and for framework developers and those utilising them. These findings pose challenges for universities implementing digital strategies, and for professional service staff involved in curricula and lecturer related training and development.

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Dissemination of research findings

Cannon, P. (2017) A review of professionalism within LIS. *Library Management*, 38(2/3), pp. 142-152. doi: [10.1108/LM-07-2016-0053](https://doi.org/10.1108/LM-07-2016-0053) [Professional Doctorate assignment, not explicitly thesis related but contextualises my professional background]

Cannon, P. (2018) What Skills do Lecturers Require to be Considered Digitally Competent? (from the UWS Annual Learning, Teaching and Research Conference 2018, Paisley, UK, 27-28 June 2018).

Cannon, P. (2018) Ethics and the Role of PKSB in Research. (from the CILIPS Autumn Gathering 2018, Glasgow, UK, 24 Oct 2018).
<http://eprints.gla.ac.uk/171941/1/171941.pdf> [Professional Doctorate reflection. Not explicitly thesis related but contextualises my professional background]

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https://www.slideshare.net/infolit_group/exploring-how-university-lecturers-construct-their-knowledge-of-information-and-digital-literacy-paul-cannon

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Author's declaration

I declare that, except where explicit reference is made to the contribution of others, that this thesis is the result of my own work and has not been submitted for award at any other institution.

Terminology and definitions

There are three main terms that are used consistently throughout this thesis: information literacy, digital literacy, and digital competence. For the purpose of this thesis, I will define these terms as follows:

Information literacy

Information literacy “comprises the competencies to recognize information needs and to locate, evaluate, apply and create information within cultural and social contexts” (from the Alexandria Proclamation on Information Literacy and Lifelong Learning by the International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions (2005, n.p.))

Digital literacy

Digital literacy is “the ability to understand and use information in multiple formats from a wide range of sources when it is presented via computers”. Given the changes in technology over the proceeding 25 years, I will substitute “computers” for “digital devices”. (from The United Nations Educational Scientific and Cultural Organization (n.d., n.p.) who use Gilster's (1997) definition of digital literacy)

Digital competence

Digital competence is the “situational embedding” and “appropriate application of [digital] skills... within life situations” (adapted from Nelson, Courier and Joseph, 2011 (p.104-105))

1 Introduction

The purpose of this study is to develop a benchmark of digital competence within a university lecturer population.

Digital competence is an ambiguous term that has yet to be properly defined in the academic literature. A lack of definition is not helped by the various conceptual constructions of digital literacy (Knobel and Lankshear, 2006). The predominant theory in digital competence is that of Prensky's (2001) digital native and digital immigrant, whereby today's students are technologically fluent or "digital natives", whilst older generations are "digital immigrants" who reach for a print book rather than use an internet search engine. This theory persists within universities despite these perceptions being challenged within the literature (White and Le Cornu, 2011).

Where attempts have been made to measure digital competence, the focus has been on students and based on small, unrepresentative samples (Connaway *et al.*, 2013). There is a large gap in the literature on the digital competencies of lecturers. This study will take a multi-professional approach to defining the competencies that university lecturers need to become digitally competent using four distinct phases.

This research study will take place within two UK universities; one a million+ institution and the other a Russell Group institution. The thesis is written from the perspective of a librarian employed by a UK university.

In this chapter, I will introduce digital literacy in a university context and reflect on my personal and professional background to further contextualise the study. I will reflect on the research journey and the initial aims and objectives of the study, before concluding with an explanation of the structure of the thesis.

1.1 The importance of digital literacy

Digital literacy has been of growing interest to the education and business sectors for the last two decades. The United Nations Educational Scientific and Cultural Organization (n.d., n.p.) use Gilster's 1997 definition of digital literacy as "the ability to understand and use information in multiple formats from a wide range of sources when it is presented via computers". Within UK universities Jisc, who arguably have led developments in the sector, define digital literacies as "the capabilities which fit someone for living, learning and working in a digital society" (Jisc, 2015, n.p.). The

terms digital literacy, capacity, competency and ability are used synonymously (Goodfellow, 2011), leading to a conflation in the use of etymologically different terminology. For example, digital competence has been described as the successful application of digital literacy in real world scenarios (Nelson, Courier and Joseph, 2011), or the “skill, ability, and knowledge to successfully use computers, their related applications, and software” (Maderick *et al.*, 2016, p. 329).

Goodfellow (2011) and Lea (2013) note that digital literacy is framed within socio-cultural practices. In universities, academic literacies are contextualised within specific disciplines. Therefore, it follows that there are no reasons why digital literacy may not also be adopted and adapted to different academic disciplines. With an emerging epistemological knowledge base, social-cultural settings define digital literacy in each university; digital literacy is also applied differently depending on professional use. There is, for example, computer literacy (the technology itself), ICT literacy (use of technology), and information literacy (library and information science) (Kenton and Blummer, 2010). The boundaries of professional literacies merge into other professional areas; media, academic, and meta-literacies. Information literacies, to Goldstein (2013) at least, are most often associated with librarians and information professionals, and librarians are often the starting point for academics looking to use information and digital literacy in their courses (Anderson, 2011). However, Goldstein (2013) also notes that librarians cannot solely develop the field of study without other “players” – a recognition, perhaps, of the socio-cultural and multi-professional settings of information and digital literacies.

Due to varying definitions and professional uses of digital literacy, it is very difficult to focus solely on a singular literacy. The opinion of the researcher is that regardless of professional boundaries, digital literacy must only be considered in its plural form, digital literacies. This view is shared by Lankshear and Knobel (2015, p.12) who suggest that digital literacy is not an “autonomous entity” and is instead compiled from a diverse range of “skills and techniques that a proficient person can *do*”.

The complexity in defining digital literacies is not helped as digital, technological and socio-cultural practices are constantly evolving, further adding to the ambiguity of the term itself and its use (Gruszczynska, 2013). Goodfellow (2011), however, summarises by explaining the conflation between literacies and competencies – that,

in real world use, the term digital literacies is synonymous with the digital competencies of individual learners. Whilst this still leaves room for discipline-specific competencies, shaped by socio-cultural practices, there could equally be a defined and measured core set of generic competencies applicable to any individual.

These arguments can be summarised using Figure 1, Jisc's (2015) digital capabilities framework. Each competency is represented by a circle. Each circle represents different professions' epistemological and tacit knowledge. As each circle overlaps all other circles, a core set of competencies and professional knowledge is shared; no profession exclusively owns the knowledge that underpins each competency.

Figure 1. Image from Jisc (2015) Digital capabilities framework illustrating the holistic nature of digital literacy in Venn diagram form

It would appear there is a gap in the literature investigating the work of librarians and information professionals in the field of information and digital competencies, which also encompasses the perspectives of other, interrelated professions. As the introduction has illustrated, the work that has been conducted in this area has not been sufficiently drawn together and critically analysed as one body of literature (Aviram and Eshet-Alkalai, 2006).

1.1.1 Digital literacies in university education

The abundance of digital devices in our lives and the importance of these devices to access resources, from virtual learning environments (VLEs) to business and civic

engagement systems, has led a number of organisations to believe that a lack of digital literacy skills leaves many at a disadvantage (European Commission, 2008). The same dearth of digital skills in the general population has been noted to adversely impact the UK labour market, where employers state that graduates hold digital skills, but not necessarily those required for a work environment (ECORYS UK, 2016). The absence of appropriate digital skills can be linked to academic staff who lack knowledge of the digital workplace, leading to an inability to support students in meeting these graduate attributes (Beetham, 2015); this despite an increasing digital university environment and teaching and learning requirements, which in itself can be a barrier to participation (Miller, 2015).

The overarching hypothesis within university education is that of the “digital native” (Prensky, 2001, p.1). Prensky argues that the current (US) educational system is no longer fit for current students naturalised to digital technology. Older generations who have adapted to the digital world are termed “digital immigrants” – their first step is a print book rather than an internet search engine. Thus, they are “socialized” differently and, as the instructors of natives, struggle “to teach a population that speaks an entirely new language” (Prensky, 2001, p.2). This theory has alarmed lecturers who perceive that the gap between native and immigrant is too large to bridge (White and Le Cornu, 2011). However, many have subsequently challenged those notions and a newer ‘visitors and residents’ theory has emerged.

The visitors and residents approach “hypothesizes that neither age nor gender determines whether a person is a visitor (one who logs on to the virtual environment, performs a specific task or acquires specific information, and then logs off) or a resident (one who has an ongoing, developing presence online)” (Connaway *et al.*, 2013, p.1). Despite new theories and challenges to the digital natives approach, it is still a theory to which many subscribe. The visitors and residents approach to digital competence is also the anecdotal observations of the researcher. It is simply not the case that people born after 1980 are digital competent, whilst those born before that date are deficient.

1.1.2 Student perspectives on digital literacy

Many studies have assessed current educational practices and pedagogies as inadequate for the current university students who expect and demand greater use

of technology in the classroom and assignments (Bulger, Mayer and Metzger, 2014). The expectations that students have of technology use in university education are driven by their experiences in secondary education (Committee of Inquiry into the Changing Learner Experience, 2009). Whilst there is an expectation that universities will provide students with current technology, there is no expectation that academic staff will be digitally competent (White and Wild, 2014). This despite a student preference for technology-enhanced curricula, and the rise of blended (a combination of online and face-to-face teaching) and online learning environments (Mirriahi *et al.*, 2015).

Most of the studies in this field are single case studies with small populations. Where the competencies of students have been measured, self-assessment is used. The extent to which one can draw conclusions as to the digital competencies of students from such methodologies must be questioned. Indeed, in one such survey a Wilcoxon matched-pairs test was used on student pre-service teachers' digital competencies. The results demonstrated a statistically significant over-reporting of digital competency in all self-reported topics tested (Maderick *et al.*, 2016). It is perhaps because both academics and students use technology in their private lives (Alvarez, 2013) that they conflate being able to function on social networks and use personal technology with rounded digital competencies in other literacy areas.

1.1.3 Digital immigrant academic staff

Where student digital competence levels have been widely investigated (Bennett, 2014), albeit often lacking validity and rigour, the same is not true of academic staff who remain an under-researched group. Where patterns have emerged on the digital competencies of students, as well as research into how the curricula can be utilised to enhance their digital competencies, just how competent and willing academic staff are to rise to the challenge of developing digital curricula is not known.

UK-based students report the levels of digital competence amongst academic staff as variable (National Union of Students, 2010), with one in five students noting that lecturers need additional IT training. Although the report has a relatively small sample size, ~500 respondents, the findings resonate with information on the general population (Centre for Economics and Business Research, 2015). In a similar sized survey of students about to enter university education, the authors note

that staff capability with ICT can contribute to a 'digital divide' between students, their expectations, and the actuality of university study. The same survey highlights that staff effectively using technology can enhance student ICT skills (Committee of Inquiry into the Changing Learner Experience, 2009). Both aforementioned reports are predominantly based on secondary data from mixed methods research, although the Changing Learner Experience report did receive oral evidence from sixteen academics, third-sector organisations and educationalists.

Although there are relatively few studies that have deliberately sought to measure the digital competencies of academic staff, some research has looked at early adopters of technology, digital pedagogical practices and the opportunities and barriers to digital change. A narrative inquiry by Cousins and Bissar (2012) emphasises that academics are willing to learn and adapt to new technologies and practices, but find the breadth of resources confusing, and a lack of time to develop existing teaching materials a barrier to adoption. Conversely, in sixteen interviews with the early adopters of technology within an institution, Bennett (2014) notes that "digital practitioners" utilise a range of digital tools, both those available and supported by the institution, for instance VLEs, as well as other technologies, such as social networks and alternate learning platforms. However, a small survey of academics (n=13) found some respondents did not use social networking simply because they lack the digital competency to do so (Al-Aufi and Fulton, 2015). One interesting reflection from Bennett's (2014) interviews is that lecturers will use technology when it assisted their teaching practices, but will reject technology if they questioned its pedagogical value.

The application of a digital pedagogy to the learning outcomes of a course (Committee of Inquiry into the Changing Learner Experience, 2009; Mirriahi *et al.*, 2015) and concerns whether digital technologies are compatible with developing a broad-based subject knowledge (White, Beetham and Wild, 2013) are also noted as barriers for adoption and learning of digital practices amongst lecturers. Lea's (2013) essay notes that lecturers are driven by a subject-based pedagogy, not a need to be digitally competent for competencies sake. In one small case study with sixteen dance lecturers, participants were particularly apprehensive to use blended learning when these activities were linked to assessment (Alvarez, 2013). The same lecturers also failed to embrace digital technology as they were still learning how to develop

online resources for their students whilst adapting to a new role of digital practitioner. In this particular case, staff did not have the time to develop new resources or undertake training despite various training being offered as part of the study. Nevertheless, it has been reflected, in one single-university case study, that in initiatives to develop technology adoption amongst lecturers, progress was slow, lecturers were risk-adverse and teaching practices had not been transformed (Mirriahi *et al.*, 2015).

Despite these reservations and barriers to the development of digital competencies and pedagogies, Bennett (2014), whose sixteen lecturer interviewees were drawn across pure and applied and hard and soft subjects at a UK university, found that many early adopters of technology felt that digital tools were a norm in their academic practices, not a new skillset to learn. Importantly, these “digital practitioners” also understood the pedagogical reasons for and the need to adopt technology within their teaching. Bennett (2014) observes their participants reflect on a student need and interest in technology; they understand the technologies in detail to make the appropriate use of them within their teaching practice and the curricula. Equally, they reflect that digital competencies, intertwined with subject knowledge and pedagogical practices, need to be developed just as much as lecturer and student subject knowledge. However, despite their own awareness of technology and its application to teaching, one interviewee reflected that their own digital skills were not as well developed as their students, but that this did not concern them. This reflection could be true, but may equally indicate the same digital native misconception of millennial students, and illustrate the anxiety barrier to wider-technology adoption amongst academic staff.

By far the largest study of academic staff is a survey with over 4,500 respondents from across the United States (Allen *et al.*, 2012). The survey methodology gives information measures to ensure a representative sample from US universities but has no information on the validity of the survey tool. Nevertheless, the survey indicates that just over half of all academic staff assign e-only textbooks to students, use digital materials in course presentations, and teach a mix of online and blended learning. Whilst this survey is comprehensive in the number of respondents, it only indicates that staff are using digital technologies, rather than using it well or appropriately. There is also no qualitative data that describes why and how

academic staff are using technology within their teaching; it could simply be an acknowledgement that the sector is urging staff to adopt digital technologies and working practices (Cousins and Bissar, 2012; Masterman and Manton, 2011). In a separate US study, Nelson, Courier and Joseph (2011) defined twenty aspects of digital literacy and asked a small group (n=82 response rate) across a single university to rank the aspects in order of importance. Results were filtered by the academic college and degree programme on which the respondents taught. Of interest to this study is that across all colleges, digital information literacies were the top-ranking aspects (mean rank across colleges, 1=information research retrieval, 2=information validation, 3=information communication). Whilst the results were not statistically significant across all degree programmes, and a larger response from one college may have influenced the results, it does show that in this one group of lecturers information literacies rank highly on the spectrum of digital literacies.

As reflected in the introductory section of this literature review, the lack of a definition of digital literacies generally and, more specifically, a definition of digital literacies and their underpinning competencies, has not helped the epistemological consolidation and development of this field of study, or allowed its effective appraisal. Further research is needed in this area, particularly with respect to how the library and information profession can help develop its digital literacy epistemology and its relation to other literacies and professions.

Just as there is a misrepresentation of digitally competent millennial students, the same applies to the perceived deficit of digital competencies amongst lecturers. It must be noted that with one exception, all the studies investigating lecturers are single case studies, with small sample sizes, conducted across one university. This is a problem articulated by Connaway *et al.* (2013, p.2) whose literature review found “no longitudinal research studying individuals’ information use and search behaviours within a contextual framework in the different educational stages”. Further valid and rigorous research is needed to investigate the digital competencies of academic teaching staff if the body of knowledge on student digital competence is to be twinned with that of lecturers.

1.2 Reflexivity

1.2.1 Personal and professional background

In 2015, the University of the West of Scotland (UWS) started a Professional Doctorate programme. I was in the first cohort of students to enter the programme. Prior to the programme being promoted across the university, I had never considered undertaking a doctorate. Until then I only understood a PhD to be the route to doctoral qualification; one that I erroneously believed would require me to give up professional work at a time when I had started to achieve some early career success. Six years earlier, I completed an MSc in Library and Information Science via a distance learning route whilst working full time, a similar model to the Professional Doctorate. The MSc was a positive experience and gave me the chance to reflect and build upon my professional practice whilst giving me a qualification required to move into a professional role in librarianship. This, along with the opportunity to develop my practice-based research and the ability to tackle a professional research problem made the Professional Doctorate an appealing option.

At the start of my Professional Doctorate, I worked as the Social Science Subject Librarian at UWS. I had been in that role for two years and I had become an integral part of the School of Social Sciences; collaborating with School staff to develop teaching programmes and teaching at all levels in each of the programmes delivered across the School. It was my 'embeddedness' that drove my initial research questions: the opportunity to develop curricula with lecturers helped me understand the difficulties that some lecturers have with digital literacy, both conceptually and in developing their own digital competence. My role during these proceedings was, however, always that of the librarian or information specialist. Whilst my interest in digital literacy and competence is holistic, I tend to consider digital literacy through the lens of information literacy, which broadly can be defined as a competency to "recognize information needs and to locate, evaluate, apply and create information within cultural and social contexts" (International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions, 2005).

In 2016, I moved jobs to start work in the University of Glasgow Library. This role has moved me away from day-to-day teaching to a research-focussed role. Nonetheless, I still regularly refer to information and digital literacy frameworks, those at the heart of this research study, using them to anchor my professional practice and referring to

them in discussions with lecturers. I still find myself surprised at how few lecturers – from both universities I have worked in – know of, let alone utilise the frameworks in their teaching and professional development. From a personal professional perspective, I find that information and digital literacy frameworks ground me in my work, reinforcing my sense of professional belonging as a librarian.

1.2.2 Research journey

My Professional Doctorate journey has been a meandering one. By the time of submission, I will have taken seven years to complete the doctorate. Whilst a Professional Doctorate is a part-time degree, when I started this journey, I had not anticipated just how *part-time* my doctorate would be at times. The journey has been long somewhat due to my own phlegmatic dawdling at times but also due to the many personal and professional changes that have occurred over the seven years. The length of time this study has taken has also been impacted by the changes to the study design as a result of the findings at each of the different phases of the research.

I should note that part of the research and subsequent write-up took place during the COVID-19 pandemic. While the pandemic did not overly affect the timeline of the study, the shift to online learning has thrust digital competence to the fore in universities and will naturally affect how participants felt and their responses to the research at that particular time. I reflect further on the digital shift in my conclusions and note how the pandemic affected the methods of the study and how the findings may be interpreted as a result at appropriate points of the thesis.

1.2.3 Writing in the first person

I discuss my methodological position in the next chapter but, briefly, this is a qualitative study that takes a relativist stance. My methodology, contextual constructionism, acknowledges that “knowledge is context specific and influenced by the perspective of the perceiver” (Lyons, 2021, p.242). As such, my central role in the research should be recognised. Additionally, in a Doctorate of Professional Studies thesis, one is expected to reflect upon and explore their professional practice and work-based problems. This thesis and my research journey is, therefore, very personal. Consequently, there is both an alignment with the methodology and typology of this thesis to justify the use of “I” throughout.

1.2.4 Research aim, objectives, and questions

Initially, the overall aim of this research study was to develop a benchmark of digital competence among university lecturers. The objectives were to:

1. compile and critically analyse the existing literature on digital competency,
2. distil the competencies university lecturers need to be digitally competent based on information and digital literacy frameworks [Phase one],
3. carry out workshops to form a multi-professional approach to the competencies university lecturers need to be digitally competent [Phase two],
4. develop identified competencies into a quantitative questionnaire [Initial phase three], and
5. distribute and analyse a questionnaire to lecturers across two university Health Schools to reveal a benchmark of digital competence among lecturers [Initial phase four].

Objectives four and five were not completed due to the findings made at phase two. As such, an additional objective was created to replace initial objectives 4 and 5, Phases three and four. This objective was to:

4. explore the reasons why lecturers, librarians, and learning technologists construct information and digital literacy in dissimilar ways [Phase three].

1.2.4.1 Research questions

Phase one

- How does the 'A new curriculum for information literacy' (ANCIL) framework relate to university lecturers in a UK university context?
- What digital literacy frameworks are in use across a sample of UK universities?

Phase two

- What digital competencies do I feel are relevant to university lecturers, and why?
- Which of these digital competencies do I believe are relevant to information literacy, and why?
- What digital competencies do a multi-professional group of lecturers, learning technologists, and librarians feel are relevant to university lecturers, and why?

- Which of these digital competencies are relevant to information literacy, and why?

Phase three

- How do university lecturers construct their understanding of information literacy facets and digital competencies?
- Does their understanding reveal why lecturers construct these concepts in such a disparate manner?

1.2.5 Thesis structure

As a result of the meandering journey of this study, the thesis has changed, sections discarded, some re-written, and some written anew. The structure of the thesis will, therefore, be presented in a fashion that represents the research phases and journey taken, rather than in the linear structure as envisaged at the start of the research. Each phase of the research will be presented separately, complete with the phase's own objectives, research questions, methods, findings, and discussion. The following methodology chapter, however, applies to all phases of the research.

Chapter three begins with a rapid review of the literature on digital competence in university lecturers, noting further gaps in the literature. Chapter four constitutes phase one of the research. This chapter investigates information literacy as related to university lecturers and discovers which digital literacy frameworks are used in a sample of UK universities.

Chapter five, phase two, uses the information from phase one as materials for workshops with lecturers, librarians, and learning technologists. The workshops were used to form a multi-professional understanding of the digital competencies relevant to university lecturers through an information literacy lens. Chapter six, phase three, uses interviews with lecturers to explore the findings from phase two.

Chapter seven provides reflections on the methodology and aims of the research, followed by a discussion of each phase with respect to their research questions and the extent to which each phase answered those questions. Chapter eight provides conclusions and implications for professional practice for university strategy and policy, university professional services, and for future research and framework developers. I close chapter eight with a summary of the limitations from the research.

2 Methodology

2.1 Introduction to chapter

This study was initially meant to be a mixed methods study using qualitative analysis of digital literacy frameworks, coded and transcribed into a quantitative questionnaire. The research journey has, however, led me to a solely qualitative thesis. As such, I will focus this chapter on the philosophical orientations through which you will be able to understand the methods chosen and my interpretation of the data generated in each of the phases.

2.2 Philosophical orientations

This is a qualitative study that seeks to understand how lecturers comprehend information and digital literacy and develop their digital competence. As such, I will adopt a 'Big Q' qualitative approach, which utilises qualitative methods within a qualitative study (Cole, 2016), in order to understand the perspectives of my participants within the context of this study.

Whilst digital literacy is a relatively new phenomenon, with Gilster coining the term in 1997, the concept is relatively well-known within universities and by university lecturers (Tang and Chaw, 2016). In addition, digital literacy frameworks have been constructed in collaboration with teaching staff and educational researchers, Jisc's Building digital capabilities framework (2017), for example, and are used by librarians and learning technologists to centre their practice and are used in their interactions with lecturers (Hinrichsen and Coombs, 2014). Although information and digital literacy as concepts and the frameworks themselves are not new to universities or lecturers, my experience tells me that there is still a great deal of uncertainty in what constitutes digital literacy and a digitally competent person. Indeed, the debate about how these concepts are defined and used has been noted by other researchers (Cordell, 2013; Knobel & Lankshear, 2006). This lack of agreement, despite the existence of the frameworks, illustrates the importance of individual experience.

The individual voice is central to this exploratory study, but I believe that the aforementioned state of research on digital literacy and my experience of utilising information and digital literacy frameworks brings important contextualisation to the study. My interpretations of the data generated throughout the study will be shaped

by the fact that this is a Professional Doctorate, with the nature of the research questions originating from my professional practice, coupled with my experiences, and focussing of this research to the information literacy facets of digital literacy. As such, I will take a relativist stance to the research, centred around the belief that the experiences of lecturers will be understood only relative to their social and cultural practices (Given, 2008).

2.3 Contextual constructionism

Further to my relativist stance, I will adopt a contextual constructionism methodology. Contextual constructionism hinges on the belief that understanding of the social construction of knowledge, that is, its social and cultural perspective, is vital if we are to make “sociological sense” of the data (Nichols, 2015, p.79). As such, any interpretation that I apply to this research can only occur within the context of my own situated knowledge.

I had initially considered phenomenology as a methodology, the same approach taken by Bennett (2012) in their Doctor of Education thesis on early adopters of digital tools. However, upon further exploration and reading, I was drawn to contextual constructionism due to the “simultaneous multiplicity of contexts” (Nichols, 2015, p.82). The contexts important to researching digital competence in university lecturers include teaching strategies, the requirements of the subject, departmental, and curricula aims, and the individual pedagogical approach of the lecturer, to name but a few. As such, these also affect the “levels of context” (Nichols, 2015, p.82), from the top-down university and subject requirements to the bottom-up influence of student expectations of the digital environment and how individual lecturers respond to those requirements. Furthermore, the pace of change in technology itself reflects that “accepted knowledge is the result of a temporary consensus” (Ben-Yehuda, p.333), an additional key part of the contextual constructionism methodology.

I have already discussed my professional background and a brief career history relevant to this research, but to further my own self-aware context – a key component of contextual constructionism – I work within a UK and European university and, consequently, my practice is drawn upon frameworks influential within the UK and Europe. I am a member of my professional body, the UK-based Chartered Institute of Library and Information Professionals, and I am guided and

bound by their Ethical Framework (Chartered Institute of Library and Information Professionals, 2018). Of particular interest to this study is CILIP's ethical principle of "The development of information skills and information literacy", which relates back to the grounding of my professional practice in the use of information literacy frameworks. The frameworks and CILIP's Ethical Framework are acutely important to this research and how it will be conducted as librarianship is a profession with a largely phronetic-based episteme (Nolin and Åström, 2010; Robinson and Bawden, 2013). This is something that I have reflected on in previous writing (Cannon, 2017) and means that I am heavily situated in my professional context as there is less connectivity to inter-related professions and their research bases.

The key contexts in which this research will be examined will, therefore, be:

1. The information and digital literacy frameworks that will form the lens through which information and digital literacy will be defined and discussed, and
2. My professional background as a librarian.

3 Digital competencies of university lecturers: A rapid review of the literature

3.1 Introduction to chapter

This chapter seeks to build upon the introductory literature review to specifically look at digital competence of the primary population of interest in this study: university lecturers. I will utilise a rapid review methodology, which employs pragmatic, yet rigorous literature review methods appropriate for the resource constraints of a doctoral study, namely a condensed timeframe and a single researcher.

3.2 Methods

In order to assess the digital competencies of university lecturers, I conducted a rapid review of primary studies to synthesise the available data using a replicable and objective approach formed from the methods described in Abrami *et al.* (2010), Featherstone *et al.* (2015) and Tricco *et al.* (2015). I extracted data from eligible studies on any aspect of digital competence, whether qualitative or quantitative, and no matter how inconsequential the data appeared within the wider-article content.

Studies were identified via a comprehensive yet rapid search process using relevant subject-specific and multidisciplinary bibliographic databases.

3.2.1 Search strategy

Eight bibliographic databases were searched in December 2018; Web of Science Core Collection, Scopus, ASSIA, ERIC, Sociological Abstracts, British Education Index, Australian Education Index, and Library & Information Science Abstracts. Text words were identified from the introductory literature review. Full details of the search strategies for each database can be found in [Appendix 1](#). New results were identified using email search alerts until 26 January 2020.

No date limits were applied to the searches; the earliest article retrieved was from 2009.

3.2.2 Inclusion and exclusion criteria

The criteria used to select studies can be found in Table 1. Broadly, only primary research was considered, and the research had to either be focussed on the digital competencies of university lecturers or make reference to the digital competencies of university lecturers as part of a wider-study.

Setting	Universities
Population	Lecturing staff regardless of academic position
Intervention	Any intervention focussing on lecturer digital competence regardless of qualitative or quantitative methodology
Comparison	Not applicable
Evaluation	Not applicable
Limits	English language filter applied during article sift Primary research Journal articles and conference papers
Types of evidence included	Any method or methodology
Exclusions	Studies were excluded where it was not clear whether the data related to university lecturers

Table 1. Inclusion and exclusion criteria, based on SPICE question formulation framework (Booth, 2006)

3.2.3 Study selection

Results from all database searches were exported to and analysed using EndNote X7. Duplicate references were removed using the Find Duplicates tool in EndNote and a manual sift of remaining records. I identified relevant studies at both title and abstract and full-text stages. My doctoral supervisors were available to resolve any queries about potential inclusion or exclusion of records. A PRISMA flow diagram can be found in [Appendix 2](#).

3.2.4 Quality assessment and data extraction

I appraised each article at the full-text screening stage using a modified version of the ReLIANT tool (Reader's guide to the Literature on Interventions Addressing the need of education and Training) (Koufogiannakis, Booth and Brett, 2006). A summary of the appraisal can be found in Table 2.

3.3 Results

199 results were retrieved via the searches of the bibliographic databases. Thirteen studies met the inclusion criteria. One study was excluded due to a lack of data and poor study quality. This exclusion left twelve studies in the synthesis.

3.3.1 Study summary

Included studies are international in spread, with one study based in Australia (Pechenkina and Branigan, 2018), one in Bulgaria (Yovkova and Peytcheva-Forsyth, 2019), one in Colombia (Espinosa, Betancur and Taborda, 2016), two studies based in England (Alvarez, 2013; Bennett, 2014), one in Hong Kong (McNaught, Lam and Ho, 2009), one in India (Bilawar, Pujar and Pawar, 2017), one in Spain (Gordillo *et al.*, 2012), one in Spain and Mexico (Mercader and Pozos, 2015), one in Spain and Romania (Duta, 2014), one in Ukraine (Kotkova and Perminova, 2019), and one where the study location is not revealed (MacCallum, Jeffrey and Kinshuk, 2014).

Of the included studies, two used mixed methods (one a case study that details a questionnaire and evaluation of course materials (Alvarez, 2013), and one with a questionnaire and training needs analysis (Mercader and Pozos, 2015)), two used interviews (Bennett, 2014, Pechenkina and Branigan, 2018), and eight used questionnaires or surveys (McNaught *et al.*, 2009, Gordillo *et al.*, 2012, Duta, 2014, MacCallum *et al.*, 2014, Espinosa *et al.*, 2016, Bilawar *et al.*, 2017, Kotkova and Perminova, 2019, Yovkova and Peytcheva-Forsyth, 2019).

3.3.2 Study quality

All studies have methodological limitations. In most cases the methodology or research instrument is not sufficiently detailed to fully appraise the study quality or validity of the instrument used. One study (Bennett, 2014) does, however, detail the methodology sufficiently and acknowledges the study limitations, despite full details of the study instrument not being available. A summary of the appraisal can be found in Table 2.

3.3.3 Table 2: Summary of included studies: study characteristics and limitations

Reference (first author and year)	Methodology and intervention	Country and setting	Study population and sampling	Description of research instrument	Are the results of the study clearly explained?	Limitations	Research themes
ALVAREZ, I. 2013.	Methodology: Case study. Intervention: Evaluation of course documentation and online questionnaire.	Country: England, UK. Setting: One university.	Questionnaire responses from 8 lecturers and 30 undergraduate students. Evaluation of course documentation. Sampling method not provided.	Details of the questionnaire are not provided. The evaluation of course documentation appears to be a list of technologies used at the point of analysis.	A summary of findings is provided.	Research both teacher and investigator. Case study design and lack of detail on research instruments lead to questions on the validity of the findings and whether practice implications are reflective rather than data-led.	Digital confidence is a recurrent issue for lecturers.
BENNETT, L. 2014.	Methodology: Phenomenology. Intervention: Interviews.	Country: England, UK. Setting: One university.	16 lecturers interviewed. Purposive sampling.	Thematic areas of the instrument are described. Presumably semi-structured interview.	In depth analysis of the interviews are provided, thematically arranged according to Sharpe and Beetham's Digital Literacies Framework (Sharpe and Beetham, 2010).	Exact details of the instrument are not provided. Limitations in the sample size and the need for further research are highlighted by the author.	Digital confidence is a recurrent issue for lecturers; Lack of training and time is a barrier to developing digital competence; Technology use is determined by the pedagogical relevance of the tool.

Reference (first author and year)	Methodology and intervention	Country and setting	Study population and sampling	Description of research instrument	Are the results of the study clearly explained?	Limitations	Research themes
BILAWAR, P. 2017.	Methodology: Not stated. Intervention: Quantitative survey.	Country: India. Setting: 10 state universities in Maharashtra.	Survey responses from 347 lecturers. Sampling method not provided. Distribution of responses across the 10 universities is not stated.	A 65 question survey instrument is described, with lecturers scoring themselves on a five-point scale. Corresponding methods of formulating the 'e-information literacy index' are provided. An abbreviated form of the survey instrument is appended to the study.	Some findings are provided tabular form. Findings are briefly, qualitatively, summarised.	Detail on how lecturer sample was formulated is not clear; presumably all lecturers at the 10 state universities. Validity of the instrument is not discussed. Lecturers are unlikely to know what all indicators are and, therefore, not able to self- report their literacy levels. Components of e-literacy index appear to measure awareness and use of tools rather than literacy levels.	The level of digital competence in lecturers is variable across all population characteristics; Lack of training and time is a barrier to developing digital competence.

Reference (first author and year)	Methodology and intervention	Country and setting	Study population and sampling	Description of research instrument	Are the results of the study clearly explained?	Limitations	Research themes
DUTA, N. 2014.	Methodology: Not stated. Intervention: Questionnaire, possibly qualitative and quantitative, although not stated.	Country: Spain and Romania. Setting: 4 universities in Spain, 4 universities in Romania.	240 teachers in Spain and 245 in Romania. Detail not provided on whether this is the sample size or number of respondents. Distribution of responses across the 8 universities is not stated.	14 item questionnaire. No further details are provided.	'Analysis and interpretation' was undertaken in SPSS 17.0. Results table shows 34 items, which does not correlate to the 14 item questionnaire. One sizable quotation, presumably from the instrument, is provided.	The instrument results address the issues raised in the literature review, but no research question is provided, making appraisal difficult. Lack of information on a research question, instrument design and results analysis make for a high risk of bias.	Digital confidence is a recurrent issue for lecturers.
ESPINOSA, H. R. 2016.	Methodology: Not stated. Intervention: Quantitative structured survey.	Country: Colombia. Setting: One university faculty (agriculture).	Total population of 185 lecturers. Stratified random sampling provided a sample of 65 lecturers. Response rate not provided.	The instrument questions were validated by "expert judgment" [sic] and a summary of the thematic areas the instrument covers is provided.	Results of the study are provided qualitatively and quantitatively in the analysis and discussion. Quantitative data is additionally provided in tabular form. Appropriate statistical tests are used throughout.	Researchers belong to same faculty in investigation. Exact details of the instrument are not provided. Some conclusions are not supported by the data.	The level of digital competence in lecturers is variable across all population characteristics; Lack of training and time is a recurrent barrier to developing digital competence.

Reference (first author and year)	Methodology and intervention	Country and setting	Study population and sampling	Description of research instrument	Are the results of the study clearly explained?	Limitations	Research themes
GORDILLO, I. C. 2012.	Methodology: Not stated. Intervention: Questionnaire.	Country: Spain. Setting: One university faculty (education).	336 students across all levels within the faculty, undergraduate, masters, and doctoral level. Sampling method not clear. Response rate not provided.	23 item questionnaire on IT availability and use within the faculty. Instrument validated within the faculty and other faculties.	All student groups are amalgamated and, therefore, the results are simplistically presented in terms of percentage agreement/ disagreement with the questions.	Researchers belong to same faculty in investigation. Sampling method is not clear. Exact details of the research instrument are not provided although many questions and themes are discussed in the results.	Students self-assess as digitally competent, lecturers do not.
KOTKOVA, V. V. 2019.	Methodology: Critical analysis. Intervention: Qualitative questionnaire.	Country: Ukraine. Setting: One university.	124 students and 52 lecturers. Sampling methods and population characteristics are not provided.	6 question questionnaire. General instrument themes are provided. The validity of the instrument is not discussed.	The results for each question is provided, but not the question wording. The contrast in student and lecturer responses is discussed.	Details of the instrument are not provided. No details of sampling, response rate or characteristics are provided, nor how representative data is. The limitations lead to a simplistic analysis of results.	Lack of training and time is a barrier to developing digital competence.

Reference (first author and year)	Methodology and intervention	Country and setting	Study population and sampling	Description of research instrument	Are the results of the study clearly explained?	Limitations	Research themes
MACCALLUM, K. 2014.	<p>Methodology: Structural equation modelling and exploratory factor analysis.</p> <p>Intervention: Quantitative questionnaire.</p>	<p>Country: Not stated, although assumed in the Oceanic region due to demographic characteristics provided in the results and that two of the three authors are based in New Zealand (the other in Canada).</p> <p>Setting: Various universities.</p>	<p>University lecturers. Sampling was via a multi-stage stratified convenience sampling, at conference presentations and staff email lists. Total sample population is, therefore, unknown. 196 responses received, with 21 removed (incomplete or significant outliers).</p>	<p>Five-part quantitative questionnaire, where all items were measured in a 7-point Likert scale. All items were derived from existing instruments to ensure content validity. The instrument is described and appended in whole.</p>	<p>Study results are clearly explained and discussed in detail, supporting the authors' conclusions.</p>	<p>As the authors note, the sampling method and response rate limits generalisability. Additionally, the email lists and conferences used in sampling are not provided.</p>	<p>Students self- assess as digitally competent, lecturers do not; Technology use is determined by the pedagogical relevance of the tool.</p>

Reference (first author and year)	Methodology and intervention	Country and setting	Study population and sampling	Description of research instrument	Are the results of the study clearly explained?	Limitations	Research themes
MCNAUGHT, C. 2009.	<p>Methodology: Not stated.</p> <p>Intervention: Questionnaire, one version for students, one for lecturers. The versions differ in “minimal contextual ways”. Quantitative analysis is presented. It is not clear whether the questionnaire also has qualitative items.</p>	<p>Country: Hong Kong.</p> <p>Setting: One university.</p>	Questionnaire distributed to all year 1 students and lecturers on year 1 courses across all university faculties. 689 student (83% response rate) and 56 lecturer responses (39% response rate).	Questionnaire is a counterpart to an Australian digital native survey, adapted for local context. Exact details of the research instrument are not provided, and no further detail of the Australian counterpart exist. Some questions are listed in the findings and the instrument is thematically summarised.	The results are described in detail in discussion and tabular form. Appropriate tests are used. Comparative responses are provided between faculties and between students and lecturers where appropriate.	The authors acknowledge that the lecturer response rate is low and not evenly spread across faculties. Five of eight faculties had a response rate >50% and two had 100%. These faculties are not stated and, therefore, the lecturer responses may be biased and not generalisable. The authors further note four results with non-significant standardised residuals and low p -values.	Students self-assess as digitally competent, lecturers do not.

Reference (first author and year)	Methodology and intervention	Country and setting	Study population and sampling	Description of research instrument	Are the results of the study clearly explained?	Limitations	Research themes
MERCADER, C. 2015.	Methodology: Cross-case analysis. Intervention: Survey, interviews and focus groups.	Country: Mexico and Spain. Setting: One university in Spain, 21 universities in Mexico.	Responses from 78 lecturers in Spain (from a sample of 140 in the Educational Science Faculty) and five faculty managers, and 27 lecturers, institutional managers and training co- ordinators from across 21 Mexican universities (38 universities were invited to participate). Total sample size not provided. Probability and propositional sampling was employed.	In Spain, a survey was used, followed by five in-depth interviews with faculty managers. In Mexico, one of four focus groups was used (the Mexican instrument was part of a much wider five-year project). The Foresee Matrix was used to compare and contrast the two cases.	Analysis is clearly presented in tabular form, allowing factors unique to one case or common factors to be easily identified. The tabular form allows the author conclusions to be easily interpreted.	Similarities or differences between the two countries, education systems and universities sampled are not adequately described; generalisability between cases is difficult. It is not clear why only one element of the larger Mexican study is presented for analysis or why only one of four focus groups were used in the analysis. Whilst clearly presented, there is insufficient detail to how the differing research methods were reconciled to form analysis, leaving the results open to significant bias.	Lack of training and time is a barrier to developing digital competence.

Reference (first author and year)	Methodology and intervention	Country and setting	Study population and sampling	Description of research instrument	Are the results of the study clearly explained?	Limitations	Research themes
PECHENKINA, E. 2018.	Methodology: Not stated. Intervention: Semi-structured interviews.	Country: Australia. Setting: One university.	8 lecturers from 9 who participated in a new VLE pilot. 7 lecturers were male, 1 female. Sampling was by identifying lecturers on courses with few students. No further sampling details provided.	Interview themes were: “lecturers’ expectations of the transition experience and its desired outcomes [from VLE pilot, authors use LMS acronym for Learning Management System]; lecturers’ instructional design philosophy concerned with the usage of LMS; challenges associated with the LMS change process; and professional development that lecturers deemed crucial to the LMS change success” (p.236).	Interviews were thematically analysed using NVivo. Details of the thematic analysis framework not provided. The conference paper is split into the four interview themes with thematic areas and representative quotations used throughout, making for clear analysis.	The authors acknowledge the limited sample size and non- representative nature of the course on which the sample lecture.	Technology use is determined by the pedagogical relevance of the tool.

Reference (first author and year)	Methodology and intervention	Country and setting	Study population and sampling	Description of research instrument	Are the results of the study clearly explained?	Limitations	Research themes
YOVKOVA, B. 2019.	Methodology: Not stated. Intervention: Online survey with 27 qualitative and quantitative questions.	Country: Bulgaria. Setting: One university.	199 lecturers from a (presumed total university) sample of 1729.	The research instrument sought to identify the factors affecting the use of electronic resources to support disabled students. For the quantitative questions, descriptive statistics were used with appropriate tests and significance levels. Full details of the research instrument are not provided.	The survey results are clearly presented according to the research questions posed. The results are appropriately analysed and discussions and the conclusion are data-driven.	Details of the instrument are not provided, although some questions are provided in the analysis. Whilst the survey response rate is low, the number of responses is relatively high and representative of the university faculties. Details on whether the respondent characteristics are representative of the university sample are not provided, but respondent characteristics are detailed.	The level of digital competence in lecturers is variable across all population characteristics; Students self-assess as digitally competent, lecturers do not.

Table 2. Summary of included studies: study characteristics and limitations. Table adapted from ReLIANT (Reader's guide to the Literature on Interventions Addressing the Need of education and Training) (Koufogiannakis et al., 2006).

3.3.4 Analysis

3.3.4.1 The level of digital competence in lecturers is variable across all population characteristics

Bilawar et al.'s (2017) short article on "e-information literacy", "the ability to properly use and evaluate electronic resources, tools and services and apply it for lifelong learning process" (p. 432), illustrates that the lecturers in this study have differing levels of digital literacy dependent upon their faculty and academic position. In the study, an "e-information literacy index" (p. 434) was used to measure the self-assessed digital literacy levels of 347 lecturers from ten state universities in Maharashtra, India. The questionnaire revealed a "relatively flat distribution... where 2010 (60.52%) of teachers [university lecturers] were found to be e-information literate and [the] remaining 137 (39.48%) were not e-information literate" (p. 434).

Across the faculties surveyed, Bilawar et al. (2017) found that those lecturers in science faculties were the most e-information literate (0.5835, a score of 1 would be e-literate and 0 e-illiterate on the index scale), followed by social sciences (0.5427) and arts and humanities faculties (0.4616). The validity of the index scores must be questioned due to presumed differences in the population and subject constitution across each of the faculties in the ten state universities surveyed. Respondent numbers by university, subject, gender, and designation are not supplied. Nevertheless, this does provide some discipline-level information not otherwise available. The questionnaire also revealed that female respondents perceive themselves more e-information literate than male respondents (0.5516 and 0.5309, respectively); there is no discussion as to why this may be the case and the index difference appears to be insignificant.

Bilawar et al. (2017) found that Assistant Professors were the most e-information literate (0.5621), followed by Professors (0.5338), with Associate Professors (0.4975) being the least e-information literate. Regrettably, there is no discussion on the tenure of each professorial group, nor whether tenure is consistent across all universities sampled. Age profiles against index scores would allow the data to be seen through the lens of Prensky's (2001) digital natives and immigrants theory, where those born into a digital world are naturalised to technology and hence

described as 'natives' and those where digital technology developed throughout their lifetimes and termed 'immigrants'.

Espinosa et al. (2016) find a variable level of self-assessed digital competence across age groups in their survey of lecturers in the Faculty of Agricultural Sciences in the Universidad de Antioquia, Colombia. The survey results demonstrate that the use of technology in teaching, aside from email and search engine use, is low for all lecturer age groups, genders, and contractual status. Espinosa et al. focus on a "significant difference ($p < 0.05$) in favour of lecturers of the younger age group in the use of Moodle" (p.267), the VLE. What is not explained is that use of the VLE is 22.2% for ages 21-30, 6.9% for 31-50, and 15.4% for 51-75, which does not support the discussion point that the data is consistent with other findings where there is a "positive correlation between age and ICTs use" (p.267). Additionally, 11.1% of 21-30 year olds, 13.9% of 31-50 year olds and 23% of 51-75 year olds use blogging in teaching practice.

No correlation between faculty nor academic position and utilisation of technology in the classroom are found by Yovkova and Peytcheva-Forsyth (2019) in their survey results from 199 lecturers in Sofia University, Bulgaria. Indeed, neither sex nor age were influences on the self-identified level of digital competence of the lecturers in the survey. Both Espinosa et al.'s (2016) and Yovkova and Peytcheva-Forsyth's (2019) survey data would, therefore, support the 'visitors and residents' theory (White and Le Cornu, 2011) where the situational context dictates how digitally competent one is rather than age.

Whilst one must consider that although the surveys in Bilawar et al. (2017) and Espinosa et al. (2016) are self-reported by lecturers, they both support the idea of low levels of digital competence and digital confidence in university lecturers. This is not the case for the lecturers in Yovkova and Peytcheva-Forsyth's (2019) study. The data across the three studies would, however, support Espinosa et al.'s belief that lecturers are failing to adequately develop their digital skills. The data provided by Espinosa et al do not, however, support their conclusion that "men aged over 31 require further technical and training support" (p.269), especially given the low sample size. Indeed, given the low levels of engagement with the VLE in Espinosa et al. (2016) and the high number of lecturers who require support to adapt educational

materials for students with additional support needs in Yovkova and Peytcheva-Forsyth (2019), one could argue that all age groups and sexes require additional training and support in order to develop their digital competencies.

3.3.4.2 Digital confidence is a recurrent issue for lecturers

The variability of digital competence across lecturer populations is more complex than simply characteristics, such as age, seniority, and faculty. Digital confidence appears to influence technology use as much as digital competence.

One barrier to the creation of an Open Educational Resource (OER) in the Dance Department at the University of Surrey, England, was the variable levels of digital literacy of staff involved in the project (Alvarez, 2013). During the OER creation process, staff were offered 'e-learning sessions' to familiarise themselves with technology and develop digital skills. Whether staff attended the 'e-learning sessions' is not clear, with Alvarez noting that a barrier to staff developing digital competence was a lack of time and training. What is clear, is that the time and training barrier affected staff digital confidence and prevented staff from engaging with digital tools, as they deemed the risks of a blended teaching approach "too risky to implement, especially when activities were connected to assessment." (Alvarez, 2013, p.8). However, when concluding the case study, Alvarez reflects that during the OER development, lecturers quickly developed their digital competence and are now digitally confident enough that they are looking for further opportunities to embed digital literacy into the wider-programme.

Bennett's (2014) study on the early adopters of digital technology found that this group of lecturers perceived digital tools to be a natural component of their teaching practice. Indeed, two of Bennett's interviewees specifically argued against separating the digital tool from the pedagogical context. One could hypothesise that understanding and applying digital technology as a pedagogical tool enables lecturer digital confidence. This hypothesis is in contrast to Alvarez (2013) where lecturers conceivably see technology as an 'add on' to their teaching approach, which then forms a barrier to engagement and confidence building. Similarly, Duta (2014) states that lecturers understand the potential use of technology as a pedagogical tool but require additional training to realise technology's potential. Whilst Duta's statement is a single quotation from one respondent, which does not appear to be tied to a wider

theme of the research and, therefore, likely not representative of the wider-findings, Duta uses this quotation to conclude that embedding technology in the classroom is a challenge to lecturers, something that is supported in Duta's literature review.

Whilst Bennett's (2014) interviewees felt their digital skills lagged behind that of their students they did not let this affect their use of technology. They instead engaged their students in a dialogue, developing their skills in collaboration with their students. One of Bennett's interviewees did feel anxious about supporting students when troubleshooting technological problems, with Bennett reflecting that this feeling may be a barrier "for those beyond the early adopter group [of technology within the classroom]" (Bennett, 2014, n.p.). This quotation may support the work of Alvarez (2013) and Duta (2014), where Alvarez's lecturer colleagues took a risk adverse approach to using technology and Duta feeling that lecturers require additional support to overcome digital confidence issues.

3.3.4.3 Students self-assess as digitally competent, lecturers do not

Gordillo et al.'s (2012) study asked education students about their digital experiences on their programmes. The students in Gordillo et al.'s survey state that lecturers make regular use of digital technologies in-class (56% frequently, 15.5% always, 28% occasionally), with 99.4% of lecturers using PowerPoint to deliver their lectures. Gordillo et al. contemplates that lecturers are slowly adapting to new technologies and methods of lecture delivery, but are reluctant to develop their digital teaching practice, beyond PowerPoint. As discussed earlier, lecturers may be reluctant to use technology in the classroom due to either a lack of digital confidence or perhaps a lack of confidence in IT infrastructure, or both. MacCallum et al. (2014) note that ICT anxiety influenced lecturer digital literacy; if lecturers have a fear of IT failing or looking foolish, they will be reluctant to develop digitally. There may be a direct relationship between digital confidence and digital competence, but a digitally competent lecturer may also resist using technology due to a constrained IT infrastructure.

Also surveying students, as well as lecturers, McNaught et al.'s (2009) study investigated the "nature of differences in digital experiences between teachers and students in an Asian context" (p. 656). McNaught et al. (2009) found a statistically significant effect in that students self-reported that they were more skilled in using

technology than teachers when considering the factors 'advanced web of mobile features', 'social features' and 'entertainment'. Lecturers, however, perceived their skills to be higher than students for simple web functions. Additional analysis on the perceived low level of lecturer digital skills data showed little variation between staff in different faculties, age and gender suggesting that, in this small sample, a low level of digital confidence is universal to all lecturers. Conversely, Yovkova and Peytcheva-Forsyth (2019) find that when asked to self-report their level of digital competence using "some of the most popular digital technologies", lecturers identify as "'experts' (18.71%) or as 'professionals' (48.5%)" with very few reporting being "beginners in ICT use – 8.7% and merely 2.3% express discomfort in relation to the use of ICT" (p.3). However, a quarter of the same lecturers only report digital competence when appropriate support or guidance is given. This additional data may suggest that lecturers have a good 'baseline' level of digital competence with familiar software packages, say email and word processing, but conceivably lack the digital competence to use unfamiliar software or utilise advanced features of familiar software. This hypothesis is augmented by a large proportion of Yovkova and Peytcheva-Forsyth's lecturers having never used "uncommon" tools such as audio lectures and self-study materials (41%) (p.3) and only a third using electronic methods of assessment.

3.3.4.4 Lack of training and time is a barrier to developing digital competence

Mercader and Pozos (2015) argue that digital technology use within education has caused such a shift in thinking that new approaches to lecturer education is required. To identify barriers to change and resistance to the adoption of digital technologies, a cross-case analysis was employed utilising different research methods across universities in Spain and Mexico. Despite the different populations sampled across the university education systems of two different countries, Mercader and Pozos (2015) note 11 common 'barriers and resistances' and 15 factors that are unique to the two systems. A lack of training is a common thread, at induction, in continual professional development plans, and in the pedagogical use of technology in curricula. To compound a lack of training, lecturers do not have sufficient time to develop their skills nor reflect on their experiences of using technology for education and, as previously discussed, lack digital confidence in the classroom. The authors

also identify that lecturers perceive themselves as technically inferior to their 'digital native' students.

Similar factors are also identified by Espinosa et al. (2016). Despite information on training in the use of the VLE being offered to lecturers, a lack of training is cited as the highest factor in lack of engagement in the VLE across gender and all age groups; only a lack of technical support scores higher for the 51-75 age group. Furthermore, across all age ranges in Espinosa et al.'s study, the most frequently given reasons for not utilising the VLE is a 'lack of training', 'lack of technical support to elaborate contents' and, jointly, 'lack of knowledge of Moodle tools' and 'lack of technical support to upload materials onto the platform' (p.265). Contrary to Mercader and Pozos (2015), a lack of time does not appear to be a considerable barrier to digital engagement, with 12.8% of male and 19.2% female respondents considering time to be a factor in their reasons for not using the VLE. A lack of technical skills, followed by a lack of time and the perceived risks are the most frequent barriers to use of technology in Kotkova and Perminova's (2019) survey of lecturers. A self-reported lack of digital competence is why 68% of lecturers in Kotkova and Perminova's study provide lecture material in print-only format, with 64% believing that the "education process" (p.199) becomes more complicated when ICT is used; this despite 74% of students in the study preferring electronic provision of education materials.

In their discussion, Mercader and Pozos (2015) suggest that training should be developed that focuses on the pedagogical use of technology rather than on the technology itself, as has been the focus in the past. Arguably, since their participants still fail to engage with technology nor develop their digital competencies, training should be both focused on the technology itself, the pedagogical use of technology, and the development of lecturer digital competencies. Bilawar et al. (2017) call for university lecturers to be provided with protected time to develop their skills, and for lecturers to be provided with discipline-specific training and awareness campaigns as part of a university's continual professional development programmes.

Interestingly, Bennett's (2014) early adopter lecturers describe learning digital skills as an "investment" (n.p.) in time saved at a later date or with respect to enhancing the student experience. In contrast to Espinosa et al. (2016) and Mercader and

Pozos (2015), where a lack of initial (upon recruitment to an organisation) and continual training is a barrier to subsequent learning and engagement, Bennett's (2014) lecturers take active control of their continual digital development. This may illustrate a practice and ideological gap between early adopters and the general lecturer population, or simply highlight better training opportunities in Bennett's university. Whether early adopters of technology could be used as case studies and mentors to other lecturers is an idea worth exploring. However, with a lack of time a common theme, early adopters may not have the resource to become 'champions' for others (Pechenkina and Branigan, 2018).

3.3.4.5 Technology use is determined by the pedagogical relevance of the tool
Lecturers who are early adopters of technology will use technology when it assists their teaching practices, but will reject technology if they questioned its pedagogical value (Bennett, 2014). Early adopters took the time to understand the pedagogical use of technology and its place in the curriculum.

Whilst MacCallum et al. (2014) looked at a specific form of digital technology, mobile learning, their research found a similar link between the pedagogical usefulness of technology and subsequent adoption. MacCallum et al.'s findings demonstrate that being literate in the use of mobile technology and having the ability and a positive attitude toward using technology in-class, significantly influences the perceived usefulness of mobile learning. Three factors influenced the perceived ease of use of mobile learning. These were, in order of strength, "their perceived self-efficacy of teachers to use ICT in the classroom, their level of anxiety educators felt when using technology, and their experience with the advanced features of mobile learning" (p.151).

The juxtaposition between MacCallum et al. (2014) and Bennett (2014) is an interesting one. MacCallum et al. find that in order for lecturers to perceive mobile technology useful, lecturers have to be both literate in the technology itself and wish to use technology in the classroom; the technology being easy to use is not enough in itself. Bennett also finds that the early adopters of technology need to understand the technology itself and recognise its pedagogical value before utilising the technology. Together, the two findings pose a significant challenge to universities who must allow lecturers the time to understand technologies whilst simultaneously

develop lecturer understanding in how the technology in question can be applied pedagogically.

Interestingly, MacCallum et al. (2014) uncover no relationship between advanced general ICT skills and acceptance of mobile learning (learning utilising mobile phones in and outside of classroom settings). Putting aside that MacCallum et al.'s study is specifically focused on mobile learning, this finding would suggest that the use of technology in class is highly situational; being digitally competent does not necessarily mean that a lecturer will embed technology in their teaching. Instead, each piece of software needs to be critically evaluated against the pedagogical purpose for which the lecturer intends to use the technology. Lecturers interviewed by Pechenkina and Branigan (2018) would tend to agree. Focusing instead on a pilot for a new VLE, some lecturers in the pilot felt that the VLE had "transformational potential" in their teaching (p.239) and that the pedagogical use of technology was more important than the VLE itself.

This finding puts the onus of embedding technology with university curricula firmly in the hands of lecturers in partnership with learning technologists rather than institutional digital strategies driven by university IT departments and generalist ICT training. That being said, teaching self-efficacy is particularly important (MacCallum et al., 2014) and how self-efficacy is developed in lecturers may well stem from a strong grounding in general ICT skills. Pechenkina and Branigan (2018) observe their lecturer participants increasing their digital literacy throughout the period of their study. This increase in digital literacy is exemplified by lecturers using a pedagogically-appropriate range of advanced IT skills to transform their teaching practices; albeit with intensive training and at great human resource cost, from the lecturers and support staff involved. Indeed, MacCallum et al. (2014) note that digital literacy plays a major role in a wide range of factors that influence lecturer "behavioural intention to use mobile learning" (p.151) and recommend that lecturer general ICT skills are developed alongside the use of mobile technology.

3.4 Discussion

One of the strengths of the studies included in this review is that many have large sample sizes. The studies are also of an international scale, suggesting that the digital competence of university lecturers is of global interest. Despite these

strengths, many of the studies have methodological issues, some of which could be overcome by better reporting standards, such as the inclusion of survey instruments in appendices and as supplementary materials. Definitive conclusions are, therefore, difficult to make. As an example, Bilawar et al. (2017) show that lecturers in science faculties are more “e-information literate” than lecturers in arts and humanities faculties. Espinosa et al. (2016), however, show variable levels of digital competence across all population characteristics, whilst Yovkova and Peytcheva-Forsyth (2019) find no correlation between faculty nor academic position and technology use, nor sex nor age and lecturer digital competence levels. Some lecturers are willing to experiment with technology (Bennett, 2014), whilst others are risk adverse (Alvarez, 2013).

One must also bear in mind the age of some studies and the changing nature of technology, access to technology, and lecturing itself. The date range of included studies is 2009-2019.

Ultimately, the lack of reliable, validated, instruments to assess digital competence, hampers knowledge development in this field of research, especially in what appears to be an under-researched population group. Future research should address the availability of survey instruments and measures to move the field of research beyond self-assessed questionnaires to objective measures of competence.

3.5 Implications for practice

The themes identified in this review are:

- The level of digital competence in lecturers is variable across all population characteristics,
- Digital confidence is a recurrent issue for lecturers,
- Students self-assess as digitally competent, lecturers do not,
- Lack of training and time is a barrier to developing digital competence, and
- Technology use is determined by the pedagogical relevance of the tool.

The research included in this review is not conclusive on the ‘digital native, digital immigrant’ debate (Prensky, 2001), but the limited data does cast some doubt on the binary factor of age and digital competence in university lecturers. Instead, the review suggests that factors such as digital confidence and the pedagogical

relevance of the technology itself plays as much a part in a lecturer's digital competence levels as any other factor. Training specifically focussed on the development of lecturer digital competence levels is, therefore, likely to fail to increase use of technology in the classroom. Instead, training needs to be offered on specific technologies, how these technologies can be utilised in teaching, and on generic ICT training for lecturers.

Together, these recommendations pose a challenge to university professional service departments to co-ordinate appropriate training in order to bridge the chasm between early adopters and the general lecturer population. Indeed, Bennett (2014) argues that a common factor across early adopters is their willingness to experiment with technology, and that it is this experimentation that fosters digital confidence. Crucially, lecturers must also be allowed time to attend training and reflect on their use of technology in the classroom, on a technical and pedagogical level.

3.6 Limitations

Compared with systematic reviews, rapid reviews have a number of limitations due to their less resource intensive nature (Tricco et al., 2015). This rapid review attempted to minimise search biases by using a comprehensive, yet practical, description of the phenomenon in question when constructing the search strategy. In order to balance this limitation, the search strategies were performed across a wider range of eight subject specific and multidisciplinary bibliographic databases where one would expect research on the phenomenon to be indexed.

The review is also open to bias in that one researcher sifted against the inclusion and exclusion criteria and critically appraised the literature. Whilst the included studies are international in nature, 24 of 52 articles screened at full text were not written in English and, therefore, excluded; this adds a geographic and language bias to the review. Interestingly, most of these excluded papers are written in Spanish. Note that this is likely due to bias in the journal inclusion criteria of the databases searched, rather than pointing to geographical research expertise in the English or Spanish speaking worlds. However, this dataset is available to Spanish speakers for further review, which would benefit this field of research.

Of note is that half of references in full text screening and included outputs are conference papers. Conference papers typically constitute only a small percentage of the content of bibliographic databases (~10% in Scopus (Elsevier B. V., 2017)), for example); without handsearching conference materials and grey literature searches, a time-consuming exercise, this body of knowledge risks being lost.

4 What digital competencies do university lecturers need to be digitally competent? One librarian's view

4.1 Introduction to chapter

This chapter will detail how I intend to resolve a problem highlighted in the literature review, namely that existing digital literacy frameworks are not focussed on a university lecturer population. I will provide the steps I will take to scope existing use of digital literacy frameworks of relevance to UK universities, and how I intend to reconcile these frameworks and explore them through an information literacy lens.

4.2 Aims and research questions

This chapter focusses on the second objective of the study: to reconcile digital literacy frameworks, through an information literacy lens, and distil the competencies university lecturers need to be digitally competent.

This work will address the following research questions:

- How does the 'A new curriculum for information literacy' (ANCIL) framework relate to university lecturers in a UK university context?
- What digital literacy frameworks are in use across a sample of UK universities?

At this point, I intend to append a supplementary process. By undertaking this phase of the research as an individual, albeit drawing on the experiences and writings of other researchers, I will allow my voice to 'echo' throughout this study. This approach brings clear limitations and biases (discussed later in this chapter) but simultaneously brings alignment with my relativist stance. As such, my supplementary aim is to provide further insight into how I contextually construct my knowledge of information and digital literacy, giving additional context to my own situated knowledge.

4.3 Research methods

4.3.1 Sampling of digital literacy frameworks

Phase one of the research study aims to discover the underlying competencies required for a lecturer to be considered digitally competent. To do so, I will seek to reconcile a range of digital literacy frameworks, distilling the competencies to those

relevant to lecturing in a UK university context. In order to ground the study in my professional background as a librarian, I will only consider the facets of the frameworks that fall under the domain of information literacy. To recap, digital literacies fall under the domain of different professions. Jisc, for example, define six elements of digital capability in their framework (Beetham, 2017), see Figure 2. The epistemological and tacit knowledge that underpins these six elements fall under the remit of different professions, for example: information technology, lecturers, librarians, and careers services. There are elements where two or more professional groups have stakes in that epistemological and tacit knowledge. Equally, there are elements such as information, data and media literacies that are more closely associated with librarianship rather than other professions. These information literacies will be the focus of this study.

Figure 2. Image from Jisc (2015) Digital capabilities framework illustrating the holistic nature of digital literacy in Venn diagram form

I will begin by scoping the digital literacy frameworks in use at UK universities by employing a simple random selection method (Salkind, 2010) of public UK universities. To do so, I will list each public university in the United Kingdom (Wikipedia, 2018), assign them a number based on their alphabetical listing, then use the Google Random Number generator (Google, 2018) to randomly select a university. I will then search each university website for 'digital literacy' and 'information literacy' and browse their publications, library, and learning technology and student support service webpages for relevant information to elicit what

framework or frameworks that they use. To avoid random error bias, where a certain type of university is represented in the random selection of universities, a stratified sampling method was considered (Lemm, 2010). Here, the universities would be split into their mission groups, for example, Russell Group, Million+ universities, and University Alliance group. However, the purpose of this aim is not to compare the frameworks used across UK universities, but to achieve an indicative sample. Also, not every university explicitly states which frameworks they use and with a smaller sample, such as the 24 universities in the Russell Group, there is a likelihood that no information would be available for this sample. A simple random selection method eliminates sample selection bias, whilst still achieving the aim of a representative sample of frameworks to be identified. A total of ten universities will be sampled.

4.3.2 Sampling of an information literacy framework 'lens'

To focus my analysis through the 'lens' of information literacy, I will use the Arcadia Project's 'A new curriculum for information literacy' (ANCIL) (Secker and Coonan, 2011), which has been purposively sampled. The ANCIL framework is the output from a research project that aimed to understand information literacy specifically from a UK university perspective. The framework draws on previous reviews of information literacy frameworks and analysis of the SCONUL's (Society of College National and University Libraries) 7 pillars of information literacy, an influential framework within UK university libraries, and the Association of College and Research Libraries, and Australian and New Zealand Institute for Information Literacy frameworks. As a result of the ANCIL project being "grounded in a very broad reading of 'information literacy'" (Secker and Coonan, n.d., n.p.) and the outcome of previous research comparing information literacy frameworks, I feel that further comparator analysis would not add to the trustworthiness of this study. In short, ANCIL distils information literacy frameworks in the same manner that I will be doing for this and the following phase of the research. I will, however, undertake further analysis of the ANCIL framework, comparing and critically appraising the framework alongside additional appraisal found within the published literature, to further enhance the trustworthiness of this study.

4.3.3 Reconciling digital literacy frameworks through an information literacy lens

When the digital literacy frameworks have been sampled, I will then employ the framework analysis method (Ritchie and Spencer, 1994) to reconcile the frameworks into one object that can be distilled through the ANCIL information literacy lens. Framework analysis is a particularly useful method for reconciling the digital literacy frameworks because of the flexibility facilitated by this method. The reasons for choosing framework analysis over other methods is similar to the decision making process described by Parkinson et al. in their 2016 worked example of using framework analysis. While digital literacy frameworks are thematically similar, like Parkinson et al.'s interview data, the competencies contained within are heterogenous in that the language used and the context in which they are applied is distinct and somewhat unique. This rules out IPA with its requirement of a homogenous dataset (Parkinson *et al.*, 2016). I also have a limited sample and, therefore, a defined dataset with "a priori issues" that require investigation (Srivastava and Thomson, 2009, p.76) that also suits the framework analysis method. Indeed, Srivastava and Thomson (p.77) continue that a key feature of the method is that "it allows within-case and between-case analysis: it enables comparisons between, and associations within, cases to be made"; this is exactly what I intend to do to reconcile and distil the frameworks. Moreover, framework analysis aligns with the contextual nature of my research question and provides a theoretical alignment with my contextual constructionism methodology.

4.3.4 Internal and external validity of the framework sampling and analysis

Internal validity will be gained by my trusted professional position and my experience and familiarity with the subject of digital and information literacies. This knowledge and experience has been developed through a history of researching digital and information literacy, and applying this knowledge within my teaching practice. This experience of researching and teaching within university environments provides me with prolonged engagement in the field (Lincoln and Guba, 1985), bringing advanced familiarity with the subject. My experience and familiarity will be compared with the findings of existing literature. There is a risk, however, that my position could add an element of conceptual bias to the distillation process, where an error is made on the part of the researcher and the research problem is misinterpreted or concluded

(Bowling, 2014). I will adopt a reflexive writing style for the findings so that the methodological decisions made during the distillation process are transparent and aligned to existing literature (Lincoln and Guba, 1985).

External validity will be acquired through a rich dataset and thick description (Lincoln and Guba, 1985; Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2011), allowing readers to determine whether the analysis can be transferred to other settings. Transferability will be enhanced by the library and information community's familiarity with the frameworks analysed and the ANCIL lens through which the frameworks will be scrutinised.

4.3.5 Limitations and bias

This methods section and the following findings section set the direction of the subsequent phases of the research. Undertaking this phase of the research as an individual introduces an element of bias that would be otherwise minimised by undertaking this section in, say, a focus group or in parallel with a second researcher. A focus group, depending on its constitution, would not necessarily substantially minimise bias (Fern, 2001), and there are practical resource implications within any doctoral study that would make sampling an appropriately experienced second researcher a challenge, if running a distillation process in parallel. However, as stated earlier, a secondary aim of this phase of the research is to explore and contextualise my own knowledge and experiences within the thesis. That exploration will be key to understanding how I construct my knowledge and latter analysis as the research develops.

With the choice of frameworks, selection bias may occur if the sampling of the frameworks does not accurately portray real world use. This risk of bias has been minimised by the pilot sampling method of the frameworks. I believe this risk to be minimal on the internal and external validity of the research. However, there is a risk that I have failed to identify an influential framework, which may affect the transferability of the research. My knowledge and experience, the pilot, and the earlier literature review minimise this risk, but nevertheless, it is one that cannot be disregarded.

4.3.6 Ethical considerations

As "desk based" research, there are no ethical considerations with this phase of the research.

4.4 Introduction to findings

This first phase of the research provides the foundations on which the remainder of the thesis sits. The digital literacy frameworks I identify and the critical appraisal of the information literacy (IL) lens through which the digital literacy frameworks will be seen, will dictate the materials used in the subsequent workshop phase of the research.

4.5 A critical appraisal of the ANCIL information literacy framework with respect to lecturing in a UK university context

4.5.1 An introduction to ANCIL

As previously stated in the methods, the Arcadia Project's 'A new curriculum for information literacy' (ANCIL) (Secker and Coonan, 2011) is the outcome of a research project based at Cambridge University. Like many frameworks used within education, the focus is on learners. In the case of ANCIL this is "undergraduate learners" (p.3). There is, therefore, a need to amend ANCIL to be relevant to a lecturer population for the purposes of this study. The amendments I have made can be seen in the following sections of this chapter.

The methods used for the ANCIL research project was a "wide-ranging review of published literature and a modified Delphi study, consulting experts in the information and education communities" (Secker and Coonan, 2012, p.20). The methods used and the experts interviewed are appropriate and extensive, drawn from the authors' contacts and experience on the CILIP Information Literacy Special Interest Group (Secker, 2011). The reports and outputs (Coonan and Secker, n.d.) from the project are openly available, which is not always the case with other frameworks. As such, I consider ANCIL a rigorous and appropriate framing of IL for the purpose of this study.

ANCIL also aligns with my research aims because ANCIL investigates IL from a UK university perspective. On a more fundamental level, the approach of ANCIL differs from other IL definitions and frameworks in that the framework is grounded in wider academic practice. This grounding brings a further alignment with my research by including the perspectives of "lecturers, learning or educational developers, libraries, careers services and other academic support services" (Secker and Coonan, 2012, p.20). However, this study focuses on university lecturers and the perspectives of

lecturers, librarians, and learning technologists. The inclusion of “careers services and other academic support services” and, indeed, the ‘wider’ remit in the framework brings a misalignment that needs to be resolved.

There are ten “strands” to ANCIL, containing 31 “content” areas, with the content areas containing 65 “learning outcomes”. To focus my critical appraisal and the IL lens through which the digital competency frameworks will be distilled, I will need to refine ANCIL to the aims of this study. As such, I will critically analyse each strand in turn, discarding, expanding, and merging strands as is appropriate to a lecturing population and the Chartered Institute of Library and Information Professionals (2004) definition of IL, which is broadly to identifying an information need, where to find that information, how to evaluate, manage, and communicate that information in an ethical manner. I should note that all citations of ANCIL have merely noted its existence and do not critically appraise the framework. The lack of critical appraisal further reinforces that this work is my own, although I will triangulate my changes to ANCIL with the wider-academic literature.

4.5.2 Strand 1: Transition from school to higher education

Strand content	Learning outcomes
What are the expectations at higher education level in your discipline?	Distinguish between the expectations at school and HE level in your discipline Recognise that learning at HE is different and requires different strategies Identify and assess the range of information formats available
What are the conventions around reading, writing and presenting at higher education level in your discipline?	Develop an awareness of academic conventions at HE level Assess your reading, writing and presenting skills and compare them to experts within your discipline
Reflect on your current and previous information behaviour – what’s different?	Critique the tools and strategies you currently use to find scholarly information Evaluate the information environment including libraries and digital libraries as ‘trusted’ collections

Strand name (bold) and content areas	Contextual information
Working in a scholarly environment	Appraisal of one’s own ability in a scholarly environment
Evaluate the information landscape	Landscape is defined as the various sources and formats of information
Assess your current information seeking behaviour	Critically evaluate how effectively you identify key types of information relevant to your discipline

Table 3. Transitioning Strand 1 of the ANCIL framework (left): Transition from school to higher education (Secker and Coonan, 2011, pp.9-10) to my lecturer version of the information literacy lens (right)

The focus of strands 1 (Table 3, lefthand side), 2, and 10 are on “learning to learn” (Secker and Coonan, 2011, p.4). As the title of strand 1 states, this is an introduction as to how learning at university differs from what an undergraduate student may have experienced in school or further education. As such, the strand content covers expectations in the discipline that the student has chosen, developing academic literacies (critical reading, writing, and presenting (Lea and Street, 2006)), and a reflection on information seeking behaviour. Given the transitional nature of strand 1 and the language used, one may be forgiven for immediately thinking that this content is not relevant to a university lecturer. However, when reflecting on the CILIP (2004) definition of IL, there is a starting point of identifying an information need and knowing the most appropriate tools and strategies to find that information. This content is not explicitly contained in other strands of ANCIL, so there is a requirement to modify the wording of strand 1 to encapsulate this content for a lecturer population.

My first strand will, therefore, become “Working in a scholarly environment” this references the academic workplace and the scholarship contract of most lecturers (Locke *et al.*, 2016), but also borrows the ‘environment’ language of ANCIL, other IL documentation (Working Group on Intersections of Scholarly Communication and Information Literacy, 2013), and academic literature (Palmer and Gelfand, 2013). I will draw out the important content areas of the ANCIL strand 1 relevant to lecturers by including two content areas of “Evaluate the information landscape” and “Assess your current information-seeking behaviour”. Contextual information for this strand and content areas can be seen on the right of Table 3.

4.5.3 Strand 2: Becoming an independent learner

Strand content	Learning outcomes
Learning to learn	Reflect on how to create strategies for assimilating new knowledge Identify your learning style and preferences, including specific learning needs
Affective dimension of information literacy	Critique the concept that learning changes the learner Acknowledge the emotional impact of learning on your worldview

Table 4. Strand 2 of the ANCIL framework: Becoming an independent learner (Secker and Coonan, 2011, p.10)

As discussed in strand 1, this second strand continues the transition from school to university education. While the learning outcomes are useful reflective points for all learners, including lecturers, the strand content is unique to ANCIL in that other IL frameworks do not include these concepts. This does not necessarily render the concepts irrelevant to lecturers. Indeed, reflective practice and “being able to facilitate students’ independent learning” are important factors in being a good university lecturer (Su and Wood, 2012, p.150). I will, therefore, omit this strand from my version for lecturers.

4.5.4 Strand 3: Developing academic literacies

Strand content	Learning outcomes
Academic writing, rhetoric and persuasive writing	Identify appropriate terminology, use of language and academic idiom in your discipline Identify overt and implicit techniques for influencing the reader/viewer in different arenas - in academic writing, in advertising, in the media Develop an awareness of the epistemological structure and values in your discipline
Academic reading, critical analysis and textual interrogation	Learn the techniques of skimming and scanning Identify the strengths and weaknesses of source material Evaluate [sic] the place of source material within the wider debate

Table 5. Strand 3 of the ANCIL framework: Developing academic literacies (Secker and Coonan, 2011, pp.10-11)

As discussed in strand 1, this third strand continues the transition from school to university education. While the learning outcomes are useful reflective points for all learners, including lecturers, the strand content is unique to ANCIL in that other IL frameworks do not include these concepts, see SCONUL (2011), for example. There is a reason that the strand content is omitted from other IL frameworks, in that responsibility for developing academic literacies usually sits with centralised departments (Murray, 2016) and not the library. The holistic perspective of ANCIL warrants this strand's inclusion within this framework and not other IL frameworks. I would tend to agree with the latter perspective, especially when considering the library-centric contextual constructionism methodology through which I am approaching this study. I will, therefore, omit this strand from the IL lens for lecturers.

4.5.5 Strand 4: Mapping and evaluating the information landscape

Strand content	Learning outcomes
Identify trusted source formats	Select appropriate resources for your assignment, discriminating between good quality academic sources and other sources Develop evaluative criteria for recognizing [sic] and selecting trustworthy sources of academic quality in your discipline
Who are the experts in the field? How do we know?	Identify the key experts in your field Analyse what makes an expert in your discipline
Evaluating source material and its appropriateness for your specific purpose	Use information sources appropriately to develop or support your argument Develop evaluative criteria for assessing ways of using source material in your work

Strand name (bold) and content areas	Contextual information
Mapping and evaluating the information landscape	Developing awareness and understanding of the range of source types available and how to evaluate them for reliability, authority and their appropriateness for a specific purpose
Critically evaluate source material	Develop evaluative criteria for recognising and selecting trustworthy sources in your discipline
Identify the key experts in your field	Identify experts and analyse what makes an expert in your discipline

Table 6. Transitioning Strand 4 of the ANCIL framework (left): Managing and evaluating the information landscape (Secker and Coonan, 2011, pp.11-12) to my lecturer version of the information literacy lens (right)

Strands 4 and 5 of ANCIL concern “Subject-specific competencies (navigating the information landscape, resource discovery)” (Secker and Coonan, 2011, p.9). The purpose of strand 4 is to familiarise a student with the range of sources of information that they will encounter as part of their studies (Secker and Coonan, 2011). These sources make the ‘landscape’ and could be anything from textbooks and monographs, journal articles and conference proceedings, code and data, musical scores and film, through to people, and these sources could be accessed in any number of ways. For a lecturer, many of the lower-level competencies will be known through previous study, through use of the Vitae Researcher Development Framework (Vitae and Careers Research and Advisory Centre, 2011), for example, and professional experience (Nicholas *et al.*, 2010). However, an information landscape evolves and there are higher-order skills that are still relevant to lecturers, such as the critical evaluation of source material and identifying expertise in a discipline. As such, I feel that the competencies in this strand should reflect those higher-order skills and I will amend the content as can be seen in on the righthand side of Table 6.

4.5.6 Strand 5: Resource discovery in your discipline

Strand content	Learning outcomes
Using key findings aids in your discipline	Identify key finding aids in your discipline - e.g. catalogues, full-text databases, abstract and indexing services Develop strategies for using them
Going beyond the key finding aids	Identify subject-specific collections of information such as gateways and portals Develop strategies for using them
Finding and using specialist forms of information	Identify the types of specialist information common in your discipline – e.g. datasets, statistics, archival evidence Develop strategies for using them, including awareness of sources of expert help
Finding and using people as information sources	Identify the strengths of people in your personal network – peers, academic staff, and others – as sources of information Evaluate the strengths of inline [sic] user-generated content as sources of information

Strand name (bold) and content areas	Contextual information
Resource discovery in your discipline	Intended to familiarise lecturers with specialist resources of various types and content in their discipline
Identify key finding aids in your discipline	Examples could include: catalogues, full text databases, abstract and indexing services
Develop resource discovery search strategies and techniques	Develop search strategies and techniques for finding information on finding aids and subject specific collections
Identify subject specific collections of information	Examples could include: gateways and subject portals/websites
Identify the types of specialist information common in your discipline	Examples could include: datasets, statistics, archival evidence

Table 7. Transitioning Strand 5 of the ANCIL framework (left): Resource discovery in your discipline (Secker and Coonan, 2011, pp.12-13) to my lecturer version of the information literacy lens (right)

Strand 5 of ANCIL continues the theme of finding and using subject-specific information sources. Both the identification of appropriate resources and the effective retrieval of information from these sources are core library competencies featured prominently in library education programmes (Corrall, 2010). Given identification of appropriate sources and employing effective information retrieval strategies are two separate competencies, I intend to slightly modify this strand to give both prominence. This modification provides a closer alignment with other IL frameworks. For example, in (SCONUL, 2011) one of the frameworks used to inform ANCIL, there are competencies to “Define a search strategy...”, “Select the most appropriate search tool”, and “Identify specialist search tools...” (p.7), these competencies clearly demarcate the ‘identify’ and ‘utilise’ components of information retrieval. I have, therefore, split the strand as per the SCONUL competencies and illustrated in on the righthand side of Table 7. The final modification is to resolve a duplication in ANCIL where people or experts as information sources appear in Strand 4. While the context of the competencies from Strands 4 and 5 are slightly different, identification of expertise and utilising said expertise, respectively, in the interests of brevity in the IL lens and not wishing to overbear participants, I will combine both as appears on the righthand side of Table 7.

4.5.7 Strand 6: Managing information

Strand content	Learning outcomes
Note-taking	Distinguish between note-taking (dictation) and notemaking (considered retention of vital points) Develop a strategy for note-making - in lectures/supervisions, for your reading, in everyday situations
Time management and planning	Produce a strategy to manage your workload Evaluate your own learning and working styles
Storing information effectively	Develop and implement a plan for organising your files (including naming and organising folders) Decide on an appropriate information management technique suitable for your discipline / the resources you use
Bibliographic and reference management	Identify and use an appropriate citation style in your assignments Construct appropriate bibliographies for your assignments Evaluate reference management tools and strategies in the light of your own workflow
Push services / alerting / keeping up to date	Develop appropriate strategies for current awareness in your field

Strand name (bold) and content areas	Contextual information
Managing Information	Practical, functional skills to find, select, manage and process academic information efficiently.
Develop information management Techniques	Methods of organising files, naming conventions and folder organisation
Utilise reference management Tools	Examples can include EndNote, RefWorks and Mendeley
Develop appropriate strategies for current awareness	Current awareness is defined as keeping abreast of developments in a field

Table 8. Transitioning Strand 6 of the ANCIL framework (left): Managing information (Secker and Coonan, 2011, pp.13-14) to my lecturer version of the information literacy lens (right)

In ANCIL, Strand 6 sits alone and is not conjoined with other strands. Information management is one of the attributes named as an area of “professional expertise” within the CILIP Professional Knowledge and Skills Base (CILIP, 2016, n.p.). There is no question, therefore, as to the appropriateness of information management as a competency in an IL framework. However, some of the competencies in the ANCIL framework focus on the related, but separate, academic literacies model. Note taking, for example, is a component of Lea and Street’s (2006) Academic Literacies Model. As with previous strands, this represents the holistic nature of ANCIL, whereas the focus of my work is on core IL competencies relevant to a lecturer population. I have, therefore, decided that whilst time management and planning and note taking are key skills, regardless of the level of one’s experience, that these should be excluded from my version of the framework, as illustrated on the righthand side of Table 8. I have also aligned the language used with that of other IL frameworks, SCONUL (2011) for example, again, representing the IL aspects of the lens.

4.5.8 Strand 7: Ethical dimension of information

Strand content	Learning outcomes
Attribution and avoiding plagiarism	Identify the steps you can take to avoid plagiarism, deliberate or inadvertent Use correct academic practices in quoting, citing and paraphrasing
Sharing information appropriately	Summarise the key ways you can use and share information without infringing another's rights Distinguish between collaboration and collusion Compare dissemination practices in your discipline across a range of publication platforms (preprint repositories, blogs, bibliographic sharing services etc.)
Awareness of copyright and IPR issues	Develop an awareness of how copyright and IPR issues impact on your work Develop strategies as appropriate for working within the legal framework

Strand name (bold) and content areas	Contextual information
Ethical dimension of information	Ethical dimension of information use and production.
Develop an awareness of copyright and IPR issues	This can also include Creative Commons licensing
Compare dissemination practices in your discipline	Examination of how information is disseminated across disciplines. Examples could include preprint repositories, blogs, bibliographic sharing services, etc.

Table 9. Transitioning Strand 7 of the ANCIL framework (left): Ethical dimension of information (Secker and Coonan, 2011, pp.14) to my lecturer version of the information literacy lens (right)

Strands 7, 8 and 9 of ANCIL concern how one disseminates information appropriately and ethically. As with many elements of the ANCIL strands and those that form the IL lens for this research, there is an overlap with academic literacies. Strand 7 focuses on ethical practices in disseminating information. The first area of competence in ANCIL is plagiarism. While there are nuances to what constitutes plagiarism in different contexts, this is an area that lecturers should be competent in. Using appropriate attribution of, say, images in a presentation is more complex, but this is fundamentally a copyright issue, and that competence is covered elsewhere in Strand 7. I have, therefore, decided to remove the “Attribution and avoiding plagiarism” content. The competencies listed under “Sharing information appropriately” also concerns copyright and intellectual property rights (IPR), “...share information without infringing another's rights” (p.14). I have, therefore, decided to focus this content on the learning outcome focussing on dissemination practices, as this is a key IL concept that many academics struggle with (McVay *et al.*, 2016).

Finally, I have merged the Creative Commons licensing¹ of content and its reuse into the “Awareness of copyright and IPR issues” strand content, as illustrated on the righthand side of Table 9.

¹ Creative Commons licenses are a method by which individuals can give permission for re-use of their work under certain conditions under copyright law. See <https://creativecommons.org/about/ccllicenses/> for further information.

4.5.9 Strand 8: Presenting and communicating knowledge and Strand 9: Synthesising information and creating new knowledge

Strand 8 content	Learning outcomes	Strand name (bold) and content areas	Contextual information
Finding your voice	Use language appropriately in your academic writing Analyse competing arguments and the use of evidence to justify a position	Presenting and communicating knowledge	High-order cognitive and intellectual functions of information handling, such as communicating your findings appropriately
Managing your online identity and digital footprint	Develop an awareness of how you appear to others online Decide on appropriate level of information to communicate to different audiences (ie [sic] manage your digital footprint) Evaluate the suitability of different online locations / tools for your online presence	Identify publication methods within your discipline	Formal and informal methods of publishing research findings in your discipline
Communicating your findings appropriately	Choose an appropriate writing style, level and format for your intended audience Summarise the key methods of publishing research findings in your discipline (including self-publication, e.g. blogging) Assess the relationship between writing style, audience and publication platform	Identify publication sources within your discipline	Choose an appropriate writing style, level, format and source for your intended audience and the desired impact of the research findings
Strand 9 content	Learning outcomes		
Formulating research questions and framing problems	Use chosen information sources to articulate and analyse new problems in your field		
Assimilating information within the disciplinary framework	Assess the value of new information objectively in the context of your work Develop new insights and knowledge in your discipline		

Table 10. Transitioning Strand 8 of the ANCIL framework (left): Presenting and communicating knowledge (Secker and Coonan, 2011, pp.14-15) and Strand 9: Synthesising information and creating new knowledge (Secker and Coonan, 2011, pp.15) to my lecturer version of the information literacy lens (right)

Strand 8 of ANCIL is titled presenting and communicating knowledge. The communication element of the strand, specifically the learning outcome to “Summarise the key methods of publishing research findings in your discipline (including self-publication, e.g. blogging)” (p.15) overlaps with the content area of Strand 7, “Compare dissemination practices in your discipline across a range of publication platforms (preprint repositories, blogs, bibliographic sharing services etc.)” (p.14). Strand 7 may focus on the ethical issues surrounding “sharing information appropriately” (p.14) and how to evaluate the range of appropriate academic outputs. From a lecturing and practice dissemination perspective, these are important content areas that need to be differentiated. ANCIL includes a learning outcome in Strand 8 to “Decide on appropriate level of information to communicate to different audiences”; this is included in the content area of “Managing your online identity and digital footprint”. I think this is misguided as informal communication and publication does not necessarily have to be digital. I believe that SCONUL (2011), for example, handles this content better in their IL framework as it simply acknowledges “a variety of formats” and to “select appropriate publications and dissemination outlets in which to publish if appropriate” (p.11). I will, therefore, align my version of this strand with the SCONUL IL framework, as illustrated on the right of Table 10.

Strand 8 of ANCIL also contains content on digital identity; this reflects the holistic nature of ANCIL. IL frameworks containing elements of DL are not common but are also not unique to ANCIL. SCONUL (2011), for example, contains content on developing an online profile. However, whilst seen occasionally within IL frameworks, the concept of digital identity appears consistently in national (European Commission (Ferrari, 2013)), university (Jisc (Beetham, 2017)), and local DL frameworks (Leicester City Council, 2013). Developing a digital profile is, therefore, a concept that I will remove from my IL framework.

Lastly, in both Strands 8 and 9 there are elements of academic literacies, features of which have been seen earlier in ANCIL, namely conceptualising research questions and problems, and integrating information within one’s discipline. These content areas have been seen in Strands 3, 4, and 5 of ANCIL and my IL framework. ANCIL describes the aim of Strand 3 as “develop academic literacies” (p.4), and Strand 4 and 5 as “dealing with subject-specific information” (p.5). With Strands 7, 8, and 9

dealing “with the high-order cognitive and intellectual functions of information handling”. Given that my framework focuses on the high-order elements of IL that are relevant to lecturers, I intend to merge these concepts in Strand 9 wholly into the concepts concerning publication methods and sources in Strand 8, as illustrated on the right of Table 10.

4.5.10 Strand 10: Social dimension of information

Strand content	Learning outcomes
Becoming a lifelong learner	Develop an awareness that learning is a continuous ongoing process outside of formal educational establishments Develop strategies for assimilating new information to the conceptual framework
Information handling, problem solving and decision making in the workplace	Transfer the skills of finding, critically evaluating, and deploying information to the workplace
Information handling, problem solving and decision making in your daily life	Transfer the skills of finding, critically evaluating, and deploying information to daily life
Ethics and politics of information	Develop strategies for assimilating and analysing new information, including that which challenges your world view

Strand name (bold) and content areas	Contextual information
Social dimension of information	Actionable knowledge in the workplace and daily life
Actionable knowledge in the workplace and daily life	Develop strategies for disseminating new information and knowledge in the workplace and life outside of the university environment
Information handling, problem solving and decision making in the workplace	Develop strategies and transfer skills for finding information in the workplace and life outside of the university environment

Table 11. Transitioning Strand 10 of the ANCIL framework (left): Synthesising information and creating new knowledge (Secker and Coonan, 2011, pp.15-16) to my lecturer version of the information literacy lens (right)

Strand 10 in ANCIL completes the information literacy cycle, where one communicates or translates their findings to different fora, reflects on their learning and the original information need, and the cycle begins again (Keene, Colvin and Sissons, 2010). In ANCIL, the focus is on a graduate student transitioning to the workplace and the IL cycle from the perspective of information in “daily life”. The “social dimension of information” as ANCIL labels this strand, may be relevant to the lecturer as a person outside of their university, but less directly relevant to their work. There is, however, an increasing need for actionable knowledge and knowledge transfer within universities (Howell and Annansingh, 2013). Actionable knowledge is where one imparts academic knowledge into a context that has “direct impact” on the wider world (Denyer and Tranfield, 2006, p.213), with knowledge transfer referring to the process by which one creates then conveys said knowledge outside of the academy (Krause and Schupp, 2019). I will, therefore, merge the ANCIL strand content to reflect how this content may present itself as within the context of working as a university lecturer (right of Table 11).

4.6 Digital literacy frameworks used in a sample of UK universities

In the previous section I proposed an IL framework that will be used as a lens to distil digital competencies relevant to lecturers in a UK university context. To distil the digital competencies, I need to first identify which DL frameworks are used in UK universities. I will then reconcile the DL frameworks in the next phase of the research.

To recap the methods of identifying the DL frameworks, I assigned each public university in the UK a number based on an alphabetical listing, then used a random number generator to select ten universities. I then searched the websites of each university identified using the terms 'digital literacy' and 'information literacy' and also browsed their publications, library, learning technology, and student support service webpages for relevant information to elicit what framework or frameworks were used. The universities identified and the frameworks used in each is shown in Table 12.

University	Framework used (Oct 2018)
University of Bristol	Not explicitly stated, but references to Jisc and SCONUL
University of Sussex	Not explicitly stated, but references to Jisc
Nottingham Trent University	Explicit reference to Jisc framework embedded in practice and linked as a resource
Anglia Ruskin	Bespoke framework, informed by Jisc and EC DigComp
Ulster University	Explicit reference to Jisc framework
Bath Spa University	Digital programme funded by Jisc
The Open University	Bespoke framework, informed by Jisc
University of Wales, Trinity Saint David	Not explicitly stated
Northumbria University	Explicit use of Jisc framework
University of Sheffield	Bespoke framework, Jisc as starting point

Table 12. Sample universities and DL frameworks used in each

The investigation of university websites has revealed that most (9 of 10) UK universities use or refer to the Jisc DL framework (Beetham, 2017). This is not a surprise given the prominence of Jisc as an organisation throughout the UK

university network (Browne *et al.*, 2008). Reference was also made to the SCONUL (2016) (n=1) and the EC DigComp framework (Ferrari, 2013) (n=1). These three frameworks will, therefore, be used in the forthcoming phase two methods.

4.7 Chapter summary

This chapter started with an appraisal of the ANCIL IL framework, and I discussed how the framework relates to university lecturers in a UK university context. The holistic nature of ANCIL provided both an alignment with my methodological approach and challenges in translating the framework to be appropriate for lecturers. Many of the changes required as part of the translation process were modifications in language and context to bring ANCIL in alignment with the practices and knowledge requirements of lecturers rather than undergraduate students. Where these changes were required, I drew upon academic literature, grey literature from professional organisations, and other IL frameworks to ensure the appropriate context was achieved.

This chapter also provided a sample of DL frameworks used within UK universities. This sample highlighted the prevalence of the Jisc DL framework in the UK university sector. The sample also revealed two alternative DL frameworks, SCONUL and EC DigComp. These three frameworks will be harmonised and distilled through the ANCIL IL lens as explained in the following chapter.

5 What competencies do university lecturers need to demonstrate digital competence? Views of Lecturers, Librarians, and Learning Technologists

5.1 Introduction to chapter

The previous chapter revealed how I felt information literacy concepts related to lecturers, and what digital literacy frameworks are in use in a sample of UK universities. This phase of the research will explore how knowledge of information literacy and digital competence is contextualised and constructed from the perspectives of lecturers, librarians, and learning technologists, and myself.

5.2 Aims and research questions

In this chapter I will detail how I intend to undertake workshops to form a multi-professional approach to university lecturer digital competence. The aim of the workshops is to discover, through an information literacy lens, the digital competencies relevant to university lecturers.

The workshops will address the following research questions:

- What digital competencies do I feel are relevant to university lecturers, and why?
- Which of these digital competencies do I believe are relevant to information literacy, and why?
- What digital competencies do a multi-professional group of lecturers, learning technologists, and librarians feel are relevant to university lecturers, and why?
- Which of these digital competencies are relevant to information literacy, and why?

5.3 Research methods

5.3.1 Sampling of universities

Lecturers, librarians, and learning technologists will be sampled from two UK universities. The two universities have been convenience sampled. I have a good understanding of the teaching and research cultures in both universities and a professional relationship with individuals that can provide access to gatekeepers for the lecturers, librarians, and learning technologists. Both universities have

appropriate facilities for the workshops to take place and are within reasonable travel distance for me.

One of the universities is a Million+ university (University A), and the other a Russell Group university (University B). While I do not intend to compare findings across the universities, having two different institutions will make the sample more representative of the UK university landscape.

Given a prior relationship with both universities, I will need to take certain steps to ensure my objectivity as a researcher and to minimise any bias or risk of coercion when contacting potential participants. The steps I have taken are interwoven throughout this chapter with overarching considerations detailed in section 5.3.6, ethical considerations.

5.3.2 Sampling of participants

5.3.2.1 Lecturers

The lecturer sample was drawn from those who had published outputs or presented at conferences on their experiences of using digital technology in their teaching practice. A purposive sample was chosen where “the sample provides clear examples of the issue in question” (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2011, p.157). In this case, the issue in question is lecturer understanding of digital competence and its relation to academic practices. I believe that these lecturers will more probably be familiar with the digital competency frameworks used in this and the previous phase of the research and be better able to conceptually understand digital competence than if lecturers were selected through random sampling.

Lecturers were chosen by searching for the word “digital” in each university’s research repository; both repositories applied automatic word stemming (or truncation) whereby words such as “digitally” or “digitals” were also retrieved. The total number of results was 38 in University B and 76 in University A. The results were then cross-checked against the staff directories at each university and filtered to the relevant sample populations i.e., not research-only staff, students, or where the author was no longer working at the university. Finally, the exported results were filtered to lecturers whose research described digital literacy frameworks (n=0 across both universities) or the employment of digital technology within the curriculum (n=14 University B, n=11 University A), filtering out lecturers whose research was on

computer hardware and software i.e., digital computation or computer chips. Lecturers were then scored on whether their research discussed the embedding of technology in the curricula (two points) and where the use of technology was a secondary intervention or outcome (one point). The scoring allowed a priority order to be established for recruitment purposes.

While a purposive sample is a biased one, by focussing on lecturers that are innovators and early adopters (Rogers, 2003), I achieved a sample with experience of the knowledge stage of innovation or technology, whereby they will have the awareness of technology and potentially the frameworks that underpin their pedagogical use, the knowledge how-to “use an innovation correctly”, and the principles knowledge of “describing how and why an innovation works” (Sahin, 2006, p.16). Including later adopters of technology by random sampling may have excluded those with the necessary knowledge to actively participate in the workshops. On a practical level, later adopters would probably have required more peer support in the workshops, taking away time from the exercise and thereby potentially effecting the validity of the results if workshop outputs were partially complete.

5.3.2.2 Learning technologists and librarians

Librarians and learning technologists were selected using the same purposive sampling technique as the lecturers. In the case of librarians and learning technologists, the purposive sampling was also a near-complete sample. Learning technologists and librarians were recruited in order of those who worked closest to the campus where the workshops were organised. I assumed that knowledge of information and digital literacy concepts and frameworks would be widespread in learning technologists and librarians, with these skills being foundational for librarians, for example (Chartered Institute of Library and Information Professionals, n.d.).

5.3.3 Workshop sampling

To allow active and “genuine participation” (Ørngreen and Levinsen, 2017, p.72) in the workshops, the groups were kept to small numbers. One workshop at each university was scheduled with a sample size of four librarians and two learning technologists (both near-complete samples). To balance the lecturer sample with the

professional service staff, a sample of six lecturers was also chosen. I chose a balanced sample to allow the lecturer voice to be heard in equal weight to the professional services, given the research aim to investigate digital competencies from a lecturer perspective. I also believed a total sample of 12 lecturers to be viable, yet challenging, with a total sample of 25, and feasible with respect of managing the workshops and encouraging genuine participation from all involved. Should recruitment fall short of the desired numbers, a back-up method of interviews to complete the sample size was agreed and ethically approved in principle but, at this stage, not planned. Using interviews as a 'back-up' method was a pragmatic step to maintain the viability of the research study, although a clear limitation with interviews is that they lose the valuable interdisciplinary and cross-professional collaboration (Eigenbrode *et al.*, 2007) allowed in a workshop format.

5.3.3.1 Participant recruitment

Following ethical approval for the study (UWS reference 2018-1756-2269, application 1756), a date for the workshop in each of the universities was selected by the researcher in consultation with the academic calendar and the research supervisors. Potential participants were emailed six weeks in advance of the workshop with information on the study ([Appendix 3](#)) along with a Participant Information Sheet and Consent Form (see [Appendix 4](#) and [Appendix 5](#), respectively).

In University A, four librarians and two learning technologists accepted the invitation to participate in the workshop on 9 April 2018. However, of the lecturer sample, only two of a potential 11 participants accepted the invitation. Two additional potential lecturer participants were willing to participate but could not make the scheduled date; both agreed to be interviewed at a later date. As a result of not being able to complete the lecturer sample, an additional lecturer was sampled due to their expertise and knowledge in the field of digital literacy, a reputational, purposive sample method (Daniel, 2012); this change to the sampling method was also ethically approved.

In University B, three librarians and two learning technologists accepted the invitation to participate in the workshop on 16 April 2018, but one librarian withdrew prior to the workshop itself. Only one lecturer was able to participate, with seven willing to

participate in an interview. An additional round of lecturer sampling was conducted using the same initial sampling criteria, but on abstracts submitted to the university's Learning and Teaching Conference, scheduled after the initial sampling method and one month prior to the workshop. Sixteen potential lecturer participants were identified, of which four were able to participate in the workshop, and a further two agreed to be interviewed. On the day of the workshop, four lecturers attended from the five who accepted the invitation.

The same additional round of sampling using the abstracts from University A's Learning and Teaching Conference was used and an additional nine potential lecturer participants were identified. An additional workshop was scheduled at University A in an attempt to complete the workshop sample, but only one lecturer could attend; this workshop was cancelled. A second workshop at University B was scheduled on 6 June 2018 where potential interview candidates were invited; one librarian and three lecturers agreed to attend. Regrettably, shortly before the workshop was due to take place, two lecturers had to withdraw; this workshop proceeded with the two participants.

5.3.3.2 Characteristics of participants

While the sample was only constructed based on a participant's profession and knowledge of digital literacies or experience of using digital tools in their lecturing, the discipline of each participant was also noted as this may be a factor on which the research outcomes are judged – if for instance a large proportion of participants were from one particular discipline or subject categorisation. The disciplines illustrated in Tables 13, 14, and 15 have been categorised according to the Field of Science and Technology (FOS) Classification in the Frascati Manual (2017) in order to give a degree of anonymity to the participants and the two universities in which the study was conducted.

Profession	Discipline	Group reference
Learning Technologist	Engineering and technology	Group A
Learning Technologist	Social sciences	Group B
Lecturer	Medical and health sciences	Group B
Lecturer	Social sciences	Group A
Lecturer	Social sciences	Group B
Librarian	Engineering and technology	Group A
Librarian	Medical and health sciences	Group A
Librarian	Social sciences	Group A
Librarian	Humanities	Group B

Table 13. Participants in University A by profession, discipline, and workshop group

Profession	Discipline	Group reference
Learning Technologist	Engineering and technology	Group C
Learning Technologist	Social sciences	Group D
Lecturer	Humanities	Group C
Lecturer	Humanities	Group D
Lecturer	Agricultural sciences	Group C
Lecturer	Medical and health sciences	Group D
Lecturer	Natural sciences	Group E
Librarian	Humanities	Group C
Librarian	Humanities	Group E
Librarian	Social sciences	Group D

Table 14. Participants in University B by profession, discipline, and workshop group

Profession	Discipline	Group reference	University
Learning Technologist	Engineering and technology	Group A	A
Learning Technologist	Engineering and technology	Group C	B
Learning Technologist	Social sciences	Group B	A
Learning Technologist	Social sciences	Group D	B
Lecturer	Agricultural sciences	Group C	B
Lecturer	Humanities	Group C	B
Lecturer	Humanities	Group D	B
Lecturer	Medical and health sciences	Group B	A
Lecturer	Medical and health sciences	Group D	B
Lecturer	Natural sciences	Group E	B
Lecturer	Social sciences	Group A	A
Lecturer	Social sciences	Group B	A
Librarian	Engineering and technology	Group A	A
Librarian	Humanities	Group B	A
Librarian	Humanities	Group C	B
Librarian	Humanities	Group E	B
Librarian	Medical and health sciences	Group A	A
Librarian	Social sciences	Group A	A

Table 15. Combined participants by profession, discipline, workshop group and university

5.3.4 Data collection methods

5.3.4.1 Room set-up

Participants were pre-assigned seats around two tables, one for each workshop group, in a banquet style (two rectangular tables placed together, with chairs evenly spaced around the outside). The banquet style has been noted as being “a good form for small participatory workshops” (Chambers, 2002, p.91). The seating plan, organised per group (see Table 15), gave as proportional as possible representation from the three professional groups and a spread of disciplines across each table. In practice, participants found it easier to stand for the exercise. An unintended outcome of standing was that the workshops became more democratic as “several people can take part simultaneously without any individual in control as part of a self-organizing system” (Chambers, 2002, p.94).

5.3.4.2 Ground rules and introduction

I welcomed each participant upon arrival and, when everyone had arrived, a set of slides (available at <https://dx.doi.org/10.5255/UKDA-SN-855937>) were used to re-introduce the ground rules and the option to withdraw from the study at any point, without discrimination. The slides were then used to introduce and visualise the workshop task.

5.3.4.3 Workshop materials

Each group had two A1 sheets displaying the information literacy facets from my modified version of the ANCIL framework created in phase one. Each group also had two A4 sheets, one labelled 'Supplementary' and the other 'Not required'. A randomly shuffled pack of 66 digital competencies taken directly from the three digital literacy frameworks was also supplied. Each competency was printed on sticky-backed paper (address labels) with a colour coded border around the competency. The colour code was not revealed to the participants until the end of the workshop. The colour codes are blue for the EC 'DigComp' framework, orange for the Jisc 'Building digital capabilities' framework, and green for the SCONUL '7 pillars of information literacy through a digital literacy lens' framework. Interestingly, only two participants noticed the colour codes, indicating that the colours had no unintended influence on the workshop outcomes. The two participants that did notice the colours were informed that the colours would be revealed at the close of the workshop. Finally, each group had a set of coloured pens to annotate their worksheets as required. Copies of the workshop materials can be found at <https://dx.doi.org/10.5255/UKDA-SN-855937>.

5.3.4.4 Workshop task

Each group was asked to work as an interdisciplinary and multi-profession group to discuss the competencies and what they believe the competency entails. The groups then stuck the competency to the information facet, or facets, where they believe the competency related to. In cases where the group thought that the competency was relevant to a lecturer population, but that it did not relate to information literacy, or at least to the information literacies described on the worksheet, the group were asked to stick the competency on the 'Supplementary' sheet with an annotation as to their reasoning. Similarly, if the group decided that a competency in question is not

relevant to a lecturer population, they stuck it on the 'Not required' sheet, again, with appropriate annotation.

Groups were asked to discuss each competency and progress through as many competencies that they could within the one hour allocated to the workshop. Importantly, groups were informed that I was interested in their analysis of the competencies and their relation to information literacy, and completing the task was less of a priority than exploring the relationship between the digital competencies and information literacy.

5.3.4.5 My analysis, group discussion, and debrief

Prior to the workshops, I undertook the same exercise, the results of which are presented alongside the workshop groups (Figure 6 and 9). I also provided a reflective discussion to contextualise my undertaking (5.5.3). My analysis of the task allowed me to pilot the exercise for timing and feasibility. This analysis also provided a measure of reliability and triangulation with the work groups. Equally, from a methodological perspective, an understanding of my approach to the exercise and how I construct my knowledge will be revealed.

Ten minutes before the end of the workshops, I drew the exercise to a close and offered each table a chance to feedback their experiences to the room. All participants were then asked to reflect on my analysis in phase one and the similarities and differences between their analysis and mine.

5.3.5 Internal and external validity of the sample and data collection methods

The trustworthiness of this phase has been gained via the sampling of an expert group with experience of digital competence. Prior to reading the findings chapter, you may wish to refamiliarise yourself with my reflexivity and methodology sections (1.2 and 2.1, respectively). Internal reliability was low; this is discussed in the subsequent findings section. Including participant feedback on my undertaking of the exercise is akin to peer-debriefing and member checking suggested by Lincoln and Guba (1985). Peer-debriefing involved a disinterested third party, on an equal level of seniority and experience to me, providing honest feedback and cross-examination. While the workshop participants were not disinterested third parties, they are not directly impacted by the research beyond their contribution to the workshop. Nonetheless, the feedback received appeared to be open and honest and is

discussed further in the following chapter. Equally, by employing member checking through eliciting feedback received from participants, a measure of validation was achieved with my findings, while also correcting any factual errors I had made in my observances of the workshop exercise (Creswell, 2012). There were a number of limitations in the member checking that are explained in section 5.5.2.

All data from the workshops was collated on worksheets, as previously described. The worksheets provided a valid, participatory method to “express and analyse complexity in ways that words alone cannot” (Chambers, 2002, p.136). The worksheets were latterly digitised and analysed in NVivo 12 (QSR International Pty Ltd, 2018). NVivo 12 was chosen for its ability to collate the worksheets in one piece of software, allowing me to effectively analyse data from multiple working locations. Practically, my university provided both IT support and training in NVivo 12. If I had used other qualitative analysis software, I would have had to be self-taught and had limited to no technical support.

External validity has been gained through the rich dataset and thick description advised by Lincoln and Guba (1985) and Cohen, Manion and Morrison (2011). The representativeness of stakeholders in digital literacies in the sampling has provided a reliable, fair and comprehensive coverage of the research questions, and ensured that multiple professional interests in digital and information literacies has been represented.

5.3.6 Ethical considerations

This research will be guided by the ethical principles for library and information professionals (Chartered Institute of Library and Information Professionals, 2015), in particular the principles of equity, impartiality and avoidance of inappropriate bias, and respect for confidentiality and privacy of information users. Whilst the CILIP ethical principles are primarily concerned with information users and uses, these principles can be readily translated to the research environment and other scenarios. Given the environment in which the research will be conducted, I will also be guided by the Ethical Guidelines for Educational Research as set out by the British Educational Research Association (British Educational Research Association, 2011).

Written permission to proceed with this research study was received by the school ethics committee of University A in November 2017 ([Appendix 6](#)). Permission

granted to proceed with the study at University B was based on approval from University A ([Appendix 7](#)). Following ethics committee approval, the heads of departments of potential participants were emailed asking for access to their staff, all approved access.

Potential participants were emailed one month ahead of the scheduled workshops with information of the research, a participant information sheet, and a consent form. Potential participants were encouraged to contact me with any questions, although no one did. The contact period before the workshops gave adequate time for participants to understand the research aims, consent freely, and contact me with any questions or concerns.

Potential participants were given information on their right to freely withdraw from the study prior to and within the workshops; this was reiterated in the presentation prior to the workshops commencing (presentation available at <https://dx.doi.org/10.5255/UKDA-SN-855937>). Potential participants were, however, informed that due to the participatory nature of the workshop exercise and the anonymity of the exercise data that, should they withdraw during the workshop, their data could not be redacted.

An assumption will be made that lecturers and workshop participants are able to consent for themselves. To aid readability and reduce the likelihood of an acquiescent response (Bowling, 2014), I kept the participant information sheet and consent forms at a maximum of 1250 words (participant information sheet was 530 words and consent form 180 words) and a Flesch-Kincaid reading score between 60 and 70 (40.6 achieved (reading level of a 17-18 year old)) to enable information to be “readable by an average literate reader” (Biggs and Marchesi, 2015, p.135).

In the case of some potential participants, I had (and in some cases continue to have) a professional working connection. At no time has this been a management relationship with any potential participants. This close relationship may have led to situations where potential participants did find it difficult to refuse to take part in the study. I was clear in the participant information sheet that participants were free to withdraw from the study at any time and without detriment to current or future relationships with me. In practice, one person declined the invitation. I restated my

neutrality at the start of each workshop and that my role in the workshops was that of a neutral researcher, helping reduce any authority gradient.

The workshops were located within suitable private rooms within each university, allowing participants the space to be open and relaxed within a familiar environment. The concept of workshops and participating in research will be routine for participants, and the environment provided a comfortable space for participants where they felt safe answering questions and were honest in their responses.

All data, including signed consent forms and workshop materials was digitised and stored in a password protected, GDPR compliant, OneDrive folder (Microsoft corporation). The password to access this folder conforms to the standards outlined by Aldridge, Medina and Ralphs (2010). The only personal data relating to the workshops is the collation of email correspondence and digitally signed consent forms. All data will be retained for 10 years, post-completion of this doctorate.

This study has been self-funded.

5.4 Introduction to findings

The previous section detailed how I will move from the phase one findings to utilising the ANCIL appraisal and digital literacy frameworks as workshop materials. In phase one I critically appraised the ANCIL IL framework and discovered DL frameworks in use in UK universities. This section will reflect on the workshop process before analysing the outputs from the workshop exercise.

5.5 Overview of the workshops

To briefly recap, one workshop was held in University A that was attended by nine people. The nine people were divided into two groups, Group A and Group B. Two workshops were held in University B. These two workshops were attended by eight people, Group C and Group D, and two people, Group E, respectively. The characteristics of all groups are provided in Table 15.

5.5.1 Observations on the workshop introduction and exercise

Each group in both universities were treated the same; I introduced each workshop using the same set of slides and each group had the same worksheets and materials. Completed worksheets are available at <https://dx.doi.org/10.5255/UKDA-SN-855937>.

While both universities have different approaches and policies to teaching and learning, I did not note any differences in how each workshop group approached the task or the questions asked at the beginning or during the exercise. All groups confirmed that they understood the exercise and worked well together, despite most people not knowing each other. The only question that occurred during the introduction in University A, where the first workshop was held, was whether the groups were expected to complete the exercise. I replied stating that I was interested in their reflections and combined experiences as a group so not to rush through the exercise to 'complete' it. I repeated this explanation when delivering the final workshop in University B. I also guided Group B back to this instruction when they started to work independently of each other, bring them back as a group to aid interdisciplinary discussion.

As the exercises progressed, there were a few questions about the IL facets and DL competencies. Group B, for example, asked for clarity as to what "current awareness", one of the IL facets, meant. In this instance I offered an example of table of contents alerts for new journal issues being published, but for other questions about the nature of the competencies, I asked the groups to discuss the meaning collaboratively within their individual groups to avoid biasing the findings.

Only one group asked what the colours of the competencies represented, the answer to which was revealed at the end of each workshop. When the colours and frameworks were revealed, a lecturer in Group E mentioned that "Jisc are not very specific", sentiment that was echoed in their worksheets where several of the Jisc competencies were placed outside of the facets to represent that these competencies could be placed in all facets rather than one or two specifically.

5.5.2 Observations on the group discussion and debrief

As discussed in the methods for this chapter, a peer-debrief and member check (Lincoln and Guba, 1985) followed each workshop. This allowed participants to feedback on the exercise that they universally found interesting, and provided internal reliability to my analysis of the same task. Participants appeared to be open and honest and confirmed the observations I made of the exercise, specifically that the Jisc competencies were difficult to map to a single facet because they contained different DL concepts in one competency. This phenomenon was not unique to the Jisc DL framework with competencies from all frameworks mapped to multiple IL facets. This mapping of single competencies to multiple IL facets is illustrated in Figure 3, taken from Group A's worksheet.

Figure 3. Part of Group A's worksheet showing DL competencies mapped to many different IL facets

While the reason for the multiple mappings was not uncovered in the debrief, when discussing the exercise, both groups in both universities contradicted each other depending on their perspective when interpreting a competence or facet. As an example, Group E had a narrow interpretation of the IL facet, “Develop information management techniques” so they also mapped competencies they understood as having a wider context to both this facet and the related “Utilise reference management tools” (Figure 4). Group D, however, mapped two of the same competencies exclusively to “Develop information management techniques” because they read both the facet and competencies as having a narrow focus (Figure 5).

Figure 4. Group E mapping competencies to two IL facets

Figure 5. Group D mapping two of the same competencies to a single IL facet

The feedback across all groups was that the EC DigComp competencies were the easiest to read and interpret, with Jisc the most difficult to follow due to the many concepts in each of their competencies; this despite Jisc being used by nine of the ten universities in the sample used in phase one.

5.5.3 Reflections on my undertaking of the exercise

My undertaking of the exercise can be seen in Figure 6. There are similarities between how I mapped the DL competencies to the IL facets. I too have mapped

several competencies to more than one facet, with this happening more frequently with the Jisc competencies. My feeling is that this pattern in mapping was less due to ambiguity in language or terminology, but rather due to the competencies not being specific enough or containing more than one concept in a competence. The Jisc competency, “The capacity to find, evaluate, manage, curate, organise and share digital information” is a good example. If IL is the ability to “recognize information needs and to locate, evaluate, apply and create information within cultural and social contexts” (IFLA, 2015), then this competence aligns to all areas of IL. As such, I would map this competency across all IL facets.

I did, however, also find many instances where language and terminology also resulted in competencies being mapped to several IL facets. As an example, I mapped the EC’s “Sharing information and content” to IL facets on the themes of dissemination practices, publication sources, and actionable knowledge. Where my analysis differed significantly from the workshop groups was that I deemed that 27 of the 66 competencies to be not relevant to university lecturers. Across all workshop groups, participants felt that a total of 16 of the competencies were not relevant to lecturers. This difference could be a reflection on me as an individual undertaking the exercise rather than multiple people across professional areas. I reflect further on this difference in section 5.6.2.

During the exercise, I further reflected upon my work in phase one, questioning my lecturer version of ANCIL and identifying edits when ruminating on the competencies. The exercise itself provoked further reflection on IL when approached through a DL lens.

5.5.4 Participant feedback on my analysis

As part of the peer debrief, I presented a narrative summary of my analysis with some questions for the groups based on my analysis (see slides 5-11, available at <https://dx.doi.org/10.5255/UKDA-SN-855937>). The workshop participants agreed that an element of ‘collaboration’ was missing from the IL facets, especially given the importance of collaboration for university lecturers (du Toit, de Boer and Bothma, 2010). Participants also provided a summary of their mappings in response to my questions on whether they had mapped competencies to particular facets, and these aligned with my discussion points.

However, the member checking was undertaken at the end of exercise to allow participants to reflect on the exercise while fresh in their minds. Whilst the member checking provided a positive level of internal validity, I did feel that, to some degree, an acquiescent response set was generated. I was conscious that the participants had undertaken a cognitively demanding exercise with peers that they had not met before, and that the exercises were scheduled during their lunch breaks. Participants likely had to leave to deliver lectures or other work and may have been mindful of the time. I am, therefore, cognisant of an observer bias (Bowling, 2014) and feel that the level of internal validity was likely lower than it initially appeared.

	Underpinning competencies	Working in a scholarly environment	Mapping and evaluating the information landscape	Resource discovery in your discipline	Managing information	Ethical dimension of information	Presenting and communicating knowledge	Social dimension of information	Supplementary	Not required
EC	Browsing, searching and filtering information									
	Collaborating through digital channels									
	Copyright and Licences									
	Developing content									
	Engaging in online citizenship									
	Evaluating Information									
	Identifying digital competence gaps									
	Identifying needs and technological responses									
	Innovating and creatively using technology									
	Integrating and re-elaborating									
Jisc	Interacting through technologies									
	Managing digital identity									
	Netiquette									
	Programming									
	Protecting devices									
	Protecting health									
	Protecting personal data									
	Protecting the environment									
	Sharing information and content									
	Solving technical problems									
SCONUL	Storing and retrieving information									
	The capacity to adopt and develop new practices with digital technology									
	The capacity to collate, manage, access and use digital data									
	The capacity to communicate effectively in digital media and spaces									
	The capacity to critically receive and respond to messages in a range of digital media									
	The capacity to design and/or create new digital artefacts and materials									
	The capacity to develop and project a positive digital identity or identities and to manage digital reputation									
	The capacity to find, evaluate, manage, curate, organise and share digital information									
	The capacity to look after personal health, safety, relationships and work-life balance in digital settings									
	The capacity to participate in and benefit from digital learning opportunities									
Jisc	The capacity to participate in digital teams and working groups									
	The capacity to participate in, facilitate and build digital networks									
	The capacity to support and develop others in digitally-rich settings									
	The capacity to use digital evidence to solve problems and answer questions									
	The use of ICT-based devices, applications, software and services									
	The use of ICT-based tools to carry out tasks effectively, productively, and with attention to quality									
	Access, read and download digital information and data									
	Assess different digital formats and select those to meet current need									
	Assess how online collaboration can enhance academic practice									
	Assess the quality, accuracy, relevance, credibility, format and accessibility of digital material									
SCONUL	Assess the suitability of digital content for the intended audience									
	Assess which form(s) of digital media best meets the criteria identified									
	Assign meta-data tags to content to enable future discoverability									
	Cite and reference electronic sources appropriately									
	Communicate effectively in a digital environment, using appropriate tools, to meet audience needs, taking account of accessibility issues									
	Confidently use the digital media appropriate for presentation									
	Continuously assess how the use of digital content and tools could enhance academic practice									
	Develop an online personal profile using appropriate networks and technologies									
	Engage in online collaboration and networking to access and share information									
	Identify appropriate online search techniques									
SCONUL	Identify gaps in knowledge relating to digital tools or content									
	Identify gaps relating to the use, application or development of digital environments and tools									
	Identify search tools for locating quality digital material									
	Manage digital resources effectively taking account of version control, file storage and record keeping issues									
	Maximise discoverability of own digital material using indexing strategies									
	Personalise the digital environment according to need									
	Read online information critically, taking into account access restrictions									
	Recognise the importance of skills in locating, creating managing and sharing information through a variety of digital forms									
	Recognise where digital solutions can meet a specific information task or need									
	Remotely access external digital sources in order to extend opportunities for discovery									
SCONUL	Select appropriate publication and dissemination outlets to share information									
	Stay safe and, if necessary, private in the digital world									
	Use a range of digital retrieval tools and technology effectively									
	Use appropriate tools to organise digital content and data (social bookmarking, bibliographic software)									
	Use different online communication approaches to extend reach									
	Use new tools and technologies as they become available and evaluate them for suitability									

Figure 6. My mapping of the digital competencies to information literacy facets

5.6 Analysis of group worksheets

Worksheets from each group were digitised and uploaded to NVivo 12 for analysis.

After the sheets were coded, the data was exported to Excel for Microsoft Office 365.

Figure 7 shows the combined mapping of the DL competencies (y-axis) to the IL facets (x-axis) for all groups.

Note: Y-axis: Framework name in bold text. X-axis: Information literacy facet categorical group in bold text.

Figure 7. Combined mapping of the digital competencies to information literacy facets for all groups

Figure 7 illustrates the lack of agreement between groups as to where each DL competence was mapped to IL facet. There was only one instance where all five groups mapped a DL competence, “Identify appropriate online search techniques” (from the SCONUL framework), to the same IL facet, “Develop resource discovery search strategies and techniques”. There were very few instances where four or three groups made the same mapping, as shown in Table 16.

Number of matches	Number of occurrences
5	1
4	4
3	13
2	37
1	202

Table 16. Number of times groups mapped DL competencies to the same IL facet

The reason for the lack of agreement was not uncovered in the debrief or the observations of the groups as they undertook the exercise. One possible explanation could be the different interpretation that the groups made of the different competencies and facets. This explanation is illustrated by the feeling that the Jisc competencies did not lend themselves to one single facet due to the way that the competencies are written. Indeed, by looking at the mean average number of facets that a competence is mapped to, Jisc competencies are mapped to a greater number of facets than the SCONUL and EC DigComp competencies (Table 17).

Framework name	Average occurrence of a DL competence mapped to an IL facet
EC DigComp	4.2
SCONUL	4.4
Jisc	7.5

Table 17. Mean average occurrence of a digital competence mapped to an IL facet by framework

Condensing the number of facets into their categorical groups similarly shows no agreement between groups. This means that not only were groups not mapping DL competencies to the same IL facet, but they were also not even mapping the competencies to similar categories (Figure 8 and Table 18).

Figure 8. Combined mapping of the digital competencies to information literacy facets, condensed to categorical groups, for all workshop groups

Number of matches	Number of occurrences when IL facets were categorically grouped	Number of occurrences initially (ungrouped)
6	6	-
5	7	1
4	13	4
3	18	13
2	32	37
1	95	202

Table 18. Number of times groups mapped DL competencies to the same IL facets, condensed to categorical groups

5.6.1 Interpreting the annotations on worksheets

In addition to the arrows indicating where DL competencies mapped to multiple IL facets, the groups were also encouraged to annotate their worksheets to illustrate their decision-making processes. While there were only 12 written annotations about the competencies and facets across the five groups, the annotations nevertheless provide additional examples of how the groups interpret the competencies and facets in different ways. Group B, for example, thought beyond the competency “Storing and retrieving information” [EC DigComp] to note that there were additional ethical dimensions to digital information and Data Protection implications. Group C similarly thought that the IL facet “Develop an awareness of copyright and IPR issues” needed “and Data Protection” appended to it. Interestingly, Group D felt that the competencies “Protecting health” [EC DigComp] and “The use of ICT-based devices, applications, software and services” [Jisc] were both “Underlying” competencies rather than supplementary. This approach to defining some competencies as “underlying” was then taken by several other groups.

Other competencies caused groups confusion or did not contain sufficient information or context for groups to confidently map the competence to a facet. “Assess which form(s) of digital media best meets the criteria identified” [SCONUL] was noted as being “Rather vague” by Group B. This group also thought that SCONUL’s “Identify gaps in knowledge relating to digital tools or content” needed additional context, stating, “Define digital tools?”. Group E simply added a “?” to

SCONUL's "Personalise the digital environment according to need". Group C felt that Jisc's "The capacity to find, evaluate, manage, curate, organise and share digital information" was "Very broad", mapping that competence to four different IL facets across three different categories.

5.6.2 Competencies deemed not relevant or supplementary to university lecturers

Every group made use of the "Supplementary" and "Not required" sheets, but to differing degrees (Table 19). The 'supplementary' sheet was used for competencies that were relevant to lecturers but not related to IL concepts. The 'not required' sheet was used for competencies not relevant to university lecturers at all.

A similar picture emerged from the 'supplementary' and 'not required' sheets as occurred with the main worksheets, in that there was very little agreement between groups. The EC DigComp competence, "Protecting the environment" featured in three supplementary sheets, "Protecting health", again from the EC DigComp framework, featured twice, as did the SCONUL competence, "Personalise the digital environment according to need". The other 13 competencies were unique to individual groups.

Some groups annotated the competencies, giving reasons as to why the competencies were deemed to be supplementary or not required. Group A noted that the EC "Programming" and the SCONUL "Personalise the digital environment according to need" required "clarity" and, in the case of personalising the digital environment, the degree of personalisation was not specified, leaving the group uncertain of where to place the competence. SCONUL's "Assess which form(s) of digital media best meets the criteria identified" caused confusion for Group C. They noted that they were unsure what they were assessing the media against, finding the competence "too vague" and "unknown". The same lack of clarity was noted by Group B, who placed the EC competency, "Solving technical problems" between both the 'supplementary' and 'not required' sheets. They noted that this competence was "not in the remit of [a] lecturer", but the degree of technical problem solving was not stated on the competence, leaving them unsure where to place the competence. Should a lecturer have some or basic problem-solving skills (supplementary) or leave this entirely to IT support (not required)? Group D acknowledged that different

lecturer roles may require different competencies, noting that the EC's Programming was "Not required for most people".

Across all groups, 16 competencies were deemed to be relevant to lecturers but not to IL (supplementary) and just three competencies were considered not relevant to lecturers at all. I, on the other hand, deeming no competence to be supplementary, and 27 of the 66 competencies to be irrelevant to lecturers. This could potentially be due to me employing a much narrower interpretation of IL and the IL facets or illustrates a misunderstanding of the university lecturer role.

Group	Supplementary DL competencies [name of framework]	Competencies not required/relevant to university lecturers [name of framework]
A	Personalise the digital environment according to need [SCONUL]	
	Programming [EC]	
	Protecting devices [EC]	
	Protecting health [EC]	
	Protecting the environment [EC]	
	The capacity to participate in, facilitate and build digital networks [Jisc]	
B	Developing content [EC]	Read online information critically, taking into account access restrictions [SCONUL]
	Personalise the digital environment according to need [SCONUL]	Solving technical problems [EC]
	Protecting health [EC]	
	Protecting the environment [EC]	
	Solving technical problems [EC]	
C	Assess which form(s) of digital media best meets the criteria identified [SCONUL]	
D	Assess how online collaboration can enhance academic practice [SCONUL]	Programming [EC]
	Collaborating through digital channels [EC]	
	Communicate effectively in a digital environment, using appropriate tools, to meet audience needs, taking account of accessibility issues [SCONUL]	
	Engage in online collaboration and networking to access and share information [SCONUL]	
	Protecting the environment [EC]	
	The capacity to participate in digital teams and working groups [Jisc]	
	The capacity to support and develop others in digitally-rich settings [Jisc]	
E	The capacity to design and/or create new digital artefacts and materials [Jisc]	

Table 19. Digital competencies deemed Supplementary and Not Required by workshop group

5.7 Internal reliability of workshop exercise and next steps

Adding my own version of the exercise to the combined mapping of all groups shows little agreement between my analysis and the workshop groups (Figure 9 and Table 20) nor any agreement between individual groups. The internal reliability of the exercise is, therefore, very low. The third phase of the research was due to be a survey of lecturers based on a harmonised set of DL competencies obtained in the workshops. Due to the low internal reliability of the exercise, the proposed third phase of the research cannot proceed.

Figure 9. Mapping of the digital competencies to information literacy facets for all groups, combined with my analysis

Number of matches	Number of occurrences across workshop groups	Number of occurrences across workshop groups including my analysis
6	-	1
5	1	3
4	4	9
3	13	17
2	37	69
1	202	234

Table 20. Number of times groups mapped DL competencies to the same IL facet, and combined with my analysis

5.8 Chapter summary

This workshop phase of the research sought to harmonise the digital competencies from the three DL frameworks identified in phase one and distil them through an IL lens. The workshops utilised the inter-professional knowledge and experiences of librarians, learning technologists, and lecturers to explore DL as relevant to university lecturers. The aim was to use the distilled competencies to develop a questionnaire to assess lecturer digital competence with respect to IL. The workshops, however, revealed that different groups interpret and experience DL and IL in different ways, to the degree that there is no agreement between groups as to how DL relates to IL. Workshop groups could also not agree on what digital competencies were relevant to lecturers, but not IL, and what competencies were not relevant to lecturers at all. Furthermore, combining my undertaking of the same task did not lead to significantly more matches, and the competencies I deemed to be irrelevant to lecturers was very different to the interpretations made by workshop groups.

There were no discussions during the workshops nor during the peer debrief that explained the degree of difference between groups. However, the annotations that groups made on the worksheets and competencies provided a glimpse into how they interpreted the wording of the DL competencies and the IL facets. Not only did

groups map competencies to a wide range of IL facets, but they also wrote that some competencies were “rather vague” and required further context and definition. This discovery is similar to LuMarie F. Guth et al.’s (2018, p. 709) finding that lecturers noted a “lack of clarity” in IL terminology. Similarly, the post-exercise discussion and debrief revealed that participants found some frameworks easier to follow than others. Indeed, participants felt that the Jisc framework particularly difficult to interpret because too many concepts were included in each of their competencies. There is, however, a paucity of literature on language and lecturer comprehension of DL and respective frameworks.

This lack of agreement between groups, the absence of clarity in framework concepts, and the differing nature of the annotations on the worksheets is perhaps not surprising. Nichols (2015, p.78) notes that contexts are “located in terms of social and cultural reference points” of individuals. There are, of course, many “levels of context: micro, meso, macro” (p.82) that will affect the situations in which each workshop participant constructs their understanding of information literacy and digital competence. I had, however, hoped that across the multi-disciplinary groups there would have been commonalities in the worksheets. The lack of understanding and different interpretations provided by groups to the semantic meaning of the DL competencies and IL facets offers a potential answer to the lack of agreement between workshop groups and indeed my own analysis. In the next chapter I will propose methods to explain the lack of agreement between workshop groups and uncover how lecturers construct their knowledge of information literacy and digital competence.

6 Deepening our understanding of lecturer construction of information literacy and digital competence

6.1 Introduction to chapter

We have seen from the previous chapter that lecturers, librarians, and learning technologists had different views on which digital competencies were relevant to university lecturers, and that there were considerable differences in how they mapped digital competencies to an information literacy landscape.

6.2 Aims and research questions

In this chapter I aim to explore the reasons why lecturers, librarians, and learning technologists construct information and digital literacy in dissimilar ways. I will, however, focus my attention to the primary population group of interest: university lecturers.

Such was the heterogeneous nature of the results in phase two, I did not expect to be able to definitively answer why the workshop groups mapped the digital competencies to the IL facets in such a disparate manner. Therefore, rather than using this phase of the research to explore the digital competencies and IL facets themselves, I wished to use the competencies and facets to explore the contexts upon which lecturers utilise technology and construct their knowledge of IL and DL. By doing so, I hope that I will bring contextual richness to the findings of phase two, which will then aid my understanding of why the groups mapped the digital competencies to the IL facets the way they did. I will, therefore, seek to explore this aim by asking the following research questions:

- How do university lecturers construct their understanding of information literacy facets and digital competencies?
- Does their understanding reveal why lecturers construct these concepts in such a disparate manner?

The following methods section details how I used in-depth interviews to explore these questions. While the interviews were unable to explain the findings from phase two, they did provide a glimpse into how knowledge of digital competence is constructed in an individualised way. The individual contexts in which this knowledge

is formed may hint at a reason for the heterogeneous findings from workshops. This insight is further explored in the findings, chapter summary, and following discussion.

6.3 Research methods

6.3.1 Replicating the workshop format

The initial idea of this phase of the research was to replicate the workshops but individually with one lecturer at a time in an interview format. I believed that this method would allow me to gain a deeper understanding as to the individual choices that lecturers made when deciding to match a digital competence to the appropriate information literacy facet. This depth of understanding was missing from the workshop phase as I observed two workshop groups in parallel with multiple participants in each group.

To test the feasibility of undertaking an interview using this method and to examine the generated data, a pilot interview was held in August 2018 with a lecturer from University A who had expressed an interest in attending the workshops but could not make the workshop date. As with the workshops, the interview lasted one hour, and as with many of the workshop groups, the interviewee was only able to partly complete the exercise; this was in part due to pausing to respond to questions about the choices the lecturer was making as part of the exercise. Ultimately, the pilot interview felt rushed, and the data generated was not deep enough to gain a rich understanding of how lecturers construct their understanding of information literacy facets and digital competencies. I considered extending the length of interview but was conscious of not wanting to place too much burden on participants nor to make participant recruitment more difficult in an already small sample of experts. As such, an alternative method was required to realise the research aims.

6.3.2 In-depth interviews

In order to fully understand how lecturers construct their knowledge of information and digital literacy, I chose to employ an in-depth interview method.

In-depth interviews will allow me to gain a better understanding of lecturers “lived experiences, values and decisions”, more so than other qualitative methods such as “surveys, informal interviewing, or focus groups” (Johnson and Rowlands, 2012, n.p.).

Interviews are not, however, neutral, where only the perspective of the interviewee are heard. Kvale and Brinkmann (2009, p.2) have termed interviews as “inter-views”, where the interview process and the knowledge generated from the interview are influenced not just by how the interviewee responds to the questions, but through the exchange between both persons involved in the interview. There is, therefore, a methodological alignment in my use of contextual constructionism in how I will both construct the interview schedule and conduct the interviews themselves.

6.3.3 Thematic analysis

The transcripts generated through the in-depth interviews will be analysed using the Braun and Clarke approach to thematic analysis (Braun and Clarke, 2006). Thematic analysis was developed from content analysis, a quantitative method that came into being in the social sciences in the early twentieth century (Robson, 2011). Content analysis was initially applied to media items, starting with newspapers and broadening out to radio, television and advertising. The method is quantitative as the frequency of words are counted and coded according to categories set by the researcher. Critics have argued that by simply accounting for the frequency of words and categories in an item, the context of the item is lost and the coding deprived of all meaning (Joffe, 2012). However, Boyatzis (1998) believes that the encoding of qualitative information and the development of patterns within a wide variety of information types can lead to the interpretation of a phenomenon in a sensitive and systematic manner. This development of a coding structure and the analysis and re-analysis of the data in question (Fereday and Muir-Cochrane, 2006), adds a layer of refinement and intricacy not available through content analysis. This application of tacit meaning is closely aligned to my contextual constructionism philosophical stance. Here, my research questions and my interpretation of the findings occur within my own situated knowledge, that of being a librarian utilising both information and digital literacy frameworks in my daily work. As such, I will be employing the “Big Q” approach to thematic analysis as detailed by Braun and Clarke (2006). The “Big Q” approach “recognizes that the analysis is the result of a researcher with a particular set of skills, training, disciplinary knowledge, biography and socio-demographic positioning actively engaging with their data” (Clarke and Braun, 2016, p.86). The inductive approach to thematic analysis can often lead to themes that are tangential to the interview questions asked to participants, there is no coding

framework employed and the themes generated from the data are derived solely from the responses given by participants (Braun and Clarke, 2006). As discussed though, I will bring my own interpretation to the data, through the lens of my own situated knowledge.

Braun and Clarke (2006) have a 15-point checklist of criteria for good thematic analysis. The practical methods I have employed to ensure that my analysis is valid and in line with the Braun and Clarke approach can be seen in [Appendix 8](#) and further detailed below.

6.3.3.1 Thematic analysis coding and theme generation

By designing the interview schedule, conducting the interviews, and editing Zoom's automated transcripts myself, I was immersed in the data from an early stage. My inductive approach also involved transcribing the interviews faithfully, including pauses and "erms" and "ahs". A good example of this is Evelyn's response to an IL facet, "*[Long pause] Yeah, it does. I'm just trying to formulate, erm, in my own words... what I think it means...*".

I employed a 'dual-coding' approach whereby I generated codes from each participant, then across each transcript, generating and editing codes by question e.g., question 1 by participant A, question 1 by participant B, etc. question 2 by participant A, question 2 by participant B, etc. I was careful to avoid generating codes from a few examples by developing a series of codes, then sub-themes, and then developing these into the main themes. This process was developed across three major versions of my coding. As an example, the theme "Lecturers require guidance and support to increase their digital competence and technology utilisation" was generated across all eight interviews with 55 coding references across the participants.

The screenshot shows a window titled 'Lecturers require guidance and support to increase their digital competence and technology utilisation'. Below the title is a table with the following data:

Name	In Folder	References	Coverage
Amal_transcript	Files\\Interviews	2	0.94%
Ashley_transcript	Files\\Interviews	11	10.46%
Efe_transcript	Files\\Interviews	9	8.55%
Evelyn_transcript	Files\\Interviews	3	0.84%
Jamie_transcript	Files\\Interviews	11	11.03%
Jude_transcript	Files\\Interviews	6	8.02%
Masami_transcript	Files\\Interviews	6	6.42%
Sam_transcript	Files\\Interviews	7	7.63%

Figure 10: A screenshot from NVivo showing how the theme 'Lecturers require guidance and support to increase their digital competence and technology utilisation' is coded across the interview transcript files.

My coding process allowed themes and sub-themes to be cross-referenced against each other. Some sub-themes were combined when checking back to the original dataset. The benefit of using NVivo 12 software for this process was that all relevant extracts generated for each were collated under my coding structure.

As you will see in the next findings section and detailed above, my methodological stance reinforces the central position of my analysis of the data, rather than the data being paraphrased or described. As such, the interview data analysis provides a collation of genuine responses by participants that represent the themes I generated. Therefore, the extracts chosen provided a good illustration of the wider theme to which they were coded. As an example, Efe's contribution of, "*I think what do I really want to communicate and how do I want to communicate it, and then that would dictate what type of device that is going to be suitable*" is a good illustration of how a quotation matches the theme, "Pedagogy and ILOs are the central construct from which digital technology is adopted and digital competence formed".

Overall, my thematic analysis, from start to finish took six months to complete, enough time to adequately complete all phases of the analysis in a rigorous manner. As previously noted, a full response to Braun and Clarke's (2006) "15-point checklist of criteria for good thematic analysis" can be found in [Appendix 8](#).

6.3.4 Distilling the workshop phase to an interview format

In order to explore how lecturers construct their understanding of information literacy facets and digital competencies, a method was required that would distil the facets

and competencies to a number that would not produce excessive burden on lecturers; it would simply not be possible to sufficiently discuss each of the 24 facets and 66 competencies at an interview. Equally, there would also not be time within the context of a Professional Doctorate to then analyse the interview outputs. As such, a method was required to distil the workshop phase to a rigorous interview format that would produce a valid exploration of the research questions.

Four possible methods to determine which competencies and facets would be presented to lecturers in the interviews and in what order were considered. These methods are presented below with their strengths and limitations discussed.

6.3.4.1 Quantitative method

This method proposed that the digital competencies would be ranked according to how closely they were correlated in the workshops. A competency consistently matched to one facet would be presented first, with a competency that workshop groups matched to several disparate facets would be presented last. Where competences were matched to the same number of facets, their dispersal across the facets would be used to determine the order. As an example, the information literacy framework has seven groups containing 17 facets. One group is 'Managing Information', which contains three information literacy facets. The SCONUL digital competency 'Access, read and download digital information and data' was matched by three workshop groups to three different facets within this group (Figure 10). This digital competency is, therefore, ranked higher than the SCONUL digital competency 'Recognise the importance of skills in locating, creating managing and sharing information through a variety of digital forms', which was matched to four different facets across four information literacy groups.

SCONUL	Access, read and download digital information and data
	Recognise the importance of skills in locating, creating managing and sharing information through a variety of digital forms
	Underpinning competencies
	Working in a scholarly environment
	Evaluate the information landscape
	Assess your current information-seeking behaviour
	Mapping and evaluating the information landscape
	Critically evaluate source material
	Identify the key experts in your field
	Resource discovery in your discipline
	Identify key finding aids in your discipline
	Develop resource discovery search strategies and techniques
	Identify subject-specific collections of information
	Identify the types of specialist information common in your discipline
	Managing information
	Develop information management techniques
	Utilise reference management tools
	Develop appropriate strategies for current awareness
	Ethical dimension of information
	Develop an awareness of copyright and IPR issues
	Compare dissemination practices in your discipline
	Presenting and communicating knowledge
	Identify publication methods within your discipline
	Identify publication sources within your discipline
	Social dimension of information
	Actionable knowledge in the workplace and daily life
	Information handling, problem solving and decision making in the workplace
	Supplementary
	Not required

Figure 11. An illustration of how the digital competencies ‘Access, read and download digital information and data’ and ‘Recognise the importance of skills in locating, creating managing and sharing information through a variety of digital forms’ are spread across the information literacy group, ‘Managing information’.

The strength of this method would be an impartial order of competencies, as determined by the workshop phase of the research. However, in practice, the scoring of the competencies meant that some frameworks were more highly scored than others, an interesting finding in itself. Using this correlation scoring method, the first ten competencies presented to lecturers would be five from SCONUL, one from Jisc, and four from the EC framework. These ten competencies were matched to four (of seven) information literacy facet groups. There is, therefore, a limitation that the interviews would only discuss lecturer construction of competencies in relation to one or two frameworks and a small proportion of the overall information literacy facets. Whilst this will always be the case with a limited time to interview participants, there is a danger that the findings of the interviews would be strictly limited to very few competencies and facets, and that practical recommendations could not be made to people creating and utilising the information and digital literacy frameworks. The heterogenous nature of the data meant that further ranking of the competencies and facets to ensure an even distribution across the frameworks and information literacy groups would render the ranking meaningless; there was simply too much difference in distribution to form an appropriate prioritisation of digital competencies. This would render the order open to questions of reliability. What if another workshop group was convened? There were such small differences between the scores that the ranking of the competencies could dramatically change.

6.3.4.2 Allow lecturers decide on the order

Lecturers who volunteered to participate in the interviews would be given the full list of competencies and information literacy facets and asked to select 15 competencies or facets that most resonated with their professional practice. Fifteen competencies or facets would allow for sufficient discussion of each within a one-hour interview. This method would remove the bias of the researcher and any perceived limitations of the workshops, and the data generated from the workshops. A clear finding on lecturer preference would be apparent if multiple lecturers chose the same competencies or facets, or those from the same framework. This finding would have implications for practice and the interview would only serve to discover more about how lecturers construct their understanding of digital competencies. However, given the nature of the workshop findings, I was in doubt as to whether this would occur

over the course of ten interviews; a relatively small sample, with a large number of possible choices. Lecturers may also choose different competencies and facets for different professional purposes, lecturing or research, for example. Asking lecturers to select only 15 competencies or facets from a potential sample of 66 may prove superficial, and questions over the representativeness of the lecturer sample could be questioned. Additionally, if a similar level of heterogeneity were to occur in the lecturer choices as in the workshops data, thematic analysis of the interview data could prove problematic with a lack of similar themes across a limited number of interviews.

6.3.4.3 Purposive sampling

A purposive sample of competencies and facets would allow for a balance between the quantitative data derived from the workshops with a practical consideration of balance across the frameworks against the aims of the research. A reflective exercise would allow competencies to be selected that would more likely result in agreement between lecturers on how they construct digital competencies. Those competencies with clearer definitions could be triangulated against workshop data to achieve a balance across the frameworks. However, without sufficient literature to construct an impartial decision-making process, nor clear data from the workshops, this method would become highly biased to the researcher's opinions on the frameworks and, therefore, influence the outcome of the interviews.

6.3.4.4 Random stratified sampling

A random stratified sample would be taken from all information literacy facets and digital competencies. Five information literacy facets and ten digital competencies would be chosen to be discussed at the interviews. This method would reduce potential bias and assures that all interviewees will be discussing the same facets and competencies; this may make themes more easily identifiable.

6.3.5 Facets and competencies to be discussed at interview

On balance, between minimising bias, producing a rigorous method, and not overburdening participants, versus the time and resources available within the context of a Professional Doctorate, I decided to pursue the random stratified sampling method.

The 24 information literacy facets were numbered according to the order presented in the workshop handouts and the 66 digital competencies were then organised from those the workshop groups most closely correlated in the workshop analysis to the least correlated (Table 21).

	Information literacy facet	Digital competence
1	Working in a scholarly environment	Identify appropriate online search techniques
2	Evaluate the information landscape	The capacity to find, evaluate, manage, curate, organise and share digital information.
3	Assess your current information-seeking behaviour	Engaging in online citizenship
4	Mapping and evaluating the information landscape	Manage digital resources effectively taking account of version control, file storage and record keeping issues
5	Critically evaluate source material	The capacity to develop and project a positive digital identity or identities and to manage digital reputation
6	Identify the key experts in your field	Protecting the environment
7	Resource discovery in your discipline	Stay safe and, if necessary, private in the digital world
8	Identify key finding aids in your discipline	The capacity to collate, manage, access and use digital data
9	Develop resource discovery search strategies and techniques	Storing and retrieving information
10	Identify subject-specific collections of information	Select appropriate publication and dissemination outlets to share information
11	Identify the types of specialist information common in your discipline	The capacity to look after personal health, safety, relationships and work-life balance in digital settings
12	Managing information	Browsing, searching and filtering information
13	Develop information management techniques	Use appropriate tools to organise digital content and data (social bookmarking, bibliographic software)
14	Utilise reference management tools	The use of ICT-based devices, applications, software and services.
15	Develop appropriate strategies for current awareness	Identifying needs and technological responses
16	Ethical dimension of information	Use different online communication approaches to extend reach
17	Develop an awareness of copyright and IPR issues	The capacity to communicate effectively in digital media and spaces

18	Compare dissemination practices in your discipline	Identifying digital competence gaps
19	Presenting and communicating knowledge	Develop an online personal profile using appropriate networks and technologies
20	Identify publication methods within your discipline	The capacity to design and-or create new digital artefacts and materials
21	Identify publication sources within your discipline	Evaluating Information
22	Social dimension of information	Assign meta-data tags to content to enable future discoverability
23	Actionable knowledge in the workplace and daily life	The capacity to critically receive and respond to messages in a range of digital media
24	Information handling, problem solving and decision making in the workplace	Sharing information and content
25		Assess the quality, accuracy, relevance, credibility, format and accessibility of digital material
26		The capacity to participate in, facilitate and build digital networks
27		Developing content
28		Read online information critically, taking into account access restrictions
29		The capacity to support and develop others in digitally-rich settings
30		Managing digital identity
31		Confidently use the digital media appropriate for presentation
32		The capacity to participate in and benefit from digital learning opportunities
33		Netiquette
34		Use new tools and technologies as they become available and evaluate them for suitability
35		The capacity to use digital evidence to solve problems and answer questions
36		Protecting devices
37		Assess different digital formats and select those to meet current need
38		The capacity to participate in digital teams and working groups
39		Collaborating through digital channels

40	Recognise where digital solutions can meet a specific information task or need
41	The capacity to adopt and develop new practices with digital technology
42	Copyright and Licences
43	Identify search tools for locating quality digital material
44	The use of ICT-based tools to carry out tasks effectively, productively, and with attention to quality.
45	Protecting personal data
46	Maximise discoverability of own digital material using indexing strategies
47	Protecting health
48	Remotely access external digital sources in order to extend opportunities for discovery
49	Interacting through technologies
50	Identify gaps relating to the use, application or development of digital environments and tools
51	Solving technical problems
52	Continuously assess how the use of digital content and tools could enhance academic practice
53	Innovating and creatively using technology
54	Cite and reference electronic sources appropriately
55	Programming
56	Personalise the digital environment according to need
57	Integrating and re-elaborating
58	Assess how online collaboration can enhance academic practice
59	Assess which form(s) of digital media best meets the criteria identified
60	Use a range of digital retrieval tools and technology effectively
61	Access, read and download digital information and data
62	Communicate effectively in a digital environment, using appropriate tools, to meet audience needs, taking account of accessibility issues
63	Identify gaps in knowledge relating to digital tools or content
64	Recognise the importance of skills in locating, creating managing and sharing information through a variety of digital forms

65	Engage in online collaboration and networking to access and share information
66	Assess the suitability of digital content for the intended audience

Table 21. Order of information literacy facets and digital competencies for sampling

To balance discussion in the interviews between the information literacy facets and the digital competencies, I decided to select five facets and ten competencies that would form the interview schedule. The Google random number generator tool (Google, 2018) was used to generate five numbers from 1-24 and the corresponding information literacy facet was then selected for the interview schedule. The exercise was repeated, with random numbers between 1-66, with the corresponding digital competence selected.

The five information literacy facets chosen, in the order generated, were:

1. Identify the key experts in your field,
2. Develop an awareness of copyright and IPR issues,
3. Critically evaluate source material,
4. Actionable knowledge in the workplace and daily life, and
5. Identify publication sources within your discipline.

The ten digital competences chosen and their frameworks, in the order generated, were:

1. Assess which form(s) of digital media best meets the criteria identified (SCONUL),
2. Recognise where digital solutions can meet a specific information task or need (SCONUL),
3. Read online information critically, taking into account access restrictions (SCONUL),
4. Interacting through technologies (EU DigComp),
5. Assess how online collaboration can enhance academic practice (SCONUL),
6. Identify appropriate online search techniques (SCONUL),
7. Identify gaps in knowledge relating to digital tools or content (SCONUL),
8. The capacity to adopt and develop new practices with digital technology (Jisc),

9. The capacity to develop and project a positive digital identity or identities and to manage digital reputation (Jisc), and
10. Managing digital identity (EU DigComp).

The number of competencies per digital literacy framework are as follows: SCONUL = 6, EU DigComp = 2, and Jisc = 2.

The distribution of digital competencies across the three frameworks was not a surprise given that SCONUL has the largest number of competencies in the framework when compared with the EU DigComp and Jisc frameworks (30, 20, and 15, respectively). Proportionally, of the ten competencies, one would expect to see 4.6 SCONUL competencies, 3.1 EU DigComp competencies, and 2.3 Jisc competencies.

6.3.6 Interview schedule

The interview schedule consisted of lecturers being asked to read the facet or competence text, as copied directly from the corresponding framework, including any emphasis on the text, for example, bold text. Lecturers were then asked to reflect on their understanding of the text and relate the facet or competence to their work as a lecturer. The pilot interview indicated that an interview lasting one hour should be sufficient to discuss the 15 items on the schedule in enough depth, without putting a time burden on the lecturer participants.

Introductory slides were added to re-introduce myself to the participants and to restate pertinent ethical considerations. The ethical considerations were there to remind participants that they were free to withdraw without any negative consequences, were free to decline to answer any questions, and to restate my position as a neutral researcher, should our paths have crossed as part of my professional role. When the lecturer re-confirmed that they were happy to proceed, the recording started. The slides used for the interview schedule can be found at <https://dx.doi.org/10.5255/UKDA-SN-855937>.

6.3.7 Lecturer sampling

As I was looking for lecturers with a developed understanding of digital competence and those who have experience of utilising technology in the curricula, the same purposive sampling method employed for the workshops was utilised (described in 5.3.3). Additional searches of the institution research repositories were made in June

2020 and respective learning and teaching conference programmes, and this led to a further nine potential participants from University B and a further three from University A. When combined with lecturers from the workshop phase who expressed an interest in participating, but could not make the workshop dates, this made a sample of potential participants of 13 from University B and 4 from University A.

Potential participants were emailed in early June 2020; the recruitment email can be found in [Appendix 9](#). There were two responses from lecturers at University B and three responses from lecturers at University A. The five responses were short of the ten lecturers I had initially hoped to recruit to enhance the validity of the findings. As a result of the small sample and low response rate, a gatekeeper on a digital learning project at University A offered to recruit lecturers on the project on my behalf. An email was sent from the gatekeeper to six lecturers on the project introducing me and the research toward the end of June. A further three participants were recruited from this group.

In total, eight participants were recruited for interviews that commenced on 22 June 2020 and ran until 4 August 2020.

The participant pseudonyms and disciplinary breakdown can be seen in Table 22.

Pseudonym	Discipline
Amal	Social sciences
Ashley	Social sciences
Efe	Arts and humanities
Evelyn	Clinical, pre-clinical and health
Jamie	Psychology
Jude	Computer science
Masami	Social sciences
Sam	Education

Table 22. Interview participants and disciplines

6.3.8 Internal and external validity of the sample and data collection methods

Due to various restrictions at the time of the COVID-19 pandemic, the interviews were conducted via the video conferencing software Zoom (Zoom Video Communications, Inc.). Zoom provided a platform that participants were familiar with

and one that offered benefits to me as a researcher; namely the ability to easily share the slides that acted as the interview schedule and a full transcript of the interview for later editing. At the time of the interviews, Zoom, accessed via a university account, also provided GDPR-compliant cloud hosting of the recordings and transcripts. The capability of Zoom to provide these features saved me having to rely on recording devices and manually transcribe the notes.

One matter of consideration is that, given the interviews took place during the COVID-19 pandemic, with the sudden switch to online-only teaching with university campuses closed, this may have influenced how lecturers framed their responses to my questions. I reflect further on this effect in the chapter summary.

As with the workshop phase, NVivo 12 was used to analyse interview transcripts. An additional benefit in using NVivo 12 for the interviews was that the detailed coding allowed the data to be checked for referential adequacy where it can “later be examined at leisure and compared to the critiques that had been developed from all the data collected” (Lincoln and Guba, 1985, p. 313).

The full interview transcripts, complete with my coding and coding structure can be found at <https://dx.doi.org/10.5255/UKDA-SN-855937>.

6.3.9 Ethical considerations

The change of format from the workshop to interviews required an amendment to my original ethics application. The amendment noted the change of research method, from workshop to interviews, and a new consent form ([Appendix 10](#)) and participant information sheet ([Appendix 11](#)). The participant information sheet introduced the new methods, as detailed above, whilst the consent form additionally asked for consent to record the interview and for the “permission for anonymised data to be shared on an openly available data repository, including a transcript of the recording”.

The interview arrangements were negotiated with the participants to ensure they were not inconvenienced by the research process. At the beginning of each interview, I restated the principles detailed in the consent form, as detailed in the slides (available at <https://dx.doi.org/10.5255/UKDA-SN-855937>), including the right to withdraw without detriment, and asked the participants to re-state their consent before proceeding to record the interview and proceed with the schedule.

6.3.10 Presentation of interview transcripts

I have been faithful to the manner and expressions of lecturers in the presentation of quotations in these findings; these include false starts, pauses and hesitations. One of the more interesting findings was how lecturers responded to the text used to describe the various information literacy facets and digital competencies. Some lecturers took lengthy pauses before contextualising their knowledge of some concepts and wording, whilst others seemed more confident in both their understanding of the text and relating the facet or competence to their work. A detailed discussion of this finding can be found in the following section. As a result of this finding, the quotations are presented as exactly as transcribed; the transcription of which is as faithful as possible to the manner in which the interviewee responded to the questions. The full interview transcripts can be found at <https://dx.doi.org/10.5255/UKDA-SN-855937>.

6.4 Introduction to the findings

The previous section discussed how I intend to use interviews to deepen our understanding of how lecturers construct their knowledge of information and digital literacy and, in doing so, find whether this helps explain the heterogenous results seen in the workshop phase of the research. This section will discuss the results of a thematic analysis of the interview transcripts, starting with an overarching theme, before discussing the other themes I constructed from the interviews.

6.5 Lecturer construction of digital competence is still at an embryonic stage

The overarching theme from the interviews is that lecturer construction of digital competence is still at an early stage. This is not to say that lecturers are not digitally competent, but that the manner in which they construct their knowledge and practices is, at times, disconnected from the practices and behaviours that the frameworks would lead us to believe a digitally competent person should possess. The reasons for this are complex and centre around several factors: how lecturers form their understanding of digital competence is entwined in their pedagogies and disciplinary background, how lecturers use and are supported to use technology, how the university environment shapes their digital practices, and the frameworks themselves.

The majority (7/8) of the lecturers interviewed for this study struggled with the language of digital competence and the competencies and facets described in the frameworks. Many of the lecturers had to pause to understand the information literacy facet or digital competence. Whilst pausing to read and comprehend text, especially in an interview format, is not uncommon (Wellard and McKenna, 2001), the length of pause for some lecturers hinted at a lack of comprehension or confusion, “*Sorry, I'm just thinking... I mean, I don't know.*” (Amal), or in some cases a feeling that what they were reading was not relevant to them or their level of seniority, “*I think, if I was just straight in the door in my first teaching post, I think that would be probably quite low down on my list of priorities.*” (Jamie). With the exception of a few cases where lecturers verbalised being confused by what the competence or facet text meant, what wasn't clear from the pauses or delayed replies to a question was whether that was due to their competence or comprehension, or whether the language in the framework was the cause of confusion, “*I suppose I don't kind of distinguish, as I said, I don't know if digital media means just anything digital kind of thing, or is it something specific to, like, media, you know?*” (Masami). The use of Plain English and clarity of concepts in the frameworks is a theme I shall return to at a later stage of the analysis.

What is clear, is that student expectations of learning are driving lecturers to experiment with digital technologies (Shelton, 2014), with lecturers increasingly looking to the student body to develop their teaching methods.

I would look to the learner again... I would be trying a variety of different approaches, trying new approaches as I can, try different ways of delivering, having a multi-varied [offer], and then allow the students to come back and tell you what works for them and be prepared to accept the fact that different students have/like different things. (Efe)

6.6 The reasons for gaps in lecturer digital competence is many and varied

With lecturers focused on the student learning experience and student digital competence, many neglect their own personal developmental, with lecturers learning by doing, rather than a strategically planning their learning.

Probably we always think about our digital competencies for students and what we are trying to get students to do and we don't often reflect it on ourself. (Jamie)

Yeah, I think, I think this is just crucial actually. It is to a) know that you've got gaps and that's maybe a bit that's a problem probably because you don't know until you start to think about how am I to use this tool. (Ashley)

As Ashley alludes to, a lack of strategic professional development can, in part, be due to lecturers not knowing about gaps in their knowledge until the gap needs to be filled. As Sam notes, *"I know I have gaps in my knowledge, but I don't know how to identify them... I don't know what I don't know, relating to digital tools and content."* All lectures reflected on gaps in their knowledge, prompted by reading the EC digital competence 'Identifying digital competence gaps' (Ferrari, 2013, p.6). The reasons lecturers identified for gaps in their knowledge ranged from the "vastness" of digital tools and technologies, tools lacking context to their lecturer role (Evelyn), to not growing up with digital technology (Amal), time constraints for personal development, and lecturers being assumed to be digitally competent (Jamie), and self-identified competency gaps being too large or daunting to fill (Sam), this final issue links to the issue of digital confidence seen in rapid literature review (Alvarez, 2013; Bennett, 2014; Duta, 2014).

Jamie's feeling that digital competence is assumed of lecturers, *"It's kind of assumed that if you come out with a kind of, PhD, you've got the skills. And I'm not necessarily sure we do if I'm honest!"* and Sam's reflection that some gaps in competence are too big and daunting to fill may be interlinked. Sam is hesitant to ask for advice for fear of asking a "stupid question". This hesitancy, and perhaps a lack of confidence, leaves competence gaps unfilled, in turn exacerbating this feeling of inadequacy (Greener and Wakefield, 2015). When reflecting on the advanced use of technology in the medical faculty, Sam expresses that inadequacy in what I sensed was a feeling of helplessness, of being so far from that level of skill, *"...I don't think I could do that. So I can't give you any examples of how I would do that in my work, because I just don't think I can."*

Ashely's reflection that competence gaps are exposed when they start to use a new digital tool is similar to Masami's learning-by-doing approach to skills development,

"I'm going to have to become better simply because we have to do everything online"; a particular reference to the switch to online-only learning as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic. However, Masami feels that their approach to identifying and filling competence gaps through experimentation with technology is not universally shared by their peers.

But I suppose what I'm thinking, the other way of thinking about this question as well is, are you happy or, like, erm, confident enough or willing enough to try things and, you know, this idea to develop things. Because I know so many people who just say "no I'm not touching that because it's digital" and it's like, well okay! And where do you see your life going from here, you know?! (Masami)

So that goes back to when people are teaching stuff and if they're not, like, "No, I'm not, I'm not doing anything. I'm just doing lectures and that's it. And I'm not putting anything online and I'm not doing that", you know, like that kind of just stubbornness of not accepting change is not really with the times anymore. So yeah, that kind of, yeah. But then also now with this whole moving online and all that moving teaching online, it's become so much clearer that not everyone still, even today, have the same kind of digital not capabilities but just the capacity. (Masami)

While the reasons for lecturers not wanting to engage with digital technology are many and varied, the reasons for the gaps in digital competence made by all participants will influence engagement and uptake of technology. Lecturers may well feel reticent to engage with technology through a lack of digital confidence (Sam), being a digital immigrant (Amal), not having the time to develop competence or confidence with technology (Jamie), having unidentified competence gaps (Ashley) or having a feeling that there are too many technologies available (Evelyn). Ashley offers a contrast to Masami highlighting peers that fail to engage with technology by noting that digital competence is gained slowly and incrementally, [when producing digital lecture content] *"People know that they need to be in a space where light is good, audio is good. They're using headphones if they don't have good audio on the computer, whatever. So you're, you're almost by, you know, I guess through stealth come to a point where people recognise those things."* Perhaps Masami's

contribution was in direct response to the challenges faced by lecturers switching learning online in the face of the COVID-19 crisis and the suddenness of this happening, which often left lecturers feeling overwhelmed (Dinu *et al.*, 2021). What remains to be seen is whether the gaps lecturers identified at the start of the pandemic remain in subsequent years or whether new gaps emerge as a result of the incremental learning-by-doing and by learning through “*stealth*” that Masami and Ashley identified.

6.7 Pedagogy and ILOs are the central construct from which digital technology is adopted and digital competence formed

Where lecturers are using digital technology, pedagogy and intended learning outcomes (ILOs) for students are the driver for use and define how lecturers construct their digital competence.

Many of the responses in this theme came from the SCONUL digital competence to “Recognise where digital solutions can meet a specific information task or need” (SCONUL, 2016, n.p.), with Jude acknowledging that the chosen digital solution is “*very much depending on the learning outcome*” or where the “*learning outcomes will be at the centre of that*” (Efe). For Jamie, a lot of what lectures do is “*implicitly driven. I think we know what we want students to get, and when you're asking me that question, I'm thinking we maybe specify that in terms of learning outcomes*”. Efe continues that:

“I don't think the device is the way to think about it from the start, I think, it is to think about the actual mode of communication that you're going to use, which is comes to the end... I think what do I really want to communicate and how do I want to communicate it, and then that would dictate what type of device that is going to be suitable” (Efe)

Similarly for Masami, when describing moving their teaching online during the COVID-19 pandemic, “*I'm having to think about which digital media best meets the criteria, the criteria being meeting the ILO and also the course*”. For Masami, even in a period of rapid change and high stress, ILOs still dictate how the course is delivered and assessed, rather than these decisions being technology-led; perhaps an easier and forgivable option given the circumstances at the time.

Efe, Jude, Jamie and Masami's approaches typify an approach to teaching using technology that has the ILO at the heart of learning. Ashley, too, exemplifies the learning first, technology second mindset. However, there is an acknowledgment with Ashley that their familiarity with certain technologies may influence how the ILO is framed.

“So it's that adaptability, that I think we need to get to. How people identify those, I would do that through: Well, what am I trying to achieve? What do I want to try to achieve? What might be the various tools I might use? Do I know how to use that one? Do I know how to edit? Do I know it, because otherwise it's going to take me hours longer than it probably needs to and it may not produce the quality of output that I want.” (Ashley)

Ashley's reflection hints that ILOs may be changed, perhaps just subtly, if a lecturer's digital competence does not allow them to perform a particular task. For Efe, building learning outcomes around “*higher order capacities*” allows the freedom to “*change and shift*”; this approach exemplifying Efe's commitment to co-design of the curricula with their students, building in flexibility to adapt assessment and technology in response to student input. Efe's approach is highly adaptable, with Ashley also using the word “*adaptability*”. The questions Ashley poses when considering potential technologies and Efe's mindset illustrates that being digitally competent requires lecturers to be knowledgeable about a range of technologies and confident enough to adopt that range of technologies or to quickly learn how to use a chosen digital tool.

However, one must also reflect on whether the same considerations that Ashley made when choosing technologies were made in a similar manner before the 'technology revolution'. Indeed, for Amal, digital technology may not always be the answer nor a student's preferred choice:

“I think if it's true that students would rather have a paper book in the hand, a textbook, rather than having particularly complicated website to get to a really badly readable PDF version of the book or something, then I do believe that paper, a book paper is a good technology. And I think maybe that's better than simplicity.” (Amal)

Furthermore, Efe's flexible approach to ILOs allows Efe to adjust where digital technology fits within "*the negotiation – and it wouldn't always fit.*" This approach allows Efe to adjust the teaching offer to blended learning as appropriate or desired by their students.

Where technology is adopted in teaching and learning, the change to digital can be subtly introduced over time. Ashley describes asking students to discuss a topical issue in class. In the past, newspapers were the foci, whereas now, students are prompted to use and engage with discussions on Twitter (a microblogging and social network):

"I would make a judgment on what I was trying to achieve and whether that [Twitter] may be an easy and quick way to get students to be reading about the things I want them to read about." (Ashley)

Ashley's description of using Twitter for a task previously undertaken using print newspapers is a good example of how an ILO may not change or change subtly overtime, using new forms of technology or media that better fulfils the task or reflects changes in student expectations. Indeed, Amal considers that technology can "*fix... more traditional ways of teaching and learning*" where even before the COVID-19 pandemic learning environments were changing "*where students can no longer or do not want to be on campus – remote learning, I guess, in the current situation [during COVID-19 lockdown measures]*".

Interestingly, Efe poses a perhaps sceptical reflection on adoption of technology by their peers, noting a loss of the ILO at the heart of adoption:

"And for me, what's really important there, is that sometimes, sometimes – I don't know how you'll feel about this – sometimes digital learning or advances in new pedagogy to do with online learning, digital learning, digital platforms gets hijacked by some educators who are using it to further, perhaps, their own career rather than actually facilitate a positive learning outcome. So I would say that you need an open mind, you need to be able to learn, you should learn, your students should be bringing you new solutions that you then adopt, learning, and build into practice." (Efe)

The sentiment expressed by Efe may not resonate with other lecturers, and the comment was alone in my transcript coding, but Efe does highlight that critical appraisal of technology is useful to the development of lecturer digital competence. By keeping an open mind, one can appropriately judge digital technologies to meet an ILO and be open to suggestions from students to enhance the curricula and their experience.

6.8 The university digital environment determines whether technology adoption will be successful

While Efe may display some scepticism of the manner in which digital technology is embedded in practice by their peers, the majority of lecturers interviewed indicate cynicism of the way the university digital environment is formed. These attitudes vary from standardised technologies that are not applicable to ILOs (Amal and Jude), to risk adverse (Ashley) and cumbersome technology (Amal) that lecturers struggle to use (Masami), to imposing technology on lecturers (Efe) and often at short notice (Evelyn).

The use of standard technology, such as a VLE will not be uncommon to lecturers, indeed, such systems are central to the delivery of the digital education environment. Where these systems and associated digital technology frustrate lecturers is how they are expected to use the technologies and how this use can differ from a lecturers intended method of delivering their modules and programmes. Amal, for example, describes a “drive” to have the VLE “conform to a certain standard”, mentioning a now defunct medal system where “*the more gizmos you have the better the medal was*”. While Amal admits that this turn of phrase is an oversimplification of what the university was trying to achieve, Amal remained “*not quite sure whether a student would want all that kind of stuff*”. Amal felt that their simple approach was “*hard to get away with*”, showing particular disdain for those who set standards contrary to their pedagogical approach:

“The appreciation of simplicity is underdeveloped within those that do not teach but have the power to devise rules for those who do teach” (Amal)

Jude’s opinions of the VLE are not too dissimilar to Amal’s, with Jude believing that “*they’re not teaching tools, they’re not learning tools... the learning doesn’t happen in there. The learning happens with students however they choose to approach that*

material.” The final sentence links Amal and Jude’s reflections, their belief that no matter how many “gizmos” one employs, the teaching content drives learning, not the technology itself. Jude continues, “*I think, as a society, we are getting caught up so much on the innovation that we’re forgetting that all this innovation is to help [us] move on. It’s not the point by itself.*”

While Amal and Jude focussed on how universities tend to dictate how technologies are used, Efe and Evelyn concentrated on how technology can be imposed upon lecturers. As we have heard, Efe felt that that some lecturers can dictate the technologies universities adopt, but also extends this argument to departments, too. These departments find digital solutions that they favour or “*are perhaps in vogue and then impose those. And I would say that’s the wrong way to do it. You should find solutions that emerge organically from your learning environment and apply those*”. The counter argument might be that organic growth takes time and may lack the structure and uniformity that centralised university departments prefer. The feeling that technology is being imposed on lecturers resonates with Evelyn whose university is implementing new technology, seemingly with short notice and a lack of clear guidance.

“We’ve got a new system coming into play that has almost come out of the blue. We’ve been told to put things on to Moodle, we’ve been told to take training [in the new technology], which a lot of people have, and now we’ve been told that [new technology] isn’t coming along and we’re using another thing called [struggles for name of another new technology]. And I think it’s caused a huge amount of confusion, particularly for me as well! And I was quite, I was quite comforted to know that people who have been in the job a lot longer than I have are also extremely confused about what’s happening... Yeah, so I guess if I’m still doing all my content with the thought that this is all going to go on to Moodle but we’ve been told that Moodle was not going to be there any longer and there are certain things... that is not compatible with the new system. So, that’s all causing a huge amount of concern for people.” (Evelyn)

There is a lot to unpick from Evelyn’s contribution. The implementation of a new VLE is a significant change for a university and VLE users, lecturers included. That

Evelyn feels that the technology is being imposed, without adequate consultation or time to prepare would naturally be anxiety inducing. I feel that there is also a link to the earlier theme of a concern about the potential misalignment of the new technology with Evelyn's pedagogical stance. I also sense a hint of self-doubt in Evelyn's digital competence, that there is not enough time to learn by doing, or as Evelyn said, that there are too many technologies available; this from a lecturer sample chosen for their experience of using digital technology or knowledge of digital literacy concepts.

Jude's reflection that learning does not happen in the VLE and the imposition of technology upon lecturers may also be down to usability of technology. Amal finds the platforms that their university pays for "*quite cumbersome*", and that other platforms or ways of working are a "*bit simpler*". Amal seemed to suggest in the answer that if a simpler option existed, even one that was less well aligned to the concept that they were trying to teach, the simpler option would be taken. This view is supported by Masami who openly admits to using platforms that their university prohibits, simply because they are simpler than the university versions, "*somehow I'm just always struggling with those kind of things*". These two reflections precisely encompass the appropriateness of technology to the purpose, similar to earlier pedagogical theme, but also comprehension of individual digital competencies as a concept.

Describing a bespoke website created for a research project, Ashley, makes specific reference to understanding digital literacies and being able to apply these appropriately to a given situation.

"That's the whole point of literacies for me in digital context is that you supposedly call them what you like, you need to write them out, understand what they are and you then need to make a decision about what you're going to do and why and how you're going to make sure that you, you, kind of protect, if you feel there's risks, or you put things in place to ensure that." (Ashley)

Ashley felt that the regulations imposed by the "*university and institutional setting*", while appropriate from a legal position, were just "*way over the top in the sense of what we were trying to achieve*". Ashley's project was not centrally provided

software, but the same risk adverse pervasive thinking resonates with Amal’s overburdened and cumbersome technology that Masami struggles to use. Ashley continues:

“...[it] requires that little bit of bit more, I guess, digital literacy that’s been developed through a kind of an embedded engagement with debates that are happening in that space to work out which may be an appropriate, appropriate tool or platform to use.” (Ashley)

6.9 Lecturers require guidance and support to increase their digital competence and technology utilisation

Ashley’s remark that lecturers need to understand the digital landscape resonates with Amal who notes that one must know what potential tools are available first, before one can assess whether it is useful for the intended purpose, and then how to use it in practice. All eight lecturers made similar comments about the “*burgeoning*” (Sam) range of digital tools available to them although, interestingly, these reflections were made in response to a wide range of digital competencies (Table 23); this may link back to the workshop finding where the groups differed in how they matched digital competencies to the various information literacy facets.

Framework publisher	Digital competence	Number of lecturers coded to response
EC	Interacting through technologies	2
Jisc	The capacity to adopt and develop new practices with digital technology	2
Jisc	The capacity to develop and project a positive digital identity or identities and to manage digital reputation	1
SCONUL	Assess which form(s) of digital media best meets the criteria identified (lecturers commenting on the range of tools available for that digital competence)	2
SCONUL	Recognise where digital solutions can meet a specific information task or need	2
SCONUL	Identify gaps in knowledge relating to digital tools or content	3

Table 23. The number of lecturers commenting about the range of digital tools available to them and the digital competence that prompted that response

A lack of time for lecturers to develop their digital competence has been mentioned in previous themes and appears in this theme too (Jamie, Jude, Masami, and Sam). Jude observes that technology development moves “*in days*” and that makes it difficult to fill gaps in knowledge, “*there is always going to be gaps*” (Masami). Time is doubly constraining on lecturers: there is the time to identify gaps in knowledge and the time to develop enough knowledge to use a new tool, “*there isn’t time to experiment, decisions have to be made quick*” (Sam). Ashley and Masami both acknowledge that the learning by doing approach may not be the best use of lecturer time. Furthermore, Masami notes that trying to keep up is “*exhausting*”, so much so that Jamie gets “*set in your ways*”.

“I’m probably going to take the easiest way whatever way that ends up being, you know, and then just if I find something that works, I’m probably going to go with it, rather than trying lots of different, you know, ways of or different tools because I probably don’t have the time to do lots of different, like, testing about I just find something and then go, okay, “that’ll do”.” (Masami)

The ever-expanding range of digital technology and a lack of time to fill knowledge gaps mean that lecturers are not knowledgeable about critically appraising new technology. Amal, Ashley and Masami all note that while the digital literacy frameworks promote the use of technology and the identification of knowledge gaps, there appears to be a lack of questioning as to “*whether it is any good*” (Amal). Ashley comments that academic institutions have not necessarily given lecturers guidance on potential problems or uses of technology:

“[Universities have not said] right, “If you want to use, you know, either whatever is for, for developing learning resources materials, whatever, here’s the, here’s the success criteria. Here’s things to be aware of” and ultimately we normally have to make a, we have to make a judgment somewhere as tutors down the line in terms of what we’re going to use and try.” (Ashley)

While lecturers have to be familiar with different tools to deliver a teaching method (Sam), they have to also know how they will work on different devices in order to be inclusive (Efe). As such, Efe would see what works for their students and “*be*

prepared to accept the fact that different students have like different things". Efe continues that "*core knowledge*" should be delivered in a "*safe manner*" but "*more fringe, exciting or emergent knowledge – that's when you play with technology*".

These reflections make for an interesting trichotomy: the centrally imposed technology by the university, lecturer agency to develop the curricula and technology use as they see fit, and empowering students to influence how programmes are delivered. Where the balance lies between the previous theme of centrally provided tools that save lecturers time and the need for appraisal, and lecturer agency, when the lecturers note a lack of time to fill knowledge gaps and their digital competencies, and where students fit in the picture remains unknown and worthy of further investigation.

Masami sums up the trichotomy neatly when discussing their university provided VLE and how they wouldn't necessarily think of the VLE as "*one digital technology because there's so many different things [the VLE] can do*". The flexibility that the LMS offers, gives lecturers agency to develop their courses according to the course and student pedagogical need, all whilst using centrally provided technology. However, with the move to online learning as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic, the university provided "*guidance*" on "*all the stuff you could do or should do*", removing said agency. Equally, a central approach ignores that academic disciplines have varying ways of engaging with technology (Jude).

Masami continues that providing too many tools can be exhausting for students, while Efe notes that lecturers developing their own style (with respect to technology use) can lead to a "*big diffuse mess*" where "*learners have different experiences all the time*" across a programme with different lecturers. Equally, Evelyn reflects that some of their colleagues completely reject the use of technology for reasons that would appear to represent technophobia or a fear for their jobs, while Jamie notes that universities incorrectly assume that lecturers are digitally competent. This trichotomy of university, lecturer, and student, and previous themes of a lack of digital competence in some lecturers, points toward a potential solution of mediated and guided use of technology. Here, lecturers would be given clear success criteria and potential uses, rather than a top-down (university-imposed technology) or

bottom-up (lecturer agency, influenced by student expectations) approach that appears to exist in these reflections.

One interesting reflection from Sam concerned supporting lecturers and their wellbeing:

“I think it’s also to do with, you know, when you’re as old as I am. I think that you’re meant to know things. If you don’t, it’s an absolute harassment because you’ve gotta learn something else like it’s, you know, it’s just, it’s just this sort of career long learning stuff that can be quite, sort of, you know, [pause], sometimes it’s quite dispiriting. You know, because you could you know that you could do really well in a conventional way but you’ve got to go back to square one to get the learning to do it as well in a digital way.” (Sam)

While we have heard of reluctance to engage with digital technology and an assumption that lecturers have digital competencies that they may not, universities must acknowledge that the reasons for these factors are multifaceted and that any guidance needs to be implemented in a supportive manner. A person-centred approach would resonate with Jude, who again makes reference to content being the most important factor, rather than tools. Sam’s reflection of knowing how to deliver content in a “*conventional way*” would perhaps seem less daunting if technology was seen as a delivery mechanism for learning rather than something that lecturers “*should be*” pushed to use as Masami noted.

A supportive approach to technology utilisation would also suit Efe’s thinking.

“Don’t expect to be using these emerging methods, or emerging pedagogies, to be smooth. Expect them to necessarily be bumpy. Prepare the students for them to be bumpy. Demonstrate how that – being bumpy – gives us all the capacity to learn new things.” (Efe)

6.10 Peers and students are crucial to the acquisition of new knowledge

The university digital environment and centrally available support may set the context upon which technologies are adopted and used, but lecturers tend to use

their own personal and professional networks to keep abreast of technology developments.

Amal has been “*pushed*” into using Microsoft Teams, university-provided collaborative software, but admits that unless there was pressure from a colleague “*who was quite savvy with all these things*”, they would not have explored the software, nor “*overcome [their] sort of technophobia*”. While training on new technology is organised centrally by the university, lecturers’ use of technology is driven by the needs of their teams and the projects they are working on (Jamie and Sam). Indeed, Sam manages a team and their focus at meetings is not just on the substance of what will be taught but on the mode of delivery; “*the team is the method [...] to share those sorts of things [new technologies]*”.

The collaborative nature of lecturing means that lecturers are continually acquiring new knowledge and technologies by working with different teams (Ashley and Jamie). Masami feels that this acquisition of knowledge is intuitive and not driven by an implicit need for new technology or ways of working, rather “*these [learning] opportunities, they just kind of happen*”. These observations take us back to earlier themes and the learning-by-doing method of knowledge acquisition.

In a related way to Masami, Sam acquires new knowledge when they hear someone talking about new technology and their curiosity drives them to investigate further, harking back to Efe’s earlier ‘keeping an open mind’ to learning about new technology and technology-driven teaching approaches. Interestingly, in a contribution that may be driven by Sam’s lack of confidence demonstrated earlier in this chapter, Sam noted that there was an IT forum where informal learning from a peer network was encouraged. However, Sam was reticent to attend as they perceived that other people attending the network would be more digitally literate than them.

Sam’s reflection may be driven by a lack of digital confidence or how lecturers feel sharing in a centrally organised public space, and there may be lessons in how universities can support an inclusive sharing and learning environment. Some lecturers have reported not wanting to experiment with technology in case they fail in front of students (Tshabalala, Ndeya-Ndereya and van der Merwe, 2014) but, for Evelyn, students can also be a source of learning. Evelyn reflects that their students

will ask “*Have you heard of this thing?*” or Evelyn will see students using something that they have not seen before and ask “*How did you do that? [or] Where did you learn that from?*”. This method of knowledge acquisition illustrates not only Evelyn’s willingness to learn from their students but also that their relationship with students is such they feel confident to suggest new ways of learning to Evelyn. Evelyn also shares their knowledge with peers, “*so there’s that kinda, you know, comes from top-down, bottom-up, from across the way as well.*”

6.11 Digital and information literacy frameworks lack meaning and contextual information

The final theme relates to the lenses through which lecturers construct their understanding of information literacy facets and digital competencies and may shed light on the second aim of the research, why lecturers construct these concepts in a disparate manner.

The concept of Plain English, although only directly cited by one lecturer, recurred throughout the interviews. The recurrences were for different competencies, across all frameworks, or made as a general discussion point. When Amal cited Plain English, they referred to the use of jargon and differing uses in terminology for a concept that made comprehension of the competence difficult, “*I think it makes them so much harder to understand if it’s not written in proper English*” (Amal). Jude refers to ‘*strategies*’ in one competency, labelling the word a “*buzzword*”. Jude would prefer context and meaning to enable lecturers to understand how to implement the competency in practice. Similarly, Sam notes the word “*innovation*” in another competency. Sam observes that innovation and creativity are often used as synonyms, defining each as “*innovation is to do with new ideas that can make money. And creativity is more interested in new ideas that help people to maybe understand themselves, to express themselves*”. For Sam, this competency takes on a different meaning due to ‘*innovation*’, whereas another lecturer may interpret the competency in another way.

A lack of contextual information to a competency was a source of frustration to Jude. Without additional context, Jude described the competence as “*meaningless*”.

Likewise, in response to a competency asking lecturers to assess online collaboration, Evelyn felt they understood the online collaboration environment, but

without further contextual information or assessment criteria, would not be able to fulfil the competency. Interestingly, Masami has the same reflection as Evelyn in response to a different competency that also asked lecturers to assess their practice. However, in response to a wordy competency, Efe's understanding would be enhanced by brevity in how the competence was written. There would appear to be a fine line in how competencies are written to enable comprehension and context without overburdening lecturers.

The overburdening of lecturers does not only apply to the length and readability of competencies, but also to the expectations that the frameworks put upon lecturers. Earlier themes have exposed an occasional lack of digital confidence from participants; lecturers purposively sampled for their digital skills and knowledge. Sam refers to one competency that will "*freak me out*", while in response to a different competency, Amal was "*frustrated by reading this*" and felt "*threatened*". Jude, meanwhile, rebuffed the notion of lecturers having to manage multiple digital identities, commenting that "*there is something wrong somewhere*". This, to me, evokes feelings that the frameworks are reinforcing pressure to not display one's true self and, in the context of increasing academic workload (Gregory and Lodge, 2015), putting additional burden on lecturers.

6.12 Chapter summary

Throughout this chapter we have seen the many varied ways in which lecturers construct their understanding of information literacy facets and digital competencies. The themes expose how pedagogy and ILOs are central to understanding and how knowledge is formed, with knowledge acquisition being shaped by peers and students. We have witnessed how the university digital environment shapes the adoption of technology, but also how pressure to utilise technology brings with it added pressure and can influence lecturer digital confidence. The gaps that lecturers feel they have in their digital competence varies on an individual level, and all lecturers noted a requirement for further guidance and support.

These themes have helped form an understanding of the aim and first research question of this phase: How do university lecturers construct their understanding of information literacy facets and digital competencies? The interviews only uncovered sparse information about the specific language of the competencies and facets, and

certainly did not provide enough data to provide one single answer to explain the heterogeneous nature of the findings from phase two. However, the themes I generated from the interviews did provide some insights into the nature of contexts through which digital competence is constructed. Indeed, many of the themes highlight the individualised nature of how digital competence is individualised through these various contexts. As such, given that the themes, and the similarities and differences seen across the themes, were deduced from a wide range of competencies and facets, across all three frameworks, I am now able to see why the workshops produced such heterogeneous results. These reflections from the participants help provide a glimpse into potential answers to the second research question: Does their understanding reveal why lecturers construct these concepts in such a disparate manner?

Moreover, the manner in which lecturers interpret the language of the frameworks and the frameworks' lack of meaning and contextual information compounded the different ways in which lecturers constructed their knowledge of information literacy and digital competence. Far from the frameworks being a template for universities to implement technology and for lecturers to increase their digital competence, my findings suggest that the frameworks should be seen as the start of a conversation on digital competence; that lecturer construction of digital competence is still at an embryonic stage.

However, all these themes and findings must be seen in the context of the time. The interviews were conducted between 22 June and 4 August 2020, a period in which the UK experienced various lockdowns as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic. As Nichols (2015, p.81) notes, one of the key contexts in contextual constructionism is that "the meaning of speech and behavior is highly dependent upon the settings in which it takes place". During this time, the university sector was at the beginning of a sudden shift to online learning and the interviewed lecturers, despite being sampled for their digital expertise, will have had various experiences of these rapid changes, as well had a range of emotions due to the pandemic itself.

In a final comment at the end of their interview, Ashley summarised just how embryonic digital competence is within the UK higher education sector. I have included the comment in whole as it relates so well to the summary of this chapter.

“I think it really is very important at this point because I think there's a lot of, a lot of different discussions about this kind of thing, but we tend to just use interchangeably different terms. And I think probably what you're, I guess what you're looking at are these are not quite the same thing. And, therefore, if someone wants to get maybe development support or otherwise to do these things, then we have to really segment these into key criteria and characteristics not bundle them all in and say, you know, digital, digital learning or whatever is the future, on we go. And what do you mean by that? What do we need to know in order to do a video thing or a thing for teaching or, you know, as I said, to edit a video to make it a learning resource rather than just what you're trying to achieve when you're trying to do it in the first place, because maybe that's not the right thing to be using. So I really think it's crucial that we, that we have more of this actually [research into digital competencies and how lecturers construct their knowledge]. (Ashley)

7 Discussion

7.1 Introduction to chapter

This chapter will provide a summary of the findings from each phase of the research. I will discuss why the findings were relevant and important and draw comparisons with related literature. I will also highlight the strengths and limitations of my research and highlight the gaps that remain in understanding how university lecturers construct their knowledge of information and digital literacy. I will begin the chapter with a reflection on the methodology.

7.2 Reflections on contextual constructionism

This study started out as a mixed methods study. I intended to create, validate, and distribute a quantitative questionnaire after the second phase of the research, the workshops. The heterogeneous nature of the results generated in the workshops required further contextual understanding and, as such, the quantitative element of the research could not proceed. I do not wish to elucidate further on quantitative methods as a positivist orientation would not align with the use of “I” in the thesis and would muddy the qualitative journey that this research has taken.

As a Professional Doctorate thesis, with research aims and questions originating from my professional background, coupled with my undertaking of the research as a professionally qualified librarian, a relativist stance has provided an appropriate position from which to explore my research. In phase one, I examined the appropriateness of the ANCIL framework to university lecturers. My analysis of ANCIL, itself a library-funded research project, relied upon on my professional knowledge and triangulation with library research literature. Phase two of the research, focused on how different professions understood and contextualised IL and DL, while phase three took a deeper look at how lecturers constructed their knowledge of IL and DL.

I noted in my methodology section that my relativist stance would be “centred around the belief that the experiences of lecturers will be understood only relative to their social and cultural practices (Given, 2008)”. Phase three in particular demonstrated just how individual and personal a lecturer’s social and cultural practices are to how they construct their knowledge of IL and DL. I hope, especially with the use of “I” in the thesis, that my own social and cultural practices with respect to IL and DL have

been visible throughout all phases of the research and that, too, has helped make “sociological sense” of my findings (Nichols, 2015, p.79), from which contextual constructionism centres.

7.3 Reflections on the aims of the research

The overall aim of the research was to develop a benchmark of digital competence among university lecturers. The initial objectives were to:

1. compile and critically analyse the existing literature on digital competency,
2. distil the competencies university lecturers need to be digitally competent based on information and digital literacy frameworks,
3. carry out workshops to form a multi-professional approach to the competencies university lecturers need to be digitally competent,
4. develop identified competencies into a quantitative questionnaire, and
5. distribute and analyse a questionnaire to lecturers across two university Health Schools to reveal a benchmark of digital competence among lecturers.

The heterogenous nature of the findings after the workshops with lecturers, librarians, and learning technologists, phase two of the research, meant that objectives four and five of the research were not able to be completed. As such, a new aim replaced the fourth and fifth aims:

4. undertake interviews with lecturers to explore the reasons why lecturers, librarians and learning technologists construct information and digital literacy in dissimilar ways.

With a plethora of IL and DL frameworks², I felt it important to distil the frameworks to those situated in UK university education and those relevant to my professional background as a librarian, in alignment with my methodology. The objective of translating the ANCIL framework (Secker and Coonan, 2011) to be relevant to university lecturers was a challenge that I underestimated. Secker and Coonan

² See, for example, the long list of frameworks discovered by McGill, L. and Beetham, H. (2015) *Framing digital capabilities for UK HE and FE staff: Frameworks review*. Available at: <https://docs.google.com/document/d/1Uq0lw18XVqow5sUBQniJrpcV1qF1sPqKSC73SdvHPQU/edit> (Accessed: 3 October 2016). in their preparatory review for the Jisc DL framework.

created ANCIL as part of a research project from May to July 2011. I somewhat naively thought that translating the framework would be a relatively simple process, but a paucity of literature exploring IL from a lecturer perspective made the triangulation between my experiences and published literature more challenging than expected. The additional level of self-reflection on my own experience, practices, and views on IL and how they related to lecturers and the ANCIL framework provided an additional level of complexity. Nonetheless, I am confident in the outcome of the translation process as I further reflect below.

The main challenge on reaching the initial research aim was the workshop phase of the research. Although I expected a degree of heterogeneity in workshops due to the nature of how individuals construct their knowledge of IL and DL, I had expected that the combined professions and experiences would provide a level of homogeneity across the workshop groups. I further reflect on the methods and findings in the discussion of the phase two workshops. Alas, the data did not allow me to distil the DL competencies sufficiently to begin processing the competencies into a questionnaire.

The additional aim of exploring how lecturers construct their knowledge of IL and DL provided a rich dataset that goes some way to helping us understand the perspectives of lecturers, a perspective that has not been explored before. I reflect further on the methods, findings, and insights that each phase of my research has made in the sections below.

7.4 Phase one: What digital competencies do university lecturers need to be digitally competent? One librarian's view

This phase of the research concerned the second aim of the research: to reconcile digital literacy frameworks, through an information literacy lens, and distil the competencies university lecturers need to be digitally competent. This aim arose from a problem accentuated in literature review, that frameworks were focused on the public or students, at various levels of study. The aim additionally situated the research in my professional background with the distillation of DL through an IL lens and provided the foundations of the multi-professional workshops in phase two.

Phase one of the research addressed the following research questions:

- How does the 'A new curriculum for information literacy' (ANCIL) framework relate to university lecturers in a UK university context?
- What digital literacy frameworks are in use across a sample of UK universities?

7.4.1 Reflections on the research methods

When scoping the DL frameworks in use at UK universities, I attempted to minimise bias by using a simple random selection method rather than a stratified sampling method. This method eliminated sample selection bias but still provided a representative sample of universities and hence frameworks. Despite a relatively small sample of ten universities, the findings gave an accurate picture of frameworks in use rather than a theoretical list of frameworks in existence. An understanding of the frameworks used in practice also enhanced the chance that participants in phase two would be familiar with the frameworks, giving greater opportunity to critically reflect on the competencies in the workshops.

The ANCIL framework was purposively sampled. As well as ANCIL aligning with my professional background, ANCIL also offered a research-based framework whose methods were open to critique, therefore, offering an appropriate framework for doctoral study. The creators of ANCIL had appraised other IL frameworks as part of their work and re-appraising the frameworks would constitute research waste.

The framework analysis method (Ritchie and Spencer, 1994) provided a valuable method for reconciling the digital literacy frameworks through an information literacy lens. That framework analysis allows within-case and between-case analysis (Srivastava and Thomson, 2009) meant that I could examine ANCIL across the various strand content and learning outcomes, both at a whole framework level and individual strand and facet level. This level of analysis allowed me to expand IL facets where lecturers required more nuanced competence areas than undergraduate students, who are the focus of the framework, but also condense or combine facets where the inverse was true or where duplication occurred between strand areas.

7.4.2 Discussion of phase one findings

7.4.2.1 How does the 'A new curriculum for information literacy' (ANCIL) framework relate to university lecturers in a UK university context?

My analysis of how ANCIL relates to UK university lecturers provided a unique perspective on IL which, to the best of my knowledge, has not been seen in academic or grey literature to date.

Many of the strands of ANCIL simply required modification of language and context to move from being a framework suitable to undergraduate students, to becoming an IL framework for university lecturers. The opening strand, "Transition from school to higher education" is a good example where the context of the strand required a different focus, but where a concept of transition was still required. For lecturers, transition occurs when moving to a first lecturing post, to those promoted to senior positions, and when moving to different schools or universities, for example. For this strand, I focussed on the requirements of transition to and within the "scholarly environment", as referenced in grey and academic IL literature, rather than a move from school to university.

However, in some cases I chose to omit entire strands from the lecturer version of ANCIL because the holistic nature of ANCIL made some strands less relevant to core IL concepts. Academic literacies, strand 3 of ANCIL, is generally taught outside of the library (Murray, 2016). This strand did not resonate with my professional practice but, equally, "prior knowledge, beliefs, and experiences and teaching and institutional contexts influence librarians' pedagogical practices and approaches to the Framework [the US-based Association of College and Research Libraries (ACRL) IL framework]" (Baer, 2020, p.185). Other librarians may, therefore, disagree with this omission, indeed, that is why in a UK context many bespoke IL frameworks exist (Reedy and Baker, 2011) or bespoke frameworks based on published versions (Gallacher, 2009). Indeed, one may consider developing an IL framework as an individual a limitation, but there are examples in my literature review of single researchers developing research instruments (Duta, 2014), a matrix of digital literacy elements (Belshaw, 2012), and models (De Brún, 2015), and also methodological alignment with this personal perspective.

7.4.2.2 What digital literacy frameworks are in use across a sample of UK universities?

Identifying the DL frameworks in use across UK universities was an important step in distilling the digital competencies required in lecturers. The purpose of this research question was to sample the frameworks in use rather than produce an exhaustive list of frameworks in existence, research already undertaken by Jisc as part of their “Framing digital capabilities for UK HE and FE staff: frameworks review” (McGill and Beetham, 2015). The sampling of frameworks in use also aligns with my professional-based research questions, whilst simultaneously providing a list of frameworks whose language participants in the workshops may be more familiar with.

The finding that 9 out of 10 sampled universities use or refer to the Jisc DL framework (Beetham, 2017) will not surprise many given Jisc’s market dominance in the UK university sector. I also found reference to the SCONUL (2016) (n=1) and the EC DigComp framework (Ferrari, 2013) (n=1). While a survey of frameworks in use at Australian universities has been undertaken (Huber and Shalavin, 2018), I am not aware of a similar survey of UK universities.

Interestingly, a replication of the methods used to identify DL frameworks in use at the sampled universities shows that one university (University of Wales, Trinity Saint David) where I was unable to find a framework in use in October 2018 now references the Jisc discovery tool. The discovery tool is a self-assessment tool used to show strengths and limitations in an individual’s DL competence and is not a framework, but shows further evidence of Jisc’s presence in the UK university sector. Maybe the lack of change in the other universities is indication that they are still using and are happy with the frameworks previously identified or whether progress on utilising frameworks has stalled or even whether universities have moved on from framework adoption is unknown. My own anecdotal feeling is that the university sector has moved on from frameworks to assessing DL competence in staff; perhaps too soon if the language of DL is still uncertain, as revealed in my interview findings.

University	Framework used (Oct 2018)	Framework used (updated Nov 2021)
University of Bristol	Not explicitly stated, but references to Jisc and SCONUL	No additional information
University of Sussex	Not explicitly stated, but references to Jisc	No additional information
Nottingham Trent University	Explicit reference to Jisc framework embedded in practice and linked as a resource	No additional information
Anglia Ruskin	Bespoke framework, informed by Jisc and EC DigComp	No additional information
Ulster University	Explicit reference to Jisc framework	No additional information
Bath Spa University	Digital programme funded by Jisc	No additional information
The Open University	Bespoke framework, informed by Jisc	No additional information
University of Wales, Trinity Saint David	Not explicitly stated	Digital skills framework, references to Jisc discovery tool
Northumbria University	Explicit use of Jisc framework	No additional information
University of Sheffield	Bespoke framework, Jisc as starting point	No additional information

Table 24. An update of Table 12, used in phase one, showing the sampled universities and the DL frameworks used as of October 2018 and November 2021

One limitation of this phase was the small sample size of UK universities (7.6% of UK public universities at the time of the research). As a qualitative study, I was not aiming for “representativeness”, merely an indication of DL frameworks in use. However, such was the finding and dominance of Jisc, that I am not convinced a positivist saturation sampling method would have had changed the findings.

7.5 Phase two: What competencies do university lecturers need to demonstrate digital competence? Views of Lecturers, Librarians, and Learning Technologists

Phase two investigated the third aim of the research: to carry out workshops to form a multi-professional approach to the competencies university lecturers need to be digitally competent. The purpose of this aim was to explore how different professional groups constructed their knowledge of IL and DL and, using their knowledge and experience, consider the digital competences relevant to university lecturers in the UK. As such, phase two sought to answer the following research questions:

- What digital competencies do I feel are relevant to university lecturers, and why?
- Which of these digital competencies do I believe are relevant to information literacy, and why?
- What digital competencies do a multi-professional group of lecturers, learning technologists, and librarians feel are relevant to university lecturers, and why?
- Which of these digital competencies are relevant to information literacy, and why?

The same questions, answered from my own perspective and those of other lecturers, librarians, and learning technologists, was an attempt to further situate the research in my own professional background and experiences and, therefore, bring methodological alignment. The differing perspectives also intended to bring a measure of trustworthiness and limit the risk of bias compared to approaching the research solely from the perspective of a librarian.

7.5.1 Reflections on the research methods

My study has been conducted in two convenience sampled UK universities. Although comparisons have not been made between different groups within each university, they both offer contrasting focus and strategies that offer a degree of transferability to the general UK university landscape. The convenience sample was also a pragmatic step as I understood the cultures in both universities, thereby potentially making findings easier to contextualise, although this was not necessary, due to the nature of the findings. A larger sample of universities would have enhanced the

transferability of the study, but the practicalities of arranging access to facilities and participants would have increased the complexities of the research. The benefit of a pragmatic sample surpassed the perceived benefit of increased transferability, especially when considering the qualitative nature of the study.

My sampling of participants was as objective as possible, being near-complete samples or, for lecturers, a purposive sample taken from research outputs displaying knowledge of DL. As noted in the methods chapter for this phase, participants with knowledge of IL and DL would be more likely to be able to actively participate in the workshop exercise and reflect upon their knowledge and experiences. A random sample of participants may not have achieved the same level of reflection and participation. Even with purposive sampling, across both universities, I achieved a reasonable balance of participants from the Arts and Humanities and STEMM subjects, as illustrated in Table 25.

Profession	Discipline categorisation	Number of participants
Learning Technologist	Arts and Humanities	2
Learning Technologist	STEMM	2
Lecturer	Arts and Humanities	4
Lecturer	STEMM	4
Librarian	Arts and Humanities	4
Librarian	STEMM	2

Table 25. Workshop participants by discipline categorisation

Given that I had prior professional relationships with some participants, I was careful to ensure that participants understood that my role in the workshops was that of an independent researcher when discussing the ground rules. I was mindful of this factor when recruiting participants and in the workshops and interviews.

The workshop materials were simple, the task itself was straight-forward, and the participants themselves appeared confident undertaking the task. On reflection, allowing an extra 30 minutes for the workshops would have provided a little more space in the peer debrief and participant reflection on the exercise. I was conscious that the workshops were scheduled during lunch breaks and that some participants had commitments after the hour. However, a longer workshop may have meant that participants would not have been able to or would be less willing to attend.

Ultimately, given the heterogeneous nature of the workshop outputs, additional time

would not have provided the depth of analysis or reflection required to explain the findings.

7.5.2 Discussion of phase two findings

The workshops found that multi-professional groups of lecturers, librarians, and learning technologists cannot agree on the DL competencies that relate to IL. The groups could not agree on where DL competencies mapped to IL facets, nor could they agree whether DL competencies were relevant to lecturers but not IL, nor whether certain DL competencies were entirely irrelevant to lecturers. This is a novel and an important finding. A lack of agreement on these concepts is problematic for the creators of frameworks, those trying to implement digital strategies in universities, and on the strategic development of lecturers, both from the perspective of self-development and for professional service staff offering training to lecturers.

From a professional perspective, this finding also means that librarians may find their epistemological knowledge base challenged by other stakeholders in DL. In the introduction, I used the image of overlapping circles taken from Jisc's Digital capabilities framework (Beetham, 2017) (Figure 11) to illustrate how each component of DL could represent the epistemological and tacit knowledge of different professions. If lecturers, librarians, and learning technologists cannot agree how DL relates to IL, this provides a challenge to the professional knowledge of librarians and those looking for curriculum development support or self-development opportunities who may fail to identify the expertise that librarians hold in these areas.

Figure 12. Image from Jisc (2015) Digital capabilities framework illustrating the holistic nature of digital literacy in Venn diagram form

The lack of agreement between workshop groups was stark. The number of times groups agreed where a digital competency should be mapped to an IL facet was low (Table 26).

Number of matches	Number of occurrences
5	1
4	4
3	13
2	37
1	202

Table 26. Number of times groups mapped DL competencies to the same IL facet

One possible explanation for this lack of agreement may lie in differences in language and conflation of terminology. While there appears to be little literature on specific IL facets and DL competencies, there is much debate on the definition of the concepts of IL and DL. Cordell (2013), for example, notes that there are commonalities in how digital and information literacy are defined. The lack of conceptual differentiation could possibly lead to conflation but, conversely, I would expect similarities to lead to greater harmonisation in how DL is mapped to IL. However, in their systematic review of concepts in media literacy, IL, and DL, Wuyckens, Landry and Fastrez (2022) note that researchers from different disciplines approach these concepts in diverse ways. Whilst this is not a problem

and may aid “interdisciplinary enrichment” (p.174), one cannot discern exactly how disciplines approach these concepts because so few researchers reveal their “disciplinary postures” (p.174). These differing disciplinary perspectives may have led to harmonious results if I had groups of librarians, learning technologists, and lecturers working separately in the workshops, but this would not have reflected the real-world interdisciplinary nature of curriculum and staff development.

The finding that Jisc competencies were mapped to a greater number of IL facets than the SCONUL and EC DigComp competencies is an interesting discovery (Table 27), especially given the prominence of Jisc in UK universities.

Framework name	Average occurrence of a DL competence mapped to an IL facet
EC DigComp	4.2
SCONUL	4.4
Jisc	7.5

Table 27. Mean average occurrence of a digital competence mapped to an IL facet by framework

The Jisc competence, “The capacity to find, evaluate, manage, curate, organise and share digital information” covers the whole spectrum of IL; indeed, this competence was mapped across all IL categories by workshop participants. The amalgamation of many IL concepts into one competence may be purposeful but, given that IL is multifaceted, it would not help a lecturer develop their digital competence in a specific area of IL. It is perhaps no surprise to see the level of disagreement between workshop groups when some DL competencies are vague, especially coupled with different disciplinary perspectives on the terminology of IL and DL.

To avoid bias, should the participants have been familiar with the frameworks, the competencies were randomly assigned and the framework in which they appeared were not revealed to participants. In effect, this removed the competencies from their wider context. Participants were not able to see the order in which the competencies were presented in the frameworks nor be able to read the introduction to the framework that may have provided additional contextual information. The lack of wider contextual information is a limitation of hiding the frameworks from participants. However, beyond this measure, the practicalities of having participants distil the competencies from a document could have proven challenging in a group workshop exercise. Providing participants with pre-workshop reading may have

aided their contextual knowledge but, equally, participants were selected because of their expertise in IL and DL. Additionally, in students, very few undertake pre-class reading (Heiner, Banet and Wieman, 2014; Chen *et al.*, 2021) and the same could have been true for workshop participants.

The findings from this phase of the research provide novel insights into the language of IL and DL, and how professional groups may conceptualise these concepts in different ways. Further research into the terminology used in IL and DL frameworks would provide a more granular understanding of specific IL facets and DL competencies rather than the concepts of IL and DL themselves as reviewed Wuyckens, Landry and Fastrez (2022). If this research is coupled with perspectives from professional groups, then the next generation of IL and DL frameworks may provide greater clarity of concepts to aid curriculum and self-development in these areas.

I sought to answer the following research questions for phase two:

- What digital competencies do I feel are relevant to university lecturers, and why?
- Which of these digital competencies do I believe are relevant to information literacy, and why?
- What digital competencies do a multi-professional group of lecturers, learning technologists, and librarians feel are relevant to university lecturers, and why?
- Which of these digital competencies are relevant to information literacy, and why?

Ultimately, the heterogenous nature of the findings for this phase of the research meant that I was unable to answer these questions nor progress on the initial aim of phase three, create and distribute a questionnaire to two university Health Schools to reveal a benchmark of digital competence among lecturers.

7.6 Phase three: Deepening our understanding of lecturer construction of information literacy and digital competence

Phase three of the research was a new phase brought about because of the heterogenous nature of the findings after the workshops with lecturers, librarians, and learning technologists. The objective of this phase was to:

4. undertake interviews with lecturers to explore the reasons why lecturers, librarians, and learning technologists construct information and digital literacy in dissimilar ways.

The interviews were chosen as a method to explore, in depth, the reasons why lecturers, librarians, and learning technologists construct information and digital literacy in dissimilar ways by addressing the following research questions:

- How do university lecturers construct their understanding of information literacy facets and digital competencies?
- Does their understanding reveal why lecturers construct these concepts in such a disparate manner?

7.6.1 Reflections on the research methods

After reflecting on the reasons for the heterogenous findings in the previous phase of the research, I decided that interviews would provide an appropriate, in-depth exploration of the ways in which lecturers construct their knowledge of information literacy and digital competence. My minimally structured interviews allowed an adaptable approach that would “generate a deeper and somewhat empathic understanding of their lives” (Ward and Delamont, 2020, p.333).

Piloting the interview allowed me to adapt the initial idea of replicating the workshop format into one that was feasible in an hour-long interview and one that did not overburden participants. The changes made from the pilot to the final interview format maintained similarities with the workshops and provided sufficient time to gain a rich understanding of how lecturers construct their understanding of IL facets and digital competencies.

The Braun and Clarke (2006) “Big Q” approach to thematic analysis, one that acknowledges the professional background, skills, and experiences that I bring to my research, aligns my use of contextual constructionism as a methodology.

Furthermore, the lack of a coding structure in the Braun and Clarke method allowed me to derive themes generated directly from participants, which was important given the explorative nature of the research questions and paucity of literature to explain the workshop findings.

7.6.2 Discussion of phase three findings

7.6.2.1 How do university lecturers construct their understanding of information literacy facets and digital competencies?

This phase of the research discovered that lecturer construction of digital competence is still at an embryonic stage. Most lecturers struggled with the language used across the various digital competencies and IL facets. This lack of comprehension is an important finding, especially coming from an expert group. Indeed, since this study started there have been many studies assessing digital competence in university settings, and even several systematic reviews published that attempt to assimilate this research (see Ballano, Mallari and Sebastian, 2022; Basilotta-Gómez-Pablos *et al.*, 2022; Esteve-Mon, Llopis-Nebot and Adell-Segura, 2020; Fernandez-Batanero *et al.*, 2021; González Calleros *et al.*, 2022; Gumanová and Šukolová, 2022; Perdomo, Gonzalez-Martinez and Barreto, 2020; Vinales-Cosentino, Sanchez-Caballe and Esteve-Mon, 2022; Zhao, Pinto Llorente and Sánchez Gómez, 2021). My finding that lecturers construct their knowledge in different ways challenges this rush to assess the level of digital competence in lecturers; how can one assess a competency when lecturers are uncertain of its meaning?

I identified six other themes from my interviews, starting with a finding that the gaps in lecturer digital competence was individualised. Lecturers focussed on student development, rather than strategically planning their learning, only identifying a gap in their knowledge when a need arose. This finding raises important questions for universities, librarians, and learning technologists as to how to support lecturers to identify gaps in their knowledge before they arise, and how to build capacity to assist individual lecturer requirements rather than through generic training. Basilotta-Gómez-Pablos *et al.* (2022) conclude their review on lecturer digital competence in a similar manner, noting the “great challenge” (p.13) of continuous professional development for lecturers who all have individual training requirements.

Pedagogy and ILOs dictate where digital technology is adopted by lecturers and digital competence formed. This was a similar finding to one I made in my rapid review, that lecturers and early adopters assess each piece of technology against its pedagogical relevance before adopting it. In this respect, the finding is not new.

However, most studies of lecturer digital competence are self-assessments and show higher technical ability than pedagogically appropriate use of technology (Esteve-Mon, Llopis-Nebot and Adell-Segura, 2020). This suggests further research is required to understand the pedagogical construction of digital competence. This may, in turn, shift university training and support for digital tools from a model that has historically focussed on the technology itself (Georgina and Olson, 2008) to one centred on the pedagogical use of technology in teaching.

Aligned to universities adopting a technology rather than pedagogical-centred approach to digital tools, was the finding that the university digital environment determines whether technology adoption will be successful. Antunes, Armellini and Howe (2021) note the top-down manner that technologies are adopted in universities. This aligns with the comments made by participants about standardised and cumbersome technologies that are unfit for purpose and imposed on lecturers, often without notice. Indeed, Ertmer and Ottenbreit-Leftwich (2010) note that the digital environment forces lecturers to “conform” (p.264) to the degree that it prohibits good teaching practices. Coupled with the requirement for further research into the pedagogical construction of digital competence in lecturers, universities, in particular IT departments, and researchers should also reflect upon how the university digital environment shapes utilisation of technology and the development of digital competence in lecturers.

My finding that lecturers require guidance and support to increase their digital competence and technology utilisation is neither new nor novel. The earliest result from my rapid review noting the requirement for additional support for lecturer development of digital competence was 2009. The same is being said in reviews published in 2022 (Vinoles-Cosentino, Sanchez-Caballe and Esteve-Mon, 2022). So why, 13 years later, are we still asking the same questions and noting the same gaps in the literature? Partly, this is due to a lack of standardised (Gumanová and Šukolová, 2022) and validated tools (Zhao, Pinto Llorente and Sánchez Gómez, 2021) used in research that is holding back development of our knowledge and understanding of digital competence in lecturers. Relatedly, there is a lack of longitudinal research (Connaway *et al.*, 2013). There are also cultural and environmental issues, as noted above.

In addition to the aforementioned factors, technology appears to change at a fast pace. In my interviews, Sam displayed a feeling of helplessness when they compared themselves to lecturers using advanced digital technologies in their teaching. Amal described difficulties overcoming technophobia. It is worth noting that interview participants were sampled based on their expertise in utilising digital tools, yet these two participants were overcome by technology. While wellbeing and mental health were not themes I constructed from my interviews, it is worth pausing and reflecting upon the pace of change and its effect on lecturers, especially in light of the digital shift brought about by the COVID-19 pandemic and technology's effect of negatively merging work and life (Fetherston *et al.*, 2021).

There also appears to be a persistent level of lecturers who reject technology or lack digital competence or confidence, as Masami commented on in the interviews. Ertmer and Ottenbreit-Leftwich (2010) state that a change in mindset is required in some lecturers regarding their use of technology in their teaching. While this study focusses on experts and other research has focussed on early adopters of technology (Bennett, 2014), there appears little research that looks at late adopters or those with lower levels of digital competence. Further research on those with lower levels of digital competence would provide a rounder picture of digital competence in university lecturers.

The lack of standardised and validated tools, longitudinal research, poor university digital environments, the pace of change, lecturer wellbeing, and a lack of understanding of lecturers possessing low levels of digital competence all appear to be factors in why lecturers still require guidance and support to increase their digital competence and technology utilisation.

For those lecturers who do develop digital competence and acquire new knowledge, peers and students play a crucial role in this learning process. Interview participants noted that one method to navigate the range of new technologies was through peer networks and team meetings. This, in turn, developed curiosity for lecturers to experiment with new technologies in their teaching. Indeed, even among early adopters, there is still demand for a community of practice and "show and tells" (Dale *et al.*, 2021, p.33). Peer acquisition of knowledge would appear to provide an effective model for development of digital competence and technology adoption

(Kimberley and Suvandzhieva, 2021). This model of learning aligns with my finding that lecturers accept technology when the pedagogical relevance is clear.

Furthermore, pedagogically aligned, peer acquisition of knowledge runs contrary to earlier discussions about how universities have historically implemented technology in a top-down, technology-centred manner. This should provide a point of reflection for universities and those supporting lecturer knowledge and skills development.

Finally, I identified that digital and information literacy frameworks lack meaning and contextual information. Some studies in my rapid review and the systematic reviews cited at the beginning of this discussion use or base their research instruments on information or digital literacy frameworks, and there has been a systematic review on the specific concepts of 'digital competence' and 'digital literacy' in higher education (Spante *et al.*, 2018). I am not, however, aware of any papers that critique the language of the frameworks themselves, especially from the perspective of lecturers utilising the frameworks, beyond the scoping work of the framework creators themselves.

I noted in my reflections on the methods that a limitation of this research is that the competencies were removed from the framework document itself, but even with that limitation in mind, lecturers were often left confused or even "*freaked out*" by the wording of DL competencies. Research into the perspectives of framework users may enable the next generation of frameworks to become more user friendly and relatable.

7.6.2.2 Does their understanding reveal why lecturers construct these concepts in such a disparate manner?

My interview findings do not explicitly reveal a single reason that might explain the heterogeneous nature of the workshop findings or why lecturers construct their understanding of information literacy facets and digital competencies in disparate ways. This study has, however, found that lecturers construct their understanding of IL facets and digital competencies in a highly individual and contextual manner. My first theme, "The reasons for gaps in lecturer digital competence is many and varied" exemplifies this finding. Lecturer construction of knowledge of IL facets and digital competencies centres around pedagogy and ILOs, factors that are contextualised to their teaching, disciplinary needs, and student requirements. These, in turn, are

influenced by the university digital environment and culture. These findings align with a lecturer's individual approach to teaching and scholarship and their professional background as noted in the reviews of Basilotta-Gómez-Pablos *et al.* (2022) and Gumanová and Šukolová (2022).

The themes I identified were coded from a wide range of IL facets and digital competencies, across all three frameworks on which the interviews were based. Given this range of coding and the individualised way in which lecturers approach IL and DL, it is perhaps not a surprise that lecturers construct their knowledge of IL and digital competence in a disparate manner. Frameworks have the potential to unify concepts of digital competence. However, the lecturers I interviewed found that frameworks used language that they did not relate to and lacked meaning and contextual information. This may compound the individualised approach that lecturers take to DL, potentially exacerbating the disparate construction of these concepts.

These findings are, however, from interviews with eight lecturers from two universities. Larger samples may have produced different themes and findings. Nonetheless, further research into how lecturers interpret and use IL and DL frameworks could provide additional insight into how frameworks could be utilised in universities to effectively develop digital competence in lecturers.

7.7 Chapter summary

I began this chapter with a reflection on my contextual constructionism, detailing how the methodology brought alignment with the professional nature of this doctorate and my wish to explore IL and digital competence through the personal teaching and learning experiences of lecturers and their pedagogical approaches.

Phase one of my research provided a unique insight into how IL can be framed from the perspective of a university lecturer in the UK. Utilising the research-based ANCIL framework, I was able to demonstrate how context and wording might change to move IL from a student-based construct to one appropriate for lecturers. In some cases, an IL facet only required a modification to the wording and context to be appropriate for a lecturer, in other cases whole facets were merged or removed because the student context did not fit the lecturer model of IL. My 'ANCIL for

lecturers' framework will provide a base for other researchers to explore IL from a lecturer perspective, and future research in this respect would be welcome.

Phase two provided a detailed exploration of how librarians, learning technologists, and lecturers construct IL and digital competence. I discussed how a lack of agreement between workshop groups could be due to language differences and conflation with terminology, pointing to literature that both supported and contradicted this finding. The finding that the Jisc framework was mapped to the most IL facets is problematic given how embedded the Jisc approach is within UK universities, as also demonstrated in the sampling of frameworks in this phase. There does not appear to be significant research into the specific language of IL and DL beyond the specific terms themselves. Further research into the specifics of IL and DL terminology, and how different groups construct meaning from IL and DL would help determine a clearer path for research in this domain.

The final phase of the research sought to explore the heterogeneous findings from the workshops from the perspective of the principal population of interest, university lecturers. I found that there are still many questions to be answered before research into IL and DL can proceed to measuring digital competence in lecturers.

The first theme from my interviews with an expert group of lecturers was that lecturers construct their understanding of IL facets and digital competencies in a highly personalised way. I discussed how this individual construction of digital competence left lecturers unable to identify gaps in their knowledge until those gaps arose. This challenges the cost-effective model of learning generally adopted by many universities where training is generic to all staff and disciplines. This first discussion point is related to the second theme generated from the interviews, that pedagogy is the central construct around which knowledge and understanding is formed and technology adopted. This similarly means that training and support for technology requires a far more individual approach than is generally offered in universities. For those wishing to utilise frameworks, from a university-wide adoption to departmental level adoptions, the individual and pedagogy-centred approach to digital competence requires further nuance than one framework can provide. Additional contextualisation to disciplines and individuals is likely to be required. This

again provides a point of reflection for universities and professional services staff supporting digital competence at universities.

Similarly, I discussed the effect of the digital environment at universities and how the lack of appropriate technology can prohibit good teaching practice. This finding, coupled with the individualism in how lecturers construct their knowledge of IL and DL requires a change in approach towards technology adoption and implementation by universities, especially IT departments.

My discussion on the theme that lecturers require additional support echoes throughout all the previous themes and their implications. It is perhaps no surprise that lecturers require support to develop digital competence when lecturers construct their knowledge of DL in a personal, pedagogically centred way, but simultaneously feel held back by institutional digital environments. Interestingly, my discussion noted a level of technophobia in an expert group. While digital confidence has been noted in the past (Greener and Wakefield, 2015), there is a gap in our knowledge on confidence and the related group of late adopters, which can potentially offer new avenues and insights in this field of research.

A further finding and discussion point was how crucial peers and students are to knowledge acquisition. As with the previous discussion points, this mode of learning challenges the traditional model of training offered in universities and requires new approaches to foster communities of practice and shared interest groups to further develop lecturer digital competence.

My final theme was that the frameworks themselves lacked meaning and contextual relevance. I discussed a limitation where the competencies used for the workshops and interviews were removed from the wider document. However, this limitation alone does not account for the heterogeneous findings from the workshop phase of the research. My discussion noted how the frameworks could potentially alienate lecturers when they could be used as a foundation for developing digital competence within universities. Worryingly, for researchers using the frameworks to base research instruments, especially in a field with few validated instruments (Zhao, Pinto Llorente and Sánchez Gómez, 2021), these findings cause particular concern for the subsequent validity of the findings. Future research on how different groups of

lecturers construct their knowledge of IL and DL will aid the development of valid, unified research instruments.

My findings and discussion do not specifically explain a sole reason why librarians, learning technologists, and lecturers construct their knowledge of IL and DL in a disparate manner but do provide some unique insights that can aid the development of future frameworks and the development of digital competence. The findings and discussion also provide many challenges to how universities implement technology and provide training and development opportunities to lecturers. In the next chapter, I will conclude with the implications of this research for universities and professional stakeholders looking to develop digital competence in university lecturers.

8 Conclusions and implications for professional practice

8.1 Introduction to chapter

The previous chapter provided a discussion of the research journey, from methodology to findings and strengths and limitations. This chapter will conclude the discussions and provide implications for professional practice resulting from this research. I will offer a summary of the limitations of the study and reflect on my Professional Doctorate journey.

8.2 Conclusion

The final aims of this study were to:

1. compile and critically analyse the existing literature on digital competency,
2. distil the competencies university lecturers need to be digitally competent based on information and digital literacy frameworks,
3. carry out workshops to form a multi-professional approach to the competencies university lecturers need to be digitally competent,
4. undertake interviews with lecturers to explore the reasons why lecturers, librarians, and learning technologists construct information and digital literacy in dissimilar ways.

The first aim, to compile and critically analyse the existing literature on digital competency, was achieved through the introductory literature review that set the context and importance of DL, and digital competence, within university education. The professional context and gap in the literature with respect to librarians work in digital competencies was noted, as was the lack of literature on DL and university lecturers. My rapid review which, incidentally, utilised a greater range of sources and search terms than the systematic reviews cited in the discussion, provided a rigorous method to focus the literature on the levels of digital competence in the primary population of interest in this study, university lecturers. The topics identified in the review highlighted the lack of robust data on digital competence in university lecturers, but also topics related to some of the themes later identified in the lecturer interviews, such as the pedagogical relevance of technology being important to lecturers.

The second aim was to distil the competencies university lecturers need to be digitally competent. This aim was achieved through the development of a lecturer-specific IL lens, in the form of the modified ANCIL framework, through which to examine DL. A scoping exercise was used to identify DL frameworks in use at UK universities. I then distilled the digital competencies contained within the frameworks through the IL lens.

Following the distillation process, I convened workshops to form a multi-professional approach to the competencies university lecturers need to be digitally competent, the third aim of the study. Building upon the proceeding work, this aim was achieved by sampling expert users from three stakeholder groups in lecturer and curriculum development. By working in multi-disciplinary professional groups and inter-disciplinary subject groups, the workshops provided a glimpse into how the lecturers, librarians, and learning technologists in the two universities sampled construct their knowledge of IL and digital competence.

The final aim, amended from the initial aims to compile and distribute a questionnaire to reveal a benchmark of digital competence among lecturers, was to undertake interviews with lecturers to explore how they construct their knowledge of information and digital literacy. I achieved this aim by interviewing an expert group of eight lecturers, using a minimally structured interview schedule that asked how they interpreted and would utilise a sample of five IL facets and 10 digital competences used in the workshops. The minimal structure provided me with a rich dataset on how these lecturers constructed their information and digital literacy, and partly explained the heterogeneous data from the workshops.

The findings that arose from these aims has provided a number of unique perspectives and insights that, to the best of my knowledge, have yet to be explored in academic or grey literature.

The first phase of the research provided a novel perspective of IL for university lecturers. Subsequent to the research concluding, the European Commission published a version of their DigComp framework for educators (Redecker, 2017). This framework covers educators at all levels of education, from primary to higher education. The “European Framework for the Digital Competence of Educators (DigCompEdu)” builds upon the digital competencies required for all citizens in

DigComp by providing an additional 22 competencies covering an educator's professional, pedagogic, and learners' competencies. March 2022 also saw the publication of DigComp 2.2 (Vuorikari, Kluzer and Punie, 2022), an updated version of the DigComp framework used in my research. These recent developments in DL are welcome but, beyond my findings for this phase, a gap remains from an IL perspective for educators and specifically university lecturers.

The workshops found that this sample of lecturers, librarians, and learning technologists from these two universities could not agree how digital competencies related to IL concepts, even though this was an expert group of users. This is a novel and an important finding. However, there is not enough literature critically appraising IL or DL frameworks or case studies explaining why universities who have adapted the frameworks for local context have chosen to do so. Additionally, there is not enough research on the specific terminology of IL and DL to fully understand why this finding occurred. This is not to say that the frameworks lack reliability, their widespread use indicates their usefulness, but these findings, should they resonate with others, may provide a point of reflection for the creators of the frameworks and those utilising them. Furthermore, without a consensus view on how DL relates to IL, librarians may find their epistemological knowledge base challenged by other stakeholders in DL.

The finding that groups of lecturers, librarians, and learning technologists mapped Jisc competencies to a higher number of IL facets is an interesting insight not explored in the literature. Should this finding prove transferrable through further research, either through replication studies or studies into the language of DL, then this may be an important finding given the prominence of the Jisc framework in my sample UK universities.

The workshops also provided a novel insight into the language of IL and DL from the perspective of the participants. Other than how the broader terms of IL and DL are constructed (Wuyckens, Landry and Fastrez, 2022), the specific language of IL and DL have yet to be explored in other research.

The final, interview, phase of the research provided new understanding of how lecturers construct their knowledge of IL and DL. That the lecturers in my sample struggled with the language of digital competence and IL facets challenges the push

to assess the level of digital competence in university lecturers which is, of course, something that I initially aimed to do. Some of my interview themes were seen within my rapid review and this, therefore, challenges the lack of progress in this field of research and questions why the same gaps in the literature are still occurring many years after they were initially noted. My finding that this sample of lecturers are confused by the language of frameworks is novel; this level of granularity has not been seen beyond exploration of the broader terms of IL and DL, as noted above. Confusion in language and terminology not only provides a point of reflection to framework creators and those utilising them, but compounds efforts by universities and professional services to develop effective DL strategies and support the development of lecturer digital competence.

8.3 Implications for professional practice

In line with the expectations of a Professional Doctorate, there are a number of implications for professional practice following from the findings. As Zhao, Pinto Llorente and Sánchez Gómez (2021) observe, teaching in the light of the COVID-19 pandemic had dramatically changed, and the topic of this thesis has been brought to the fore. As such the implications from this research are of paramount importance to universities. The following implications are categorised for universities, those working within universities, for framework developers, and for people in this field of research. The implications themselves are listed in no particular order.

8.3.1 Implications for university strategy and policy

The scoping exercise revealed the dominance of the Jisc digital literacy framework in the UK university sector. The finding that sampled lecturers found this framework the least easy to interpret shows that it is important to look beyond Jisc framework, especially as there is now a framework specifically designed for educators in DigCompEdu.

That lecturers, librarians, and learning technologists in my sample cannot agree on the terminology of IL and DL, and that lecturers construct their knowledge of IL and DL in a highly individualised manner, shows the importance of differing perspectives, especially when considering curricula and staff development.

Some of the lecturers, themselves experts in digital literacy, found the pace of change and utilisation of digital tools overwhelming. Universities should reflect upon

the wellbeing of lecturers and expand support measures for staff, especially as a result of the change in technology utilisation and working practices brought about by the COVID-19 pandemic.

8.3.2 Implications for professional services

I found that my participant lecturers were more focussed on students rather than planning their own development, only identifying gaps in their knowledge when a need arose. This finding provides a challenge for professional service staff being able to provide rapid support for lecturers when a need arises. There is also the challenge of enabling longer-term planning for lecturers both in terms of their own development and how future technologies and pedagogies may influence the competencies required in future.

Where training is provided, professional service staff should note that peer acquisition of knowledge was valued by this sample of lecturers. Professional service staff should consider how they support peer acquisition of knowledge, perhaps instead of or in addition to the top-down, technology-centred manner, that has historically been employed.

Indeed, I noted research stating that training for digital tools has traditionally been centred on the technology itself. The finding in my rapid review and interviews that adoption of technology by lecturers is centred on pedagogical considerations opposes this traditional model of training and should provide a point of reflection on professional service staff.

The same pedagogical construction of digital competence in lecturers highlights the requirement to move from a digital environment that forces lecturers to “conform” (Ertmer and Ottenbreit-Leftwich, 2010, p.264) to one that provides flexibility for lecturers to utilise the most pedagogically appropriate technologies.

8.3.3 Implications for future research and framework developers

Of the three DL frameworks in the workshop phase of the research, participants found the DigComp framework easiest to read and interpret. Further research on lecturer perceptions of DigCompEdu and DigComp 2.2 would provide insight as to whether these frameworks would be suitable for UK universities and lecturer professional development.

Relatedly, the findings from this study have provided insights into the terminology of IL and DL frameworks, but also shown how this terminology can “*freak out*” some lecturers. Research into the perspectives of framework users may enable the next generation of frameworks to become more user friendly and relatable.

My research focussed on expert users. There is related research into early adopters of technology (Bennett, 2014). Further research on those with lower levels of digital competence would offer a more detailed picture of digital competence in university lecturers.

I further noted that the same gaps in the literature are continually being noted and not filled. A lack of standardised (Gumanová and Šukolová, 2022) and validated tools (Zhao, Pinto Llorente and Sánchez Gómez, 2021) hinders development of this field of research. Future research that seeks to develop standardised and validated tools, coupled with longitudinal research (a gap noted by Connaway et al., 2013) will provide further insights into lecturer digital competence.

8.4 Summary of limitations

The limitations of this study have been interwoven throughout the methods, findings, and discussion chapters of this thesis. To aid critical appraisal of this research, I have summarised the main limitations from each of the phases as detailed below.

8.4.1 Limitations from Phase 1

- The sample of digital literacy frameworks was drawn from ten UK universities (7.6% of UK public universities at the time of the research). I was looking for an indication of frameworks used, not representativeness.
- My development of an IL framework as an individual can be considered a limitation, but there is similar precedent among other researchers and methodological alignment. There is a risk, however, that my position could add an element of conceptual bias to the distillation process, where an error is made on the part of the researcher and the research problem is misinterpreted or concluded.

8.4.2 Limitations from Phase 2

- Lecturers were sampled from two convenience sampled UK universities. This was a pragmatic step as I understood the cultures in both universities, thereby

potentially making findings easier to contextualise. A larger sample of universities would have enhanced the transferability of the study but would have been less practical within the scope of this research.

- I objectively sampled participants. Participants with knowledge of IL and DL would be more likely to be able to actively participate in the workshop exercise and reflect upon their knowledge and experiences. A random sample of participants may not have achieved the same level of reflection and participation.
- Participants were not able to see the order in which the competencies were presented in the frameworks nor able to read the introduction to the framework that may have provided additional contextual information. This lack of context may have hindered their understanding of the competencies without that wider context.

8.4.3 Limitations from Phase 3

- The interviews were conducted with eight lecturers from two UK universities. Larger samples may have produced different themes and findings.

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10 Appendices

Appendix 1: Rapid review search strategies

Source: Web of Science Core Collection

Indexes: SCI-EXPANDED, SSCI, A&HCI, CPCI-S, CPCI-SSH, BKCI-S, BKCI-SSH, ESCI

Interface: N/A

Database coverage dates: 1900 to date

Search date: 29 December 2018

Records retrieved: 85

Search strategy:

TOPIC: ((lecturer* or (university near/2 teach*))) AND TOPIC: ("digital literac*" or "digital competen*" or "digital capabilit*" or "digital capacity" or "digital skill*")

Source: Scopus

Interface: N/A

Database coverage dates: 1788 to date

Search date: 29 December 2018

Records retrieved: 45

Search strategy:

TITLE-ABS((lecturer* or (university near/2 teach*)) AND ("digital literac*" or "digital competen*" or "digital capabilit*" or "digital capacity" or "digital skill*"))

Source: Applied Social Sciences Index and Abstracts (ASSIA)

Interface: ProQuest

Database coverage dates: Not known

Search date: 29 December 2018

Records retrieved: 2

Search strategy:

TI((lecturer* OR (university n/2 teach*)) AND ("digital literac*" OR "digital competen*" OR "digital capabilit*" OR "digital capacity" OR "digital skill*")) or AB((lecturer* OR (university n/2 teach*)) AND ("digital literac*" OR "digital competen*" OR "digital capabilit*" OR "digital capacity" OR "digital skill*"))

Source: Education Resource Information Center (ERIC)

Interface: EBSCOhost

Database coverage dates: 1966

Search date: 29 December 2018

Records retrieved: 18

Search strategy:

TI (((lecturer* or (university n2 teach*)) AND ("digital literac*" or "digital competen*" or "digital capabilit*" or "digital capacity" or "digital skill*"))) OR AB (((lecturer* or (university n2 teach*)) AND ("digital literac*" or "digital competen*" or "digital capabilit*" or "digital capacity" or "digital skill*")))

Source: Sociological Abstracts

Interface: ProQuest

Database coverage dates: 1952

Search date: 29 December 2018

Records retrieved: 0

Search strategy:

TI((lecturer* OR (university n/2 teach*)) AND ("digital literac*" OR "digital competen*" OR "digital capabilit*" OR "digital capacity" OR "digital skill*")) or AB((lecturer* OR (university n/2 teach*)) AND ("digital literac*" OR "digital competen*" OR "digital capabilit*" OR "digital capacity" OR "digital skill*"))

Source: British Education Index

Interface: EBSCOhost

Database coverage dates: 1929

Search date: 29 December 2018

Records retrieved: 1

Search strategy:

TI (((lecturer* or (university n2 teach*)) AND ("digital literac*" or "digital competen*" or "digital capabilit*" or "digital capacity" or "digital skill*"))) OR AB (((lecturer* or (university n2 teach*)) AND ("digital literac*" or "digital competen*" or "digital capabilit*" or "digital capacity" or "digital skill*")))

Source: Australian Education Index

Interface: ProQuest

Database coverage dates: 1978

Search date: 29 December 2018

Records retrieved: 5

Search strategy:

TI((lecturer* OR (university n/2 teach*)) AND ("digital literac*" OR "digital competen*" OR "digital capabilit*" OR "digital capacity" OR "digital skill*")) or AB((lecturer* OR

(university n/2 teach*) AND ("digital literac*" OR "digital competen*" OR "digital capabilit*" OR "digital capacity" OR "digital skill*"))

Source: Library & Information Science Abstracts (LISA)

Interface: ProQuest

Database coverage dates: Not known

Search date: 29 December 2018

Records retrieved: 4

Search strategy:

TI((lecturer* OR (university n/2 teach*)) AND ("digital literac*" OR "digital competen*" OR "digital capabilit*" OR "digital capacity" OR "digital skill*")) or AB((lecturer* OR (university n/2 teach*)) AND ("digital literac*" OR "digital competen*" OR "digital capabilit*" OR "digital capacity" OR "digital skill*"))

Appendix 2: PRISMA flow diagram

Flow diagram adapted from Moher *et al.* (2009).

¹ When the full text of a paper was unavailable, inter-library loans and direct contact with authors was attempted. In three instances these methods did not result in the full text being made available to me.

Appendix 3: Workshop participant recruitment email

Dear [Title] [Name],

I am contacting you in my capacity as a Professional Doctorate candidate at the University of the West of Scotland.

I am conducting research on the digital competencies of university lecturers. Through your [name of research repository] profile, I have identified you as someone with knowledge of, or prior experience of using digital literacy frameworks or digital technology within your teaching, and would like to invite you to participate in a multi-profession workshop that will thematically explore the skills required by lecturers to be considered digitally competent.

You are under no obligation to participate and if you chose to, may freely withdraw from the workshop prior to them starting, or within the workshop itself, without reason or without any negative consequences. I would be grateful if you could inform me whether you wish to participate within the next 10 days.

Further information on the research study can be found in the attached participant information sheet and consent form. If you have any questions about this study, please talk to Paul Cannon on [phone number] or [email address].

Yours sincerely,

Paul.

Paul Cannon

[email signature]

Appendix 4: Workshop participant information sheet

Participant Information Sheet

An investigation into the digital competencies of university lecturers

What is this research study about?

- 1 There is a large gap in the literature on the digital competencies of lecturers.
- 2 Students have reported that technology helps engage them with their learning, but they are concerned about the ICT competencies of lecturers.
- 3 There is a perception of a variable, but a generally low level of digital competence amongst lecturers. These perceptions need to be tested.
- 4 A benchmark of digital competence amongst lecturers will benefit universities in their strategic planning and academic development activities.

What are the aims of this research study?

To develop a benchmark of digital competence among university lecturers. The objectives of the research are to:

- 5 compile and critically analyse the existing literature on digital competency, literacy and capacity, and attempt to define the three terms,
- 6 thematically analyse the competencies university lecturers need to be digitally competent,
- 7 facilitate workshops to form a multi-professional approach to the competencies university lecturers need to be digitally competent,
- 8 transcribe the identified competencies into a quantitative questionnaire, and
- 9 distribute the questionnaire to lecturers across a lecturer sample.

Why I am inviting you to take part in this research study?

Digital competencies are of interest to various professions within the university sector. As someone identified with knowledge of, or prior experience of using digital literacy frameworks or digital technology within your teaching, you are invited to participate in a multi-profession workshop that will thematically explore the skills required by lecturers to be considered digitally competent.

What would taking part involve?

- 1 Workshop participants will work in multi-disciplinary teams.
- 2 Participants will be asked to analyse three digital literacy frameworks to discover the competencies that underlie each facet.
- 3 Participants will be asked to reflect on the researcher's analysis of the above task.
- 4 A peer-debrief will take place at the end of each workshop where participants will be able to feedback on the workshop process or offer further commentary.
- 5 It is expected that the workshop will last one hour, however, two hours will be scheduled should participants wish to carry on discussions.
- 6 Lunch will be provided – please inform the researcher of any dietary requirements.

What are the potential benefits of taking part?

- 7 Participants will gain the opportunity to partake in multi-professional discussion on a key topic within their individual professions and university strategies.
- 8 At the end of the research project, anonymised data will be presented to the Head/Dean of School, research participants and the wider academic community through publication and applications to present at learning and teaching conferences.
- 9 Learning objects, based on the research findings will be created to enable lecturers to understand digital competence and methods to increase their levels of digital competence, a key post-publication outcome of this research study.

What are the possible disadvantages and risks of taking part?

- 10 The disadvantages and risks of participating are minimal. All data collected will be anonymised to general job roles, i.e. lecturer.
- 11 You may withdraw freely from the study prior to the workshop and within the workshop itself. However, all data collected within the workshop will be anonymised and, therefore, not able to be redacted.

How do I contact you if I have any questions?

If you have any questions about this study, please talk to Paul Cannon on [REDACTED]

[REDACTED]

Personal details withheld.

Appendix 5: Workshop consent form

Participant consent form

Title of study: An investigation into the digital competencies of university lecturers

Name of researcher: Paul Cannon

Please initial box

I have understood the participant information sheet.

I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time, without reason or without any negative consequences.

I understand that all data collected is anonymised and that if I withdraw it will not be possible for data already collected to be withdrawn.

I understand that I can decline to answer any question or questions, or to not partake in any of the workshop activities.

I understand that all responses will be kept confidential and all data will be stored securely for a period of five years.

I give permission for anonymised data to be shared on an openly available data repository.

I give permission for the researcher to re-use my data for future research as specified above.

Any questions I have with respect to the study and consent have been satisfactorily answered by the researcher.

Name of participant _____

Date _____

Signature _____

Appendix 6: Letter of ethical approval for the study

21/09/2018

Dear Paul Cannon,

Your application 1756: An investigation into the digital competencies of university lecturers, submission 3945, has been approved by the Health Nursing and Midwifery SEC. You may now proceed with your study. If you wish to make any significant changes to the study you must seek the committee's approval before actioning them.

Applicants are reminded to ensure that all required approvals, access permissions and risk assessments are in place before research begins.

Good luck with your research.

Personal details withheld.

Dr W MacKay

Appendix 7: Email stating approval for study at University B

From: [Gatekeeper at University B]

Sent: 12 January 2018 14:31

To: Paul Cannon

Subject: Re: Permission to contact School of [School name] lecturers for research study

Dear Paul,

Many thanks for your message. I've no doubt our staff will be keen to participate in this interesting work and I'm delighted to approve your request.

Please keep me apprised of your progress for my own edification!

With best wishes,

[Name of gatekeeper]

On 12 Jan 2018, at 14:26, Paul Cannon <[email address]> wrote:

Dear [Name of gatekeeper],

I am [name of job role]. I am, however, contacting you in my capacity as a Professional Doctorate candidate at the University of the West of Scotland.

I am conducting research on the digital competencies of university lecturers and would like to ask for your assistance in facilitating access to School of [School name].

There is a large gap in the literature on the digital competencies of academic staff. My study aims to take a multi-professional approach to defining the competencies that university lecturers need to become digitally competent. A thematic analysis of the predominant digital literacy frameworks within UK universities will be undertaken, followed by a workshop with key stakeholders in digital competence amongst universities; librarians, learning technologists, and lecturers.

The result of the thematic analysis will bring a novel multi-professional approach to digital competence. The competencies identified will be transcribed into a

quantitative questionnaire that will be distributed to university lecturers across two UK university Health Schools – the School of [School name] being one – allowing a benchmark of digital competence of university lecturers to be formed.

At the end of the research project, anonymised data will be presented to you and the other university's [Gatekeeper], all research participants and the wider academic community through publication and applications to present at learning and teaching conferences. Learning objects, based on the research findings will be created to enable lecturers to understand digital competence and methods to increase their levels of digital competence, a key post-publication outcome of this research study. These learning objects will be licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license, allowing both participating universities and the wider academic community to benefit from the research.

My [University B] sample will include a workshop with four librarians, two learning technologists and six lecturers, of which I have identified two potential lecturer participants within the School of [School name]. Each workshop will last one hour, although two hours will be allocated to room booking should discussions overrun. Following the workshop, one learning technologist and one lecturer, both of whom will not have partaken in the focus group, will be invited to test a quantitative questionnaire designed to measure the digital competence levels of university lecturers.

The questionnaire will take no longer than ten minutes to complete – although testers will be asked to take additional time to critically reflect on the questionnaire construction.

Lastly, I would like to distribute the tested questionnaire to all teaching and research and teaching lecturers across the School of [School name].

I would like to request your permission to contact my research study samples, as well as your permission to contact [School name] Human Resources to identify lecturers on teaching and research and teaching contracts within the School of [School name] that the correct staff are sampled for the questionnaire distribution. The research study has been granted ethical clearance by the School of Health, Nursing and Midwifery Ethics Committee at the University of the West of Scotland. Details of the ethics form are attached to this letter.

I hope that you find the attached project of interest and will be willing to help me recruit participants through your School. Please feel free to contact me if you have

any questions.

Yours sincerely,

Paul.

[Email signature]

<SEC Outcome Letter.docx><UWS ethics approval application form v1.1.docx>

Appendix 8: Responses to the “15-point checklist of criteria for good thematic analysis”

Process	No.	Response to criteria
Transcription	1	The data have been transcribed to an appropriate level. The automated Zoom transcription was checked, in detail, for each interview and edited appropriately. I included pauses, “erms” and “ahs” to provide a faithful reproduction, which then aided analysis of the true responses by participants.
Coding	2	Each data item was given equal attention in the coding process by employing a coding process that read down the transcripts (from start of the interview to the end) and across the transcripts (coding each question in turn e.g., question 1 by participant A, question 1 by participant B, etc. question 2 by participant A, question 2 by participant B, etc.)
	3	Themes have not been generated from a few vivid examples. My NVivo coding structure can be accessed at https://dx.doi.org/10.5255/UKDA-SN-855937 . Sub-themes were generated throughout each interview. These were then collated under thematic headings to provide a thorough, inclusive, and comprehensive analysis.
	4	All relevant extracts generated for each were collated under the coding structure detailed in response to No. 3.
	5	Themes and sub-themes were cross-referenced against each other and, in some cases, sub-themes were removed from a thematic heading or moved to another more appropriate heading. Some sub-themes were combined when checking back to the original dataset.
	6	My coding structure provides a coherent pattern of analysis where themes are distinct from each other, with a consistent method applied throughout the coding process.
Analysis	7	The interview data analysis provides a collation of genuine responses by participants that represent the themes I generated. My methodological stance reinforces the central position of my analysis of the data, rather than the data being paraphrased or described.
	8	The extracts that I have chosen are illustrative of the wider theme to which they were coded. The interview transcripts are available at https://dx.doi.org/10.5255/UKDA-SN-855937 , to allow scrutiny and avoid selective coding and quotation.

Process	No.	Response to criteria
	9	My analysis provides a structured argument as to how university lecturers construct their knowledge of information and digital literacy. Some themes were identified in the rapid review, but there was nearly two years between conducting the review and the coding and analysis of the interview transcripts; sufficient time for the review to not bias my thinking as I undertook the analysis.
	10	My analysis provides an appropriate balance between narrative and extracts, using both short, illustrative extracts and longer detailed examples to elucidate my analysis.
Overall	11	Enough time was allocated to complete all phases of the analysis adequately. The transcription editing process took over two months to complete. The coding process took a further two months, and the analysis an additional two months.
Written report	12	My methodological approach and thematic analysis method have been clearly described throughout the thesis, including why these approaches and methods were employed over other options.
	13	I believe that the thematic analysis is consistent between what I have said I will do (see response to No. 12) and the overall reported analysis (see responses to No. 7-11).
	14	Similar to my response to No. 13, the language and concepts used in my thesis are consistent with my epistemological position of the analysis.
	15	I have positioned myself as active in the research process and that the themes I generated are a result of my analysis (which is partly why I have adopted an 'Open Data' approach so that others can generate their own themes from the data).

Table 28. Responses to the "15-point checklist of criteria for good thematic analysis" adapted from Braun and Clarke (2006, p.96)

Appendix 9: Interview participant recruitment email

Dear [Title] [Name],

I am contacting you in my capacity as a Professional Doctorate candidate at the University of the West of Scotland.

I am conducting research on the digital competencies of university lecturers. To date the research has looked at the competencies required by lecturers to be considered digitally competent. This next phase of the research will focus on how lecturers interpret digital and information competencies.

Through your [research repository] profile, I have identified you as someone with knowledge of, or prior experience of using digital literacy frameworks or digital technology within your teaching. I would therefore like to invite you to participate in an interview to discuss your interpretation and use of digital and information competencies. The interview will take place via Zoom and will last no longer than one hour.

You are under no obligation to participate and, if you choose to participate, may freely withdraw from the interview prior to it starting or within the interview itself, without reason or without any negative consequences. I would be grateful if you could inform me whether you wish to participate within the next 10 days.

Further information on the research study can be found in the attached participant information sheet and consent form. If you have any questions about this study, please do let me know.

Yours sincerely,

Paul.

Paul Cannon

[email signature]

Appendix 10: Interview consent form

Participant Consent Form

Title of study: An investigation into the digital competencies of university lecturers

Name of researcher: Paul Cannon

Please initial box

I have understood the participant information sheet, and any questions I have about the study and consent have been satisfactorily answered.

I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time, without reason or without any negative consequences.

I understand that all data collected is anonymised and that if I withdraw it will not be possible to retract collected data.

I understand that I can decline to answer any questions.

I understand that all responses will be kept confidential and all data will be stored securely for a period of five years.

I give permission for the researcher to record the interview.

I give permission for anonymised data to be shared on an openly available data repository, including a transcript of the recording.

I give permission for the researcher to re-use my data for future research within the timescale specified above.

Name of participant _____

Date _____

Signature _____

Name of researcher _____

Date _____

Appendix 11: Interview participant information sheet

Participant Information Sheet

An investigation into the digital competencies of university lecturers

Do I need to take part in this study?

No. Before you decide to participate, it is important that you understand why the research is being conducted and what participating will involve. Please carefully read the information in this document and discuss it with others if you wish. The researcher or research supervisor can be contacted if there is anything that is not clear or if you would like more information.

What is this research study about?

- 1 There is a large gap in the literature on the digital competencies of lecturers.
- 2 Students have reported that technology helps engage them with their learning, but they are concerned about the ICT competencies of lecturers.
- 3 There is a perception of a variable, but a generally low level of digital competence amongst lecturers. These perceptions need to be tested.
- 4 A benchmark of digital competence amongst lecturers will benefit universities in their strategic planning and academic development activities.

What are the aims of this research study?

To develop a benchmark of digital competence among university lecturers. The objectives of the research are to:

- 5 compile and critically analyse the existing literature on digital competency, literacy and capacity, and attempt to define the three terms,
- 6 thematically analyse the competencies university lecturers need to be digitally competent,
- 7 facilitate workshops and interviews to form a multi-professional approach to the competencies university lecturers need to be digitally competent.

Why I am inviting you to take part in this research study

Digital competencies are of interest to various professions within the university sector. As someone identified with knowledge of, or prior experience of using digital literacy frameworks or digital technology within your teaching, you are invited to participate in an interview that will thematically explore the skills required by lecturers to be considered digitally competent.

What would taking part involve?

- 1 Individual interviews will take place with the researcher.
- 2 Interviews will take place via Zoom and will be recorded with your consent.
- 3 Participants will be asked to analyse a pre-selected random sample of five information literacy facets and ten digital competencies, taken from three digital literacy frameworks.
- 4 Participants will be asked to reflect on their understanding of the digital competencies and information literacy facets and relate them to their work as a lecturer.
- 5 The interview will last one hour.

What are the potential benefits of taking part?

- 6 Participants will gain the opportunity to partake in discussion on a key topic within their individual professions and university strategies.

What are the possible disadvantages and risks of taking part?

- 7 It is anticipated that there are not any disadvantages and risks of participating. All data collected will be anonymised to general job roles, i.e. lecturer.
- 8 You may withdraw freely from the study prior to the interview and within the interview itself. However, all data collected within the interview will be anonymised and, therefore, not able to be retracted.

How do I contact you if I have any questions or concerns?

If you have any questions about this study, please talk to Paul Cannon at [REDACTED] or the research supervisor, Glenn Marland at [REDACTED]. Should you wish to contact someone outside of the research team, please contact Beverley Young at [REDACTED].

Personal details withheld.